

D8.7 BUSINESS PLAN INCL. EXPLOITATION, MARKETING PLAN, AND FINANCING NEEDS FOR MOST PROMISING TECHNOLOGY

WORK PACKAGE 8

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIMS	Adaptive and Interactive Modelling Systems
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
BMC	Business Model Canvas
DSS	Decision Support System
CAGR	Compound annual growth rate
EU	European Union
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear low-density polyethylene
NIA	Non intentionally added
NIR	Near-infrared
PCR	Post-Consumer Recyclate
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PP	Polypropylene
PPWR	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
PS	Polystyrene
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
SBS	Sensor-Based-Specification
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SWIR	Short-wave infrared
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TBS	Tracer-Based-Sorting
WP	Work Package

PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable “D8.7: Business plan incl. exploitation, marketing plan, and financing needs for most promising technology” concerns the composition of a business plan of the development of recyclable packaging films for the food and/or non-food sector that include recycled polyethylene (PE) developed within the CIRCULAR FoodPack project. The primary goal is the commercial integration of CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies through market analysis and the development of business and organizational models.

The methodology developed by NTUA, includes initially the description of the technology and the business framework, as well as the development of a business model using the Business Model Canvas (BMC), taking into account customer needs and preferences. Additionally, a market analysis, as well as consumers and experts’ survey have been conducted by the partner Ecozept, in order to identify the market potential and the preferences and expectations of the relevant stakeholders. SWOT analysis has also been conducted to identify opportunities and threats that impact market integration and competitor analysis for the main technologies has been described.

The markets for recycled plastic packaging and recycled PE are expected to grow significantly the next years due to environmental concerns and strict regulations. Key target sectors include the food and beverage industry, as well as personal care and cosmetics. Challenges include the need for compliance with food safety regulations and the development of waste collection and sorting infrastructure.

Market analysis shows substantial demand for circular packaging, with consumers showing interest in sustainable solutions. However, consumer acceptance and resistance to change pose challenges for the widespread adoption of recycled materials. Marketing strategies involve the use of digital channels and participation in industry events to increase awareness and visibility of the proposed solutions.

The financial plan outlines the anticipated income, expenses, and profitability for the packaging solutions developed within the CIRCULAR FoodPack project. After the second year the operational result is positive, suggesting a gradual improvement in profitability after initial startup costs or expenses.

Overall, the deliverable emphasizes the importance of innovation and collaboration with stakeholders for the successful integration of CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies into the market, promoting circular economy and sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work Package (WP) 8 aims to ensure commercial integration of CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies by implementing comprehensive market analysis and developing business and organizational models. The identification of consumers demands and preferences is based on market research using qualitative and quantitative methods, engaging surveys with consumers (Business-to-Consumer; B2C) and experts (Business-to-Business; B2B). The sectors that create a value for business customers are identified and analyzed. The key exploitable results of the CIRCULAR FoodPack project have also been identified, taking into account the innovations of the project, the technical partners opinion, as well as the market and consumers demands. The potential of integration of the key exploitable results into the market is evaluated through the development of business models using the Business Model Canvas (BMC) methodology. The business models are developed based on the customers' needs and preferences and determine the most promising and sustainable technologies for sorting and recycling of food packaging films, as well as for producing packaging films for food and non-food products. In addition, in order to enhance and boost the market acceptance of the CIRCULAR FoodPack innovations, a SWOT analysis is implemented, identifying the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that affect market integration, proposing solutions to overcome existing bottlenecks. In addition, WP8 is responsible for the dissemination and communication of the CIRCULAR FoodPack findings, developing a complete communication and dissemination package for creating brand awareness and making the project's achievements accessible to the wider scientific and industrial community, including waste, recycling, converting and packaging end-users.

The specific deliverable is linked with Task 8.2: Exploitation of Results, Innovation Management and Technology Transfer that includes the development of business plans that are developed based on the Business Model Canvas (BMC) methodology, describing the actions that have to be taken in order to reach a successful market introduction of the project innovations. The technical feasibility of the project's innovations is assessed by identifying opportunities and pitfalls, market barriers, etc. An IP assessment is also taking place focusing on the ownership, the nature of the knowledge, its potential for exploitation, and the measures that are required to ensure protection of IPRs.

In the specific deliverable, a business plan including exploitation, marketing plan, and financing needs for the development of recycled PE and packaging films for food and non-food sector containing PE-PCRs, has been developed. The business model is based on the business model canvas and the final products have been customized depending on the production process of recycled PE as well as the final application either in the food or in non-food sector.

2. BUSINESS DESCRIPTION AND TECHNOLOGY OFFERED

2.1. Business description

The recycled plastic packaging market is experiencing substantial growth, driven by environmental concerns and the rising awareness among consumers and companies about sustainable packaging solutions. Additionally, stringent regulations on plastic usage are encouraging recycling and the adoption of recycled materials, with a focus on achieving high recycling rates. Two businesses are identified, one for providing recycled PE (post-consumer PE recycle; PE-PCR) and one for providing laminates containing recycled PE.

A plastic recycling company will provide PE-PCRs coming from household or B2B waste, that is characterized by high-quality properties aligned with the properties of the virgin materials.

The film packaging company providing the developed packaging films aims to deliver high-quality sustainable packaging solutions that will promote the concept of circular economy and enhance the environmental performance of the products offered. The packaging films are intended for applications either in the food or non-food industries. As environmental concerns and consumer demand for sustainability continue to grow, laminates including high percentage of recycled plastic are offered, being aligned with nowadays eco-conscious standards.

The core services of the packaging company are designed to meet the packaging needs of food companies, home and personal care companies, as well as distribution companies, while minimizing environmental impact. A wide range of packaging films can be developed, that maintain the required quality and properties, utilizing advanced eco-friendly technologies, depending on the final use and the origin of the recycled material. This factor offers a viable alternative to traditional plastic packaging, reducing the carbon footprint and appealing a more environmentally aware audience.

2.2. Technology and products description

Circular packaging for food products and circular packaging for home and personal care products have been developed within the CIRCULAR FoodPack project. Flexible recyclable mono-materials containing PE-PCRs have been fortified with debondable inks, functional barriers and tracers to improve the properties of the laminates and the recyclability of the novel materials. The novel PE PCR materials are easily incorporated into the existing processing lines of the packaging industries.

The PE recyclates (PE-PCRs) that are incorporated into the laminates, are produced either through solvent-based purification and recycling or through water-based purification (delamination and deinking) combined with mechanical recycling (recompounding). Both value chains can be applied either for food packaging or for home and personal care packaging. The recycled PE mixed with virgin PE and additives is used for the development of the final laminates.

Three key exploitable results have been identified in the context of CIRCULAR FoodPack project, namely:

KER No.1: Design 4 PCR, concerns the development of the laminates that are intended for food and non-food packaging. The business case includes the value chain of laminate production that also incorporates debondable ink and primer production, as well as tracer production and integration in the laminates. The data required for developing the value proposition and analyzing the components of the BMCs are extracted from WP5 Design for Circular Food Packaging, including the selection of the functional barrier formulations, the production of recyclable PE-based mono-material multilayered films through extrusion, incorporating the produced recycled PE, and the printing of tracers and inks that enable identification and managements after use.

KER No.2: Sorting and Physical recycling cascades describes the processing chain for sorting and recycling the packaging waste in order to produce high-quality PE recyclates. The processing chain includes the pre-treatment methods, recycling technologies and post-treatment methods required.

KER No.3: PCRs with certified quality regards the provision of high-quality PE recyclates, evaluating the performance of the PCRs and the compliance with regulatory safety requirements. In addition, the business case includes the development of innovative and improved testing methods for evaluating the compatibility of recycled materials with food products, their safety when incorporated in food packaging, as well as their purity.

2.3. Business Model canvas (BMC)

The Business Model canvases for the identified KERs are presented in the following figures. The BMCs are described in detail in Del. 8.5.

1. KER No.1: Design 4 PCR

Table 1: Business Model Canvas of CIRCULAR FoodPack's packaging films

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexible packaging production companies Food companies Other companies utilizing plastic packaging Retailers 				
	<p>Key Resources </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> B2B market Recyclate forums Social media and Website Personal communication with representatives from the entire packaging value chain Existing distribution channels Marketplaces Customers' network Supply chain relationship 			
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sales of food packaging with recycled PE to food or plastic companies Tax and fee reduction (eco-modulation) due to the use of recyclates 				
<p>Environmental and Social Costs </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of environmental footprint Recyclable packaging materials Compliance with European Recycling Regulation No 2022/1616 Less dependency on fossil-based sources Customers are willing to pay higher prices for the Circular packaging 				

Value proposition

Flexible recyclable mono-materials containing PE-PCRs are developed. The recycling process of PE food packaging waste, as well as food and non-food mixed waste, has been optimized, targeted to produce recycled PE with properties and characteristics similar to the virgin raw material. Depending on the origin of waste and the selected recycling and sorting processes, both food and non-food applications have been realized. The developed laminates are machinable and can be easily incorporated in the existing packing lines of the end-users, either regarding food or non-food applications. Functional barriers and/or tracers contained in the printing inks have been incorporated in order to prevent migration of any residual contaminants from the PCRs, as well as to make the collection and sorting more efficient, respectively. The developed solutions result in closed-loop systems for flexible packaging and enhance circularity, contributing to better environmental performance and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, as well as conserve the virgin raw material.

Customer segments

- **Flexible packaging production companies:** Flexible packaging production companies can utilize the produced laminates for developing advanced packaging solutions that can provide quality and innovation to their products.
- **Food or non-food companies using plastic packaging:** The utilization of plastic packaging to which part of the PE has been substituted by recycles offers competitive advantage, makes the branding of the company stronger and opens new markets towards environmentally conscious consumers and end-users.
- **Retailers:** Retailers can use sustainable packaging as a unique selling point for increasing their reputation among competitors and positively influence consumers, that demand eco-friendly products.

Customer relationship

- **Relationships between producers of packaging materials containing PCRs and end users.** Continuous communication and feedback help end-users to get the advanced and sustainable materials they need, while producers improve their products according to the requirements and specifications of their clients and respond to market needs.
- **Relationships between PE PCR manufacturers and flexible film packaging manufacturers.** These parties need to maintain close collaborations in order to ensure a continuous flow of materials and quality products that meet technical and environmental requirements, for the production of sustainable packaging films.
- **Communication with Retailers.** Understanding the retailers' needs and ensuring the product availability and high-quality are essential elements for successful relationships. Feedback from retailers helps companies improve their strategies and the quality of their products and services.

Channels

- Sales are focused on the B2B market which can be approached using the capabilities of recycle forums, social media, and the company's website.
- Direct communication between key partners and representatives from the entire packaging value chain or use of existing distribution channels for promoting and disseminating the benefits of the project innovations is also very important. The promotion through

marketplaces or through the customers' wide network along the value chain, can also contribute to the increase of awareness of the relevant stakeholders for the new developments and the economic and environmental benefits they offer.

Key activities

- **Development of PE-based mono-material laminates with target properties.** The PE pellets produced either using the CreaSolv® recycling method or the mechanical recycling combined with delamination and deinking set the basis for the development of non-food and food laminates, respectively. The developed PE recyclates can replace virgin materials in a percentage greater than 50%. The developed laminates also include functional barriers and tracers for improving their properties for food packaging applications and also make the management during sorting after use easier and more efficient.
- **Performance of laminates.** The performance of the developed laminates should be evaluated, regarding, initially, the adaptability and compatibility of the innovative recyclates and additives to the process line. In addition, the developed packaging films should be in line with the recycling guidelines and the requirements for the maintenance and extension of shelf-life of the packaged products. Regarding the laminates that are intended for food applications, their safety and suitability for getting in direct contact with the food product is of primary importance for developing advanced, high-value final packaging films.
- **Development of functional barriers with desired properties.** Highly effective functional migration barriers are crucial to be developed in order to be incorporated into the final packaging applications and achieve protection against migration of any residual contaminants from the recyclates to levels below any toxicological concern. The functional barriers should be validated and recyclable in order to contribute to circularity and sustainability issues.
- **Development of tracers for identifying and sorting of packaging films after use.** TBS tracers, that are easily washable and debondable as well as compatible with the existing sorting equipment, are produced for enhancing sortability and separation of food from non-food packaging waste. The tracers are incorporated into printing inks, enabling their application to the existing production lines.
- **Film/Packaging production.** Multi-layer films including mono-material layers containing the recycled PE, functional barriers and tracers are produced for reaching the value proposition, and develop an easily recyclable, cost-effective and sustainable product.
- **Interaction with food and non-food end users.** The interaction with food and non-food end users is also vital for determining the desired properties and specifications of the developed innovations, in order to design and create new flexible packaging films that cover the customers' needs.
- **IPR management.** Patenting the developed products is important to maintain and secure the usage of the patent and provide the companies a competitive advantage to the market.

Key resources

- **Physical resources**, which include:
 - i. Equipment
 - ii. Raw Materials (virgin PE, inks, primers, solvents, adhesives, additives, etc.)
 - iii. Utilities (electricity, natural gas, water, compressed air)

- **Existing Packaging Production Lines.** The use of the existing production line makes the introduction of the technologies to the market easier, reducing the required cost and time of the new product development.
- **QAS/DSS tools.** The QAS/DSS tools being developed within WP7 by the partner IRIS can also support the waste-managers during the selection of the proper processes for sorting and recycling.
- **Personnel.** Experienced staff with know-how on recyclable packaging or packaging containing recycled content allows for a substantial analysis of the properties of materials and market requirements.
- **Patents.** IPR resources including patents, partnerships, copyrights, or trademarks, are also fundamental since they can affect the value proposition and offer companies a competitive advantage in the market.
- **Financial Resources** are also important for investing in equipment, research and development, the covering of the patents, the salaries of personnel etc.
- **Creativity, Inventorship, Innovation.** Taking advantage of these principles, the company results in pioneering products, enhances its branding and offer significant competitive advantages compared to the products offered by other packaging companies.
- **Delivery Speed** is related to the ability of fast development and release of new products which can offer significant competitive advantages, access to new markets, and widening of its customers.

Key partners

- **Film/Packaging production companies and packaging converters.** Film/packaging production companies are important partners, as they have the know-how and infrastructure for the production of the laminates.
- **Plastic recycling companies having adapted the CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies** are equally important. They will process food or non-food packaging waste, using CreaSolv® recycling or mechanical recycling in line with novel delamination and deinking processes, for developing the PE PCR.
- **Functional barriers and tracers' manufacturers/ providers.** The developers of functional barriers (converters in most of the cases) and tracers play an important role for the realization of the totally new value chain that is proposed by the CIRCULAR FoodPack project.
- **Virgin polymer providers.** The final polymer can be a blend of virgin PE and recycled PE. As a result, virgin polymer providers are important partners in order to produce the final product (Note: in CIRCULAR FoodPack, in the food packaging laminates, the PE PCR was not necessarily blended with virgin, but used with 100% PE PCR in a layer sandwiched between two functional barriers).
- **Quality evaluators:** In order to ensure that the developed materials meet the quality and safety standards and requirements for the food and non-food industry, standardized quality assessments are required, and partners with the appropriate background are essential for the implementation of the business case.
- **Distributors** are the main contributors to getting products to market.
- **End-users** and brands are the stakeholders that will use and consume the developed products and they constitute the basis for the success of the business model.
- **Ink producers.** Ink producers are crucial for the provision of inks, as well as the incorporation of tracer marking into their products.

Cost structure

- **Equipment and facilities.** Costs for the purchase, installation, operation and maintenance of equipment are amongst the most important investment costs required for the production process.
- **Raw materials and utilities.** The main inputs to carry out the production process are raw materials and utilities, such as virgin PE, additives, energy, water, that need to be purchased in order to realize the specific value proposition and produce laminates either for food or non- food applications.
- **Costs for pre-treatment.** Pre-treatment can include various processes, such as cleaning and preparation of raw materials, which are necessary to ensure the quality and compliance of the finished products to the desired specifications.
- **Personnel costs** are also an essential part of the cost structure.
- **IPR protection fees.** Fees for the protection of intellectual property rights (IPR) are also important, in order to maintain a competitive advantage and to avoid copying the technology by competitors.

Revenue streams

- **Sales of food packaging with recycled PE to food or plastic companies.** The main source of revenue comes from sales of the developed food packaging films, that contain significant amount of recycled PE, to food or other plastic packaging companies. The increasing interest of consumers and businesses in such products that promote sustainability, and circular economy can increase both demand and sales.
- **Tax and fee reduction (eco-modulation) due to the use of recyclates.** In many countries governments and regulatory bodies offer tax incentives and fee reductions for companies that use recycled materials in their production. These reductions can substantially improve the cost-effectiveness of the project, making it more competitive in the marketplace.

Environmental and social costs

The development of mono-material laminate technology and new methods of production and recycling of PE impose certain burdens both in terms of their application and their integration into existing systems. In addition, in a social context, information and education of consumers on the benefits of recycling and of consuming goods containing recycled materials is necessary. This may be associated with significant and potentially costly and time-consuming campaigns and changes. Finally, industry must be able to offer sustainable solutions that are safe, healthy and environmentally-friendly without sacrificing products' quality and safety, mainly for the food industry, overcoming the sophistication of consumers.

Environmental and social benefits

The use of PE-based mono-material laminates that contain recycled material has the potential to reduce the environmental footprint, the use of virgin materials, the carbon dioxide emissions and the dependence on fossil fuel sources. Monolayer laminates can be fully recycled, thus significantly reducing waste. Mono-material laminates developed in CIRCULAR FoodPack project comply with the European Recycling Regulation 2022/1616, which sets strict standards on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods. In addition, consumers are showing a high awareness of environmental issues which has led to an increased demand for sustainable products.

Today's consumers are willing to pay higher prices for environmentally-friendly packaging, which gives companies a competitive advantage.

2. KER No.2: Sorting and Physical recycling cascades

Table 2: Business Model Canvas of KER No. 2: Sorting and Physical recycling cascades

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sorting and recycling companies Waste management companies Packaging converters to recycle on-site the packaging waste Packaging production companies Ink producers Brand owners 				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sales of offering services to waste management companies Sales of recycled PE to plastic packaging companies Tax reduction due to the use of recyclates 				
<p>Environmental and Social Costs </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of environmental footprint Low to zero remaining waste Utilization of less virgin materials Employment in research development 				

Value proposition

In the framework of KER2, high-quality recycled PE is produced, coming from post-consumer food packaging waste, as well as food and non-food mixed waste. The project proposes a new process chain, uniting all the different technical steps into one production line in order to produce high-quality end products as well as to contribute to the management of plastic waste. The new process chain seems to be competitive with other recycling and sorting methods, like chemical recycling, digital watermarking, paper-based packaging, biomaterial-based packaging, AI sorting.

Customer segment

- **Sorting and recycling companies:** The sorting and recycling of multilayer materials that consist of various layers of different plastics is challenging, due to the difficulty in sorting and separating the multiple layers. Mechanical recycling contributes to an environmentally and economically sustainable, however, current mechanical recycling processes are constrained by cost, lower quality and degradation of mechanical properties (Schyns and Shaver, 2020). The proposed new value chain aims to transform to resource-efficient, green, and competitive low-carbon ecosystem and to produce PCRs with better qualities.
- **Waste management companies.** This project offers a value proposition to waste management companies, which need to be aligned with relevant directives (e.g. Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives amended in 2024, European Parliament and Council Directive 94/62/EC of 20 December 1994 on packaging and packaging waste amended in 2018).
- **Packaging production companies.** Packaging production companies are required to minimize their waste and make packaging more sustainable. Towards eco-modulation, packaging containing recycled materials must be characterized by advanced properties and must be safe for human health, contributing also to environmental sustainability.
- **Packaging converters to recycle on-site the packaging waste.** Packaging converters can apply the proposed technologies to recycle on-site their produced plastic waste streams enhancing the circularity within their operations and contributing to the enhancement of the environmental performance of their products and processes. Apart from waste management, this case could contribute to the economic feasibility of the packaging converting companies, since recycling takes place in their premises, limiting the transportation and processing of their waste to other facilities.
- **Brand owners.** Brand owners can significantly benefit from the adaptation of proposed technologies, enhancing their environmental performance, profitability, and their competitiveness on the market.

Customer relationship

- A strong relationship should be established between technology providers and sorting and recycling companies for various activities (purchasing, installing, upgrading, maintaining the required equipment) in a long-term cooperation. Hence, the mentioned collaboration ensures the optimization of the equipment used by the sorting and recycling, as well as waste management and converters companies.

- A strong relationship should also be established between recycling companies with packaging manufacturing companies, in order to create a reliable supply chain for recycled materials to the packaging producers in order to promote sustainability and environmentally-friendly practices within the food and non-food packaging industry.

Channels

- Participation in training activities and projection of on-line videos, providing opportunities to interact directly with stakeholders and showcase the company's offerings.
- Digital platforms, such as websites and social media (i.e. LinkedIn, Twitter (X)), play a crucial role in disseminating information about the value proposition to a wider audience and facilitate professional networking, enhancement of market presence, and engagement with relevant industry stakeholders.
- Direct communication of the key partners (B2B) with possible clients, through the customers' network or through associations, such as the Forum Plastics Recyclate, serves as an alternative approach to conveying the value proposition, allowing for further discussions addressing specific needs.

Key activities

- **Collection of plastic food packaging waste, as well as food and non-food mixed waste.** The collection of the appropriate waste materials will determine the economic feasibility of the recycling process, and the environmental performance of the recycling unit, minimizing, in parallel, the quantity of waste that goes to incineration or landfilling.
- **Manufacturing Process:**
 - i. Pre-treatment processes (oversorting, shredding, washing, grinding and float-sink separation). Clean, separated and deinked waste enhances the recycling quality, rate, increases the efficiency of the recycling process, and leads to final products with advanced quality and characteristics.
 - ii. Recycling process, using CreaSolv® or mechanical recycling. CreaSolv® is a solvent based recycling method that can be used for numerous polymers and has been performed in technical scale, enabling to increase the overall plastic recovery rate. Mechanical recycling is amongst the most effective method to recycle plastics in terms of time, economic cost, carbon footprint and environmental impact.
 - iii. Post treatment process (deodorization). This process removes the odors and volatiles, leading to high quality recyclates.
- **Sequence of technical steps to one process chain.** CIRCULAR FoodPack project proposes a series of technical steps that are combined to create an overall new process chain.
- **Interaction with packaging production companies.** The interaction with packaging production companies can contribute to the exchange of information, regarding the

characteristics and specifications of the developed products, as well as the needs and requirements of the packaging industries.

- **IPR Management.** The CreaSolv® process is a solvent based recycling technique improving both process yields and product qualities. It is a patented technology, and the intellectual property must be protected, in order to maintain and track the usage of the patent.
- **Legislation setting the requirements.** Legislation (Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)) and eco-modulation set the rules and incentives for waste management and reuse in various applications. The legal framework sets the recycling targets and the minimum recycle content in the plastic materials. In the same way, eco-modulation adjusts fees and taxes according to the environmental impact of materials.

Key resources

- **Physical Resources** that include the appropriate equipment, the raw materials and the utilities
- **Personnel.** Human resources are key components of a business case since they are responsible for efficient operation and provision of their know-how in the recycling process chain and the recycling management.
- **Facilities for installing the equipment.** Appropriate infrastructure, location and buildings are necessary in order to demonstrate and setup the whole process chain.
- **Financial Resources.** Financial resources are essential for the purchase, installation, operation and maintenance of the equipment, the covering of the patents, the salaries of personnel etc. in order to provide the value proposition.
- **QAS/DSS tools.** The QAS/DSS tools being developed within WP7 can also support the waste-managers during the selection of the proper processes for sorting and recycling, as well as feasible routes for packaging with recyclates.
- **Patents.** IPR resources including patents, partnerships, copyrights, or trademarks, are also fundamental since they can affect the value proposition and offer companies a competitive advantage in the market.

Key partners

- **Collectors and sorting manufactures for plastic food packaging waste, as well as food and non-food mixed waste.** Collectors and sorters constitute crucial partners since they are responsible for effective and targeted collection of the waste, as well as the clearance of the waste in order to be further processed in the recycling unit. This process can be difficult and expensive depending on the collected waste.
- **Waste managers.** Waste managers play an important role in offering the waste management and recycling site and incorporating the developed technologies into their processing line for optimizing waste recycling and developing advanced recycled products.
- **Technology providers.** Technology for packaging recycling involves improvement of sorting processes, efficient and sustainable recycling processes, and development of new methods that

reduce the environmental performance of the processes. The suppliers of the technologies that are optimized within the CIRCULAR FoodPack project, can offer the advantageous equipment and can contribute with their expertise and know-how.

- **Compounders for pellets.** Pellets producers are crucial for developing secondary PE pelletized material, containing recycled PE coming from the CIRCULAR FoodPack process chain with properties similar to the virgin material. The pellets will then be used for development of laminates for food and non-food packaging applications.
- **Municipalities and public bodies.** Municipalities are responsible for efficiently collecting household waste. In addition, together with public bodies, they can set local and regional laws and regulations for waste management and can also provide subsidies or grants to the recycling plants.
- **Brand owners.** The brand owners set the rules and determine the requirements and specifications of recycled materials for the developed final products.

Cost structure

- **Equipment, maintenance and depreciation costs.** The most important expenditures are those that are associated with the purchase, installation, operation and maintenance of the equipment which is required for the process implementation.
- **Raw materials and utilities.** These materials, like collected waste, additives, auxiliaries, energy, water, are essential for the operation of the various installed technologies. The price and the quantities of raw materials and the costs of the utilities needed during the whole value chain are regarded as a fundamental component of the Cost Structure Block.
- **Cost for pre-treatment.** The collection and pre-treatment of waste requires sufficient cost expenses in order to produce a uniform waste that will be treated in the recycling plant and will end-up to a high-quality final product for further applications.
- **Personnel costs.** The total cost of the business case is affected by the salaries of the employees. The operation presents a new technology that involves multiple steps, factors, or consideration necessitating the commitment of employees that have a more advanced academic and professional background, demanding a substantial wage package.
- **Licensing of equipment.** Licensing of equipment or technology for the developed novel pre-/post-treatment and recycling processes is essential for a waste recycling plant to ensure compliance with regulations, efficient operation of the units, and assure quality.

Revenue streams

- **Sales of offering services to waste management companies.** The provision of the new whole process chain for the treatment of waste could create a revenue source for the technology providers.
- **Sales of recycled PE to plastic packaging companies.** Recycled PE is a very useful material for the production of new packaging which results in the conservation of new, virgin material, the enhancement of the environmental performance and the alignment with the continuously changing regulations.

- **Tax reduction due to the use of recyclates.** The recycling and reuse of PE reduces the dependence on the purchase of virgin materials. It is also in accordance with eco-modulation that poses high fees for the use of non-recycled PE and also sets a minimum recycled content in the new formulations.

Environmental and social costs

Regarding the environmental and social aspect, there is a burden from the addition of new technologies, that could refer to the costs and complexities associated with integrating these new technologies into the existing process chains. In addition, social costs for adjusting the local/national legislation to waste recycling may be incurred, including costs related to legal revisions, enforcement measures for reaching the minimum recycled content, public awareness campaigns, or other social impacts connected with legislative changes aimed at promoting waste recycling.

Environmental and social benefits

The recyclable packaging materials containing recyclate content contribute to the utilization of less virgin materials, the reduction of environmental footprint and of the dependency on fossil-based sources, as well as the enhancement of circularity.

3. KER No.3: PCRs with certified quality

Table 3: Business Model Canvas of KER No.3: PCRs with certified quality

<p><i>Key Partners</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Material producers Plastic recycling companies having adapted the Circular FoodPack technologies Packaging converters 				
<p><i>Cost Structure</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equipment, maintenance and depreciation costs Raw materials and utilities Personnel costs Distribution costs IPR protection fees 				
<p><i>Environmental and Social Costs</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addition of new technologies Social costs for adjusting the local/ national legislation to utilizing recycled packaging for food and non-food applications 				

Value proposition

CIRCULAR Foodpack focuses on the development of high-quality post-consumer recycled polymers, which are comparable to virgin polyethylene, that will be used for the development of flexible packaging for food and non-food products. The proposed solution will contribute substantially to a reduction of up to 50% in the use of virgin polyethylene to produce the flexible laminates. In order for the market to adopt the recycled polymers, they must have high-quality, simulate the virgin material and be characterized by compliance and safety to be used in the demanding applications. As a result, the introduction of innovative and improved protocols for testing the quality, safety and shelf-life of recycled materials is a key element of the value proposition.

Customer segment

- **Raw Materials Providers:** Raw material providers, e.g. recyclers, or plastic manufacturers, are those who ensure the continuous supply of recycled PE to be transformed into final sustainable products. By understanding their needs and requirements, the plant can ensure that it offers high-quality products that can be easily transformed into end products, like packaging films for various applications.
- **Packaging production companies:** Companies in the packaging manufacturing sector are seeking for more environmentally-friendly materials to meet consumer and regulatory requirements and be in line with eco-modulation.
- **Plastic industries:** The plastics industries are an important industrial key player that can use recycled materials to produce new high-quality products. The use of recycled PE instead of virgin materials reduces the taxes related to their purchase and contributes to circular economy.

Customer relationship

Building consistent relationships with customers allows for the feedback management and personalization of services based on the needs of each customer. Close relationships with material suppliers allow them to monitor PCR's compliance with quality standards and make necessary adjustments. In addition, the trusting relationships between packaging and plastics recycling companies help to exploit methods for the production and use of recycled materials and to jointly research and develop new methods.

Channels

The value proposition of the project can reach its target audience through actions such as organization of training and educational activities such as seminars and courses or cooperation with academic institutions. In addition, the channels that can be used to promote this product include websites and social media. Equally personal communication is important to develop trust and create long-term relationships with customers. Personal meetings, professional presentations and communications, webinars can provide experienced support and guidance. Existing customers can be leveraged for product distribution.

Key activities

- **Characterization of recyclates regarding quality and safety:** This process involves the analytical study of the physical, chemical, optical, migration, functional properties of recycled plastics to determine whether and to which degree they meet all health and safety standards for food packaging, as well as non-food packaging.
- **Characterization of migration:** Analytical instrumental equipment (e.g. gas chromatography coupled to flame ionization detection (GC-FID), Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) or gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)) is needed for evaluating the migration analyses of any contaminant that may be contained in the recycled PE.
- **Development of novel migration barriers:** Functional barrier combinations are crucial for effectively separating PE recyclate from the layers in direct contact with food in new packaging structures containing PE PCR.
- **Implementation of challenge tests for the assessment of the cleaning efficiency of the recycling processes for polyolefins:** Challenge tests are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of recycling processes in removing contaminants from polyolefin waste. The CIRCULAR FoodPack project achieved a significant milestone by demonstrating challenge tests on PE-based flexible packaging input waste, providing insights into the cleaning efficiencies of the developed recycling cascades in the project.
- **Interaction with food or plastic companies and packaging production companies:** Cooperation with food and plastics companies is necessary for the successful implementation of this model, also in cooperation with the relevant research institutions with competences in migration, product analytics, etc.
- **IPR management:** Intellectual property rights (IPR) management is important for protecting innovation and enhancing the commercial value of innovative processes and technologies.

Key resources

- **Specialised equipment** is one of the essential elements for the analysis and quality assessment of PCRs.
- **QAS/DSS tools to select most feasible routes for packaging with recyclates, among others.** The QAS/DSS tools being developed within WP7 can support the waste-managers during the selection of the proper processes for sorting and recycling, linked with the types of packaging which is targeted to use recyclates.
- **Equally important is human resources.** Skilled professionals with knowledge and experience in the production and evaluation of recycled materials are needed to maintaining competitiveness in the market.
- **Financial resources** are required for research and development, equipment purchase, and to support the company's operating costs, and for the researchers, research institutions to progress with the implementation of test protocols for high-quality recyclates.

- Expertise in recycling of packaging materials and **patents** are strategic resources that can give a company a competitive advantage. This key proposition with its patented technologies and deep understanding of recycling and manufacturing processes offers valuable solutions and maximizes the market value of the products produced.

Key partners

- **Material producers** are an important partner, as they produce the primary materials that enter the recycling cycles.
- **Plastics recycling companies** and sorting companies that have adapted CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies also play an essential role. This collaboration enables recycling companies to have access to high quality flexible packaging waste as input material and to produce high quality recycled plastics that can be used in the creation of new products, while ensuring food safety and environmental sustainability.
- Finally, **packaging converters** are important for the final product that reaches consumers. They are responsible for converting recycled materials into finished packaging products. Their ability to incorporate certified PCRs into their production processes determines the quality and safety of the final packaging. Or as performed in the project, their competence/know-how/infrastructure for integration of tailored functional barriers for the safe incorporation of PE PCRs into the food packaging laminates will determine the approval of these novel packaging materials by the legal authorities, such as EFSA (European Food Safety Authority).

Cost structure

- **Costs of equipment, maintenance, and depreciation:** The infrastructure for the assessment of PCR quality is highly specialized and therefore requires significant initial investment capital. In addition to the initial purchase of the equipment thereafter, ongoing and necessary maintenance is required to ensure that it works accurately.
- **Raw materials and utilities:** The cost of the materials required for the PCR process can be high, especially in the specific case where the company seeks the highest quality and certification. In addition, utilities, such as energy and water required to run the laboratories, contribute significantly to the overall costs.
- **Staff costs:** Specialized laboratories require well-trained and experienced staff. The costs of these professionals are quite high as they are directly linked to their expertise and knowledge.
- **Distribution costs:** These include advertisements, promotions and public relations activities aimed at directing the message to existing and potential customers.
- **IPR costs:** the cost of acquiring and maintaining patents, and the costs associated with defending them, are significant costs, but are necessary to protect technology and maintain the company's competitiveness.

Revenue streams

The choice of recycled materials for packaging can benefit its users with tax deductions. This technology enhances the utilization of less virgin PE and recycling and reusing of PE. Those who apply this solution are exempted from the high fees for the use of non-recycled PE, being aligned with the eco-modulation, enhancing the economic viability of this activity.

Environmental and social costs

Although new eco-friendly technologies help to enhance the environmental performance of the developed products, their introduction in the process line can cause high costs. In addition, the social costs associated with adapting the local and national legislation towards utilization of recycled PE and application of recycled packaging in various food and non-food products, as well as for convincing consumers to prefer products with recycled packaging may be significant.

Environmental and social benefits

On the other hand, the incorporation of recycled polymers with certified quality (or flexible packaging laminates with PE PCRs applicable for food packaging with functional barriers) into final business cases can pose significant environmental and social benefits. The use of recycled PE contributes to the reduction of the environmental footprint, as well as the reduction of waste that is promoted for incineration or landfilling, enhancing the well-being and protecting public health. In addition, the limitation of the use of virgin materials helps to the protection of natural resources and the maintenance of the ecosystem's balance. Overall, the use of PCRs promotes sustainable development and offers solutions for a sustainable future.

3. CHALLENGES

Every year a considerable quantity of plastic waste is disposed of, leading to a significant environmental impact. In addition, the use of virgin materials produced from fossil fuels, generates huge greenhouse gas emissions during processing. The packaging sector accounts for the highest consumption of virgin materials contributing significantly to the environmental concerns. In 2020 in the EU, every citizen generated around 35 kg of plastic packaging waste, of which only 37.5% was recycled (Eurostat, 2022). Recycling in multilayer packaging films is still a challenge due to the complicated structures and the presence of various additives that make the sorting process difficult. As a result, the use of recycled plastic materials can reduce the dependency on new fossil resources, as well as reduce plastic waste that is disposed of in landfills. This is in compliance with the principles of circular economy, the production of zero waste, as well as the elimination of environmental impact (Kartalis et al., 2000; Zeilerbauer et al., 2024; Barros et al., 2024).

In addition, regulatory authorities throughout the world impose strict regulations for the replacement of virgin materials with recyclates and set high recycling targets to reduce plastic pollution. Apart from this, consumers are more and more sensitized about the climate change, and the sustainability, as well as adoption of environmentally-friendly way of living. Therefore, consumers are increasingly demanding sustainable packaging options. The replacement of virgin materials with recycled alternatives enables, also, companies to meet this demand, enhancing their brand image and market competitiveness, demonstrating a commitment to sustainability.

High-quality PE recyclates market also faces many challenges. Consumers recycling behaviour is not always appropriate, thus the waste streams have a lot of inconsistencies, leading to contamination and mixed material streams. Pre-treatment processes can struggle with impurities and residue removal, affecting the quality of the final product. Advanced purification technologies require significant investment and technical expertise, which companies might find difficult to implement. Finally post-treatment steps have to meet market standards and deal with residual odors, which adds complexity and costs, limiting market competitiveness.

4. THE MARKET

The developed laminates are addressed to a wide variety of flexible packaging films either in the food or the non-food industry.

4.1. Market analysis

4.1.1. Flexible packaging industry

In 2022, the market size of global flexible packaging industry was valued at USD 248.9 billion, projected to reach USD 315.5 billion by 2027, with a CAGR of 4.8%. Various flexible packaging products, such as pouches, bags, wraps, etc. are produced from metal, plastic and paper and can be used in food and beverage industries, personal care industries, as well as in the pharmaceuticals sector. The trend towards sustainability and the increased prices of raw materials force many manufacturers to optimize the packaging materials and utilize recycled plastic in their products.

Food packaging industry

Food packaging industry accounted for the highest CAGR in 2022¹. The global market size for food packaging was valued at USD 479.73 billion in 2023, projected to reach USD 808.40 billion by 2032, growing at a CAGR of 6.05%. The volume of food packaging was 2 trillion units in 2023. Asia Pacific was the key player in the food packaging market with a share of 32.65% in 2023. Other key regions are the Middle East & Africa, USA, Western and Eastern Europe. Food packaging is divided into rigid plastics, rigid metal, paper & board, flexible packaging, and glass. The plastics segment dominates the global industry due to the significant properties of plastic, like flexibility, lightweight, cost-effectiveness, protection against food damage, as well as recyclability. In addition, flexible packaging dominates the market and can be used in various applications and has low cost². Based on packaging type, the market is segmented into bags & pouches, films & wraps, stick packs & sachets, bottles & jars, boxes & cartons, cans, trays, clamshells, and others³.

Sensitive care packaging industry

The global market size for personal care packaging was valued at USD 36.20 billion in 2022 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 10.7% from 2023 to 2030. Increasing consumer awareness towards sustainable solutions is expected to have a positive impact on market growth⁴. The skin care segment accounted for the largest revenue share of 33.1% in 2022 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 11.3% during the forecast period. The bath & shower segment accounted for 19.3% of the market share and is expected to rise, particularly in the Middle East and Asia Pacific. The bottles segment accounted for the largest revenue share of 30.2% in 2022, expected to grow, while cans are expected to lose market share. The pouches segment is expected to grow at the fastest CAGR of 11.7%. The flexible segment accounted again for the largest revenue share of 42.3% in 2022 and is expected to grow at the fastest CAGR of

¹ Markets and Markets, Flexible packaging market by packaging type (Pouches, Bags, Roll stock, Films & Wraps), Printing Technology (Flexography, Rotogravure, Digital printing), End-user industry, Material (Paper, Plastic, Metal) and Region – Global Forecast to 2027.

² Global Data, Food Packaging Industry Trends, Opportunities, Growth Analysis and Forecast to 2028.

³ Fortune Business Insights, Food Packaging Market Size, Share & Industry Analysis, By Material (Glass, Metal, Paper & Paperboard, Plastic {Non-biodegradable, Biodegradable}, & Wood), By Product Type (Rigid, Semi-rigid & Flexible), By Packaging Type (Bags & Pouches, Films & Wraps, Stick Packs & Sachets, Bottles & Jars), By Application (Fruits & Vegetables, Bakery & Confectionery, Dairy Products, Meat, Poultry & Seafood, Sauces, Dressings & Condiments), By End-user (Quick Service Restaurants, Café & Kiosks, Full Service Restaurants, Chain Restaurants) & Regional Forecast, 2024 -2032.

⁴ Grand View Research, Personal Care Packaging Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Product (Flexible, Rigid Plastics, Paper, Metal, Glass), By Packaging Type (Bottles, Jars, Cans, Cartons, Tubes, Pouches), By Application, By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2023 – 2030.

11.2%. Asia Pacific dominated the personal care packaging market and accounted for the largest revenue share of 40.7% in 2022 and is expected to grow at the fastest CAGR of 12.6% during the forecast period.

Recycled plastic packaging

The global market for recycled plastic packaging was valued at USD 28.9 billion in 2024, expected to grow at a CAGR of 7.8%, surpassing USD 61.2 billion, by the end of 2034. This market is growing significant, mainly due to environmental concerns, regulatory pressures and increasing consumer and companies' awareness towards sustainable packaging solutions. Governments around the world, and especially the European Union, are imposing strict regulations on the use of plastics, promoting recycling and the use of recycled materials, targeting high recycling rates⁵.

Materials that are used in recycled plastic packaging include polyethylene, polyvinyl chloride, polystyrene, polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate and others, such as polycarbonate and PVDC. Plastic packaging fortified with recycled content is used in the food and beverage industry, in personal care and cosmetics, in pharmaceuticals, in retail and consumer goods, in electronics, as well as in logistics and e-commerce.

Packaging manufacturers must work with waste management and recycling companies in order to ensure advanced recycling methods and a reliable supply of recycled material. The sector faces some challenges, such as the assurance that the recycled plastic meets the required quality standards for packaging, as well as the cost of the production of recycled plastic that can be higher than that of virgin material.

Recycled polyethylene ^{7,8}, (Gerassimidou et al., 2023)

The market for recycled polyethylene (R-PE) is part of the wider recycled plastics sector, which also includes types such as PET and polypropylene. Specifically, recycled polyethylene was estimated at USD 13.59 billion in 2022 and is expected to reach 34.07 billion by the year 2031, increasing with a CAGR of around 11% during the forecast period. The North America market accounted for the largest revenue share in 2022. Europe follows, with PE exceeding 9 million tons per year, and is expected to grow rapidly in the global recycled polyethylene market due to its significant production of waste plastic and the existence of a strong recycling industry.

Polyethylene is segmented in high-density polyethylene (HDPE) that is often recycled into items such as piping, plastic lumber and recycling bins and low-density polyethylene (LDPE) that is commonly recycled into floor tiles, shipping envelopes and some containers. Recycled polyethylene is segmented primarily into two grades, food grade that is designed for direct contact with food (squeezable bottles for chocolate syrup and butter, bags for bread and sandwiches, pasta packaging, water bottles, cereal box liners, etc.)

⁵ Future Market Insights, Recycled Plastic Packaging Market Outlook from 2024 to 2034.

⁷ Insight ace analytics, Recycled Polyethylene, Market Size, Share & Trends, Analysis report by Product Type (Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), and Others), by Grade (Injection, Food), by Application (Bottles & Containers, Films & Sheets, Bags & Sacks, Pipes & Fittings), by End-use, Region and Segment Forecasts, 2023-2031

⁸ The Brainy insights, R-PE (Recycled- Polyethylene) Market Size by Material (High-density Polyethylene, Medium-density Polyethylene, Low-density Polyethylene), Method (Chemical Recycling, Biological Recycling, Mechanical Recycling), Source, End User, Regions, Global Industry Analysis, Share, Growth, Trends, and Forecast 2021 to 2028

and injection grade that is intended to produce durable plastic products through injection moulding processes. The availability of physically recycled food grade polypropylene and polyethylene plastics is very limited. One example is the rPE from NOVA chemicals, sourced from natural rHDPE milk jugs. Several companies (INEOS, SABIC) are working on the chemical recycling for the production of food grade rPO.

Consumer awareness and preference for recycled polyethylene products can boost the sector. Recycled PE products become more competitive on the market and are more easily applied in various industries. Effective recycling of PE requires accurate sorting from other plastics, which is difficult due to the diversity of plastic types and their similarities in appearance. A better understanding of the properties of plastics by recycling operators could improve the efficiency of the process and promote the circular economy. Also in food grade polyethylene, there are challenges such as the lack of safe and high-quality recycled polymers, as the presence of contaminants from post-consumer waste can be harmful. **CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies can tackle the problem and produce high-quality recycled PE able to be used both in food and non-food applications**

4.2. Market potential

A market analysis and research on stakeholders' preferences, acceptances and expectations has been conducted by the partner Ecozept, in order to identify potential market opportunities for the CIRCULAR FoodPack innovations. The experts include stakeholders and business deciders (B2B domain) and the consumers include end customers of the respective products (B2C domain). The main innovations of the project were chosen and specifically the "packaging for food products" and "packaging for home and personal-care products". More details are given in the Annex I.

4.2.1 Experts

The main results of the qualitative expert interviews of Delphi II are:

- Most experts find the project and its aims interesting and evaluate it positively, though it contains many challenges. Most experts had a positive impression of the solution CIRCULAR FoodPack suggests, for both food and non-food products, considering it innovative and comprehensive. However, achieving the ambitious targets is difficult due to different hurdles like the implementation of marker-based sorting, the functional barrier composition and need for recycling infrastructure.
- The main benefits of CIRCULAR FoodPack are the integration of recyclate into packaging while meeting regulatory standards, closed-loop packaging involving stakeholders across the value chain, full life cycle considerations and the implementation of functional barriers. Its added value lies in promoting Circularity in flexible packaging, increasing recycled content and technical advances in collection, sorting and recycling. However, there are concerns about the feasibility of returning packaging to its original state, food safety, product functionality and the need for a guaranteed closed loop.
- Experts highlighted under-represented aspects in the product description, in particular legislation and the complexity of waste streams. One expert highlighted the need to influence legislation due to gaps and changes in regulations. At this point, recommendations to legislators from projects such as Circular FoodPack are considered useful. Concerns were

raised about the quality of waste streams and the sorting. Therefore, the importance of focusing on waste quality and sorting for successful recycling was emphasized.

- The experts emphasized the necessity of regulatory compliance. Key requirements for Circular packaging are functioning collection systems, effective sorting methods, production of recyclable material, and creation of fit-for-purpose packaging. Further, the packaging must also demonstrate a decent life cycle assessment and be competitively priced compared to virgin materials. Finally, accessibility and alignment with consumer preferences were emphasized to ensure widespread adoption and successful integration into the Circular economy.
- The experts provided detailed insights into the requirements for food packaging made from recycled PE, emphasizing food safety and the importance of a functional barrier to prevent any migration of contamination. They stressed the need for thorough documentation and verification processes to ensure consumer confidence and regulatory compliance. In addition, the challenges of regulatory approval and slow bureaucracy in the EU Commission were addressed, highlighting the need for adaptation to effectively accommodate recycled materials. Collection and sorting processes were also seen as critical, with concerns raised about scalability, as the collection and sorting infrastructure is poorly developed in many countries, and without collection on a large scale there will not be enough raw material. In addition, the effectiveness of technologies such as fluorescent markers on a large scale was questioned, as a great deal of effort might be required to modify equipment.
- The experts outlined the requirements for recycled packaging in comparison to virgin packaging, emphasizing that recycled material must meet or exceed the same standards as virgin material for the same application. Safety is paramount, and concerns persist about contamination during collection and the need for effective blocking of contaminants to ensure food safety. Recycled packaging faces stricter regulations and must undergo approved decontamination processes. While virgin material may be thinner yet equally strong due to longer polymer chains, recycled material often requires thicker packaging. Consumer preferences for longer shelf life and brand owners' focus on packaging appearance also influence the requirements for recycled packaging.
- Recycled PE must meet the same stringent requirements as virgin material during reprocessing, including cleaning, deinking and delamination. This is due to the risk of contamination in closed-loop food packaging systems, particularly with PE's tendency to absorb environmental components. Reprocessing should allow for multiple cycles to ensure effectiveness, with a hierarchy prioritising food packaging applications and advanced recyclability. One benefit of holding the PE in a circle lies in avoiding high taxes, which would result from non-compliance with future regulatory requirements. Collection infrastructure for separate collection of PE is considered crucial to minimize contamination. The complexity of recycling processes, particularly for barrier materials, raises concerns about polymer degradation and migration of toxic by-products. Mechanical recycling technologies such as CreaSolv® are seen as very promising, but chemical recycling is seen as a competitor due to its efficiency, reduced risk of contamination and flexibility in processing polymers. Ultimately, recycled materials should not compromise production efficiency or end product quality, and economically viable solutions are essential.

- Experts generally agreed on the importance of advanced sorting technologies, such as tracer technologies, to improve the accuracy of recycling processes. Efficient sorting is needed to distinguish between different types of packaging and multi-layer materials, which are essential for high quality recycled materials. To optimize sorting and collection processes, the introduction of deposit systems and take-back programs could be a solution. Tracer-based markers were considered very promising for improving sorting. However, concerns were raised about their cost, distribution and potential contamination. Ongoing projects such as the Holy Grail and Perfect Sorting were noted for their innovative approaches, with experts recommending collaboration to exploit synergies.
- Experts agree that food safety regulations and compliance approvals are the biggest challenge for PE Circular packaging. They stress that approval from authorities such as EFSA and the EU Commission is essential for stakeholder confidence and market opportunities. Challenges arise from new regulations, such as the requirement for EFSA approval of functional barriers under the Recycling Directive. Experts advocate adapting legislation to better accommodate recycled materials and criticize current regulations for focusing on material specifications rather than packaging design. Experts are divided on forthcoming legislation such as the Plastics and Plastic Packaging Regulations, with some optimistic about promoting Circularity and others concerned about its clarity and potential impact on competitive solutions in a dynamic industry.
- After food approval, sorting and collection are major challenges for Circular packaging. The implementation of advanced sorting methods, in particular tracer-based technology, poses several challenges, including uncertainty about recyclability and potential impacts on existing recycling schemes. There are also challenges in ensuring tracer distribution in fragmented packaging and the effectiveness of market introduction of tracers. On the collection side, the main challenges are to establish a well-functioning system and develop the infrastructure, and to recover a significant proportion of the packaging. Decontamination presents further hurdles, with different requirements for recycled materials compared to virgin materials, requiring approved decontamination processes. Ensuring sufficient quantities and consistent material quality remains a key challenge for the effective operation of multiple recycling loops.
- Consumer behaviour is a major challenge, according to the second round of experts. Educating consumers about sorting practices and the importance of effective collection and sorting processes is essential, as is raising awareness of sustainability. However, there's often inconsistency in consumer behaviour, despite a general desire for recycled products that also meet functional and sensory standards. Consumer sophistication, particularly when it comes to food packaging, is an additional hurdle. Experts suggest awareness campaigns to highlight the benefits of recycling and Circular packaging, emphasizing the reduction of plastic waste and the importance of engaging all stakeholders to change mindsets and promote proper recycling practices.
- Excessive pricing risks resistance from consumers, brand owners and processors. The consensus is that while a modest increase of 10-20% may be feasible, a 50% increase is likely to be rejected. The challenge is therefore to offer competitive prices that are acceptable to stakeholders.
- Experts highlighted challenges in selecting appropriate barriers for different foods, temperatures and storage times, as a one-size-fits-all approach is not feasible. In addition, the

presence of non-intentionally added (NIA) substances in recycled PE could pose significant recycling challenges, the impact of which on food safety remains uncertain. Another concern was the recyclability of the final product, in particular the inorganic barrier part, with experts questioning whether its presence could hinder recycling, especially if it exceeded 10% of the product. Luckily, this has not been a case in CIRCULAR FoodPack's new developed barriers, since the barrier layer thickness is less than 1% of the total laminate. Finally, experts discussed the overall sustainability of complex multi-layer structures and suggested focusing on the entropy of the whole process to ensure sustainability.

4.2.2 Brand owners

The main results of the brand owner survey are:

- Brand owners evaluated the use of sustainable packaging such as the CIRCULAR FoodPack, highlighting the importance of safety, compliance and sustainability. Opinions varied on cost and material performance, with one expert emphasizing life cycle assessment and barrier properties, while another expert focused on machinability and pouch-specific requirements. Challenges include reduced efficiency, higher costs for mono materials and limited recycling infrastructure. Despite this, there is strong interest in overcoming these issues and examples of innovative packaging solutions, such as 33% PE-PCR bags, are already in use.
- Experts had a positive impression of the KPIs for CIRCULAR FoodPack, with particular emphasis on key areas. One expert highlighted the importance of a 50/50 balance between recycled and virgin materials to meet regulatory and sustainability targets, particularly under the evolving Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). Another expert highlighted the need for new technologies, such as AI, to reduce reliance on tracer solutions, which add cost and complexity to the supply chain. While improvements in recycling processes such as deodorisation and deinking were praised, concerns remain about the impact of residual ink and odour on packaging quality, particularly in the B2C context.
- Brand owners note that production costs are heavily influenced by material choice and scale. New materials are often more expensive due to lower production volumes and potential machine modifications. Concerns about the stiffness and thickness of these materials also remain. In terms of willingness to pay, there is a general reluctance among customers to spend more on circular food packaging, despite regulatory pressures and taxes on virgin plastics. Fluctuating prices for these materials make strategic planning difficult. Experts agree that regulatory and stakeholder influences are stronger drivers of change than retailers, who are often reluctant to switch to more sustainable options.
- Brand owners agree that there is strong market demand for circular packaging solutions driven by legislation such as the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). This regulatory landscape is encouraging brand owners to adopt new standards, with post-consumer recycled polyethylene (PE-PCR) emerging as a viable option. The shift to mono-material and sustainable options is seen as essential for business survival, with opportunities in regions that impose taxes on plastic packaging. However, challenges such as high prices and low material availability are hindering widespread adoption, despite promising developments in mono- polypropylene (PP) and mono-polyethylene (PE). Retailers play a significant role, often resisting price increases for mono-material products, making it difficult for brands to manage costs. Consumer behaviour also adds to the complexity, with an incoherence between

expressed preferences for sustainable options and actual purchase decisions, with price often taking precedence. Overall, while the need for circular packaging is urgent, overcoming the challenges of pricing, consumer behaviour and market readiness is critical for successful adoption.

4.2.3 Consumer focus groups

The main results of the qualitative consumer focus groups survey are:

- Most people spoke out against plastic and preferred alternative materials like paper or glass, although this goes along with certain disadvantages that are mentioned above. In general, the consumers do not pay much attention to packaging and the food product itself is much more important than its packaging.
- Regarding packaging design, people have very individual preferences.
- Several participants seem to have a version against plastic packaging for home and personal care products, but due to missing alternatives as well as due to the relative unimportance of the type of packaging, people buy these products in the available packaging, which mostly is some kind of plastic. Refill systems are no permanent solution currently.
- It is most important for consumers to see the food product through the packaging. It should also be easy to handle and be practical, convenience is a key factor.
- The participants did not name plastic as an ideal packaging, their expectations and descriptions of an ideal packaging were very different.
- Participants of the focus groups evaluate glass and bioplastics/biodegradable packaging as the most sustainable forms of packaging in general.
- A significant raise of costs for more environmentally-friendly packaging would not be accepted according to the majority of the participants. Under certain circumstances, some participants would be willing to pay only a small price premium.
- Consumers have both positive and negative associations with recycled packaging. Purchasing products with recycled packaging triggers good conscience. Many customers have reluctance and trust issues regarding recycling.
- The first reaction of most people was negative with regard to a packaging made from both recycled and new packaging. They did not understand why virgin material was added at first sight and therefore condemned the packaging. Communication must either be very sensitive and transparent, or there should be no communication about the recycled content at all to get customers' acceptance.
- People are overwhelmed by the waste separation system. Main obstacles for waste separation in households are trust issues, confusion and space issues.

The main results of the quantitative consumer web survey are:

- The most popular packaging material is biodegradable packaging material, followed in equal measure by 100 % recycled plastic, bio-based packaging and cardboard. The CIRCULAR FoodPack packaging is in third place. The least popular packaging material is plastic.
- In the case of biodegradable packaging and recycled plastic, there is only a difference between men and women. Women prefer recycled plastic and biodegradable packaging slightly more than men.

- Consumers do not clearly prefer a specific design for sustainable packaging. They tend to prefer symmetric, recycled look, restrained design, natural colors and more information when it comes to sustainable packaging.
- Women lean slightly more towards a new look, symmetry and natural colors. Nevertheless, the general direction remains the same.
- The stability and recyclability of packaging materials emerge as primary characteristics of central importance to consumers. Following these in the hierarchy of importance are the ease of handling and the proportion of recycled material, which are considered secondary factors. The weight of the packaging assumes a subordinate role. Meanwhile, the transparency and design of the packaging are rated as comparatively neutral to less essential, which relativizes their significance in the context of consumer preferences.
- Women tend to rate all characteristics consistently as more important than men. There are no significant discrepancies in the evaluations between women and individuals of diverse gender identities, or between men and individuals of diverse gender identities.
- On average, respondents would be willing to pay about 12-13 % more for all the packaging mentioned above.
- Additionally, no statistically significant difference in the perception of all packaging types among men, women, and individuals of diverse gender identities can be observed.
- The hypothesis shows a significant, but weak correlation ($p \leq 0.001$). This result indicates that people who see the purchase of sustainable packaging as an environmentally-friendly measure, tend to be willing to pay more for it. However, this relationship is weak.
- These findings suggest that among men and women, there is a modest but perceptible link between a heightened awareness of personal environmental impacts from using sustainable packaging and their willingness to pay. This contrasts with individuals who identify as diverse, amongst whom this correlation is not observable.
- The result, with an r-value of 0.430, indicates that there is a significant correlation between consumer trust in new product developments and their perceived product safety.
- Men tend to be more skeptical about the safety of new products compared to women, and especially compared to individuals of diverse gender identity.
- The results of the analysis indicate a significant ($p < 0,001$) correlation ($r = 0.440$), suggesting that an increased awareness and knowledge of sustainable packaging are indeed associated with a higher frequency of purchasing these products.
- These results imply that while a certain positive correlation exists between knowledge and purchasing frequency for men and women, other factors might play a more significant role for individuals of diverse gender identity.
- A correlation coefficient of 0.280 a p-value of < 0.001 indicates a weak, but significant positive correlation. This means that while there is a slight association between the positive disposition towards sustainable packaging and the actual frequency of purchasing these products, this relationship is not strongly pronounced. The disposition towards sustainable packaging seems to be somewhat connected to the purchasing frequency, but the influence is relatively minor.

- These results suggest that while there is a general tendency among men and women to purchase sustainable packaging more frequently when they have a positive attitude towards it, this trend might be negatively correlated in individuals with diverse gender identities. The findings emphasize the importance of considering variations in consumer behaviour by gender and point to the complexity of the relationship between attitude and purchasing behaviour.
- The positive correlation reveals that there is a certain relationship between environmentally conscious behaviour in the form of waste separation and attitudes towards sustainable packaging, even though this relationship is not strongly pronounced.
- These findings indicate a weak positive correlation across all genders, with females exhibiting slightly higher correlation, suggesting a somewhat stronger association between waste separation conscientiousness and positive disposition towards sustainable packaging compared to males and individuals of diverse gender identity.

4.2.4 Assessment of the market for Circular packaging

- The market potential for Circular packaging in general is considered to be very high, especially for food products. The experts agreed that there is a significant market demand for Circular packaging. Policy changes, such as upcoming legislation requiring recyclability, could further drive demand. Brand owners have a key role to play in promoting recycled packaging, with consumers also showing interest if pricing and marketing are aligned. However, to assess the market potential, each step in the value chain must be considered separately, with innovations in sorting, collection and functional barriers crucial for successful introduction and widespread acceptance.
- Experts highlight safety and hygiene as critical factors shaping market opportunities. EFSA approval is seen as an important gateway for technology adoption, ensuring compliance and validating safety. The barrier concept is also cited as improving food safety and shelf life, particularly in monolayer packaging with minimal barrier additives. While some advocate expanding the use of barriers to drive technological progress, others aim to eliminate the need for barriers through ongoing research and development efforts.
- Food safety legislation stands out as the main market barrier, with experts stressing the need for full compliance, especially with regulations such as 1616/2002, before adopting new technologies to ensure material safety. Slow bureaucracy within the European Commission is hampering progress despite efforts to streamline regulations, with no approaches approved since 2008 despite positive EFSA opinions. Consumer perception is another significant barrier, requiring effective communication of product benefits to drive uptake. Ensuring comparable quality to virgin products is essential to avoid quality resistance. In addition, raw material supply, collection infrastructure development and competitive pricing are identified as key market challenges that need to be addressed for widespread adoption of recycled materials.
- The majority of experts advocate targeting large multinational companies for the introduction of Circular packaging due to several factors: their role as primary beneficiaries, their capacity to absorb additional costs and their potential to influence market trends if they support the concept. Experts suggest focusing on mainstream applications rather than niche markets to demonstrate the viability of Circular packaging. It is also recommended to focus on the B2B sector rather than B2C markets, as businesses are seen as more receptive to training and adoption. Finally, the importance of targeting stakeholders such as recyclers, sorters, polymer producers and coatings/adhesives producers in the value chain is highlighted for successful implementation.

- Experts recommend starting with frozen food products, particularly in the deep freeze sector like storing vegetables and fries, due to the low risk of migration in PE-based packaging at low temperatures. Dry products, such as pasta, are also suggested as simple entry-level options with minimal barrier requirements. Products like chips or chocolate, with low to medium barrier needs and large market volumes, are seen as suitable initial targets. Considerations for target markets include focusing on adult-use products to simplify regulatory compliance and opting for less emotionally attached items like flour. Additionally, fatty or acidic food products are deemed unsuitable due to increased migration potential.
- The experts agreed that there is a widespread need for Circular packaging and identified the whole of the EU as a potential market. However, they recognized regional differences in infrastructure and material sources. Germany, France, the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, Norway, Sweden and Finland were highlighted as promising markets due to their collection systems and material sources.
- Most experts agreed on the choice of coffee and chocolate as project products, considering them challenging but suitable due to their high-quality material requirements and moderate risk levels. Non-food products such as facial masks, detergents and wet wipes were not considered critical due to limited exposure, although caution is advised for products used on sensitive areas such as babies' bottoms. Chocolate powder was seen as key, with EFSA approval potentially resolving issues for all products. Despite reservations about the impact product status of chocolate and the sensitivity of coffee to foreign odours, most experts supported the product choices.
- Influencing factors for market acceptance are inter alia aesthetical characteristics, price, and technical performance of the Circular packaging.
- Experts consider it possible that business customers are willing to pay higher prices for the Circular packaging. However, the major driving force is expected to be needed from politics.

5. COMPETITION

Packaging and especially food packaging, is used to protect the materials from the outer environment, to limit any damage or deterioration, as well as to inform consumers on their ingredients and nutritional characteristics (Marsh and Bugusu, 2007). As packaging materials, glass, metal, plastic, paper and paperboard can be used. Plastic packaging is easy to be used, inexpensive and chemically resistant and is widely used in many applications. However, plastic packaging accounts for 7–10% of the total municipal waste and its replacement or recycling is of significant importance. Recycling of food plastic packaging materials is vital for reducing waste, saving resources and enhancing environmental performance of the packaging sector. Various recycling methods have been developed for the treatment of plastic packaging waste, such as mechanical, solvent and chemical recycling, incineration or landfilling. Prior to mechanical recycling collection and sorting processes have to be applied to produce a more uniform material that could be easier to be recycled. Various sorting methods can be used such as air sorting, flotation, NIR sorting, etc. (Ding and Zhu, 2023). CIRCULAR FoodPack aims to produce high-quality polyethylene recyclates that could be used either to food or non-food applications. The project develops a totally new process chain, using Sensor-Based-Specification (SBS) or Tracer-Based-Sorting (TBS), deinking and deodorization, as well as solvent-based or mechanical recycling processes. The advantages and disadvantages of the competitive technologies for packaging, recycling and sorting are described in the following sections.

5.1. Packaging methods

Plastic packaging

In plastic packaging, various polymers with different properties are used, such as polyethylene (high-density polyethylene (HDPE), low-density polyethylene (LDPE), linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE)), polypropylene (PP), ethylene copolymers with propylene, vinyl alcohol and vinyl acetate, polystyrene (PS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyamides (Nylon 6, Nylon 6/12), etc. (Dainelli, 2008). Packaging industry is the largest consumer of fossil-based plastics, and especially food packaging accounts for 50% of the synthetic plastics used. However, the fossil-based plastics pose negative impact on the environment, since they need a long time for degradation, as well as they can be incorporated into the food chain through the absorption of the microplastics (Ncube et al., 2020).

Paper-based packaging

The use of paper and cardboard containers constitutes an environmentally-friendly way of food packaging. The paper and paperboards are consisted mainly of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin which degrade much faster than plastic, can be recycled many times, can be easily processed and shaped, and has a smooth surface that enables high-quality printing, making the packaging more attractive to consumers (Levchenko et al., 2023; Roman et al., 2022; Välsänen et al., 1991). On the other hand, some paper packaging may contain hazardous chemicals that are toxic, such as phthalates, surfactants, abrasives, heavy metals, and hydrocarbons. Paper can also be a carrier of bacteria, viruses, and fungi (Zaidi et al., 2022). In addition, paper-based packaging may have insufficient barrier properties against air and moisture that may affect food quality and safety (Ploskonos and Halysh, 2023).

Bio-plastic based packaging

Bio-based materials have the potential to replace polymers coming from petrochemical sources, contributing to resource efficiency, reduction of the use of fossil fuels, limitation of greenhouse gas emissions, as well as to climate change mitigation (Juikar and Warkar, 2022; Nazrin et al., 2023; Panou and Karabagias, 2023). Bio-based materials have a lower carbon footprint compared to traditional petrochemical-based materials which leads to better waste management and reduction of pollution. Bio-based materials can be used in various packaging applications, since they are easily manufactured, have good mechanical properties, enhanced barrier properties and increased compatibility with various food and beverage products (Nazrin et al., 2023). On the other hand, biopolymers may have lower mechanical strength and thermal stability. The mechanical, thermal and barrier properties of the bio-based packaging structures can be enhanced with the use of additives or the mixing with other biopolymers (Panou and Karabagias, 2023).

5.2. Recycling methods

Chemical recycling

Chemical recycling of food packaging contributes to the reduction of the amount of plastic waste that ends up in landfilling, incineration or in the environment. The developed recycled products are characterized by increased properties and high value, for further industrial use. In Europe and the US, food packaging regulations require minimization of chemicals or the use of chemicals which get into food from recycled and virgin materials with the same safety standards. Chemical recycling can help to assure these regulatory requirements by ensuring that recycled materials are free of harmful contaminants (Volmajer Valh et al., 2022). On the other hand, chemical recycling includes processes that can have high cost, reducing the feasibility of the method, and can be energy intensive, requiring high temperatures and pressures. Compliance with regulatory and safety standards, particularly for food contact materials, is also a significant challenge (Volmajer Valh et al., 2022).

Mechanical recycling

Mechanical recycling is widely used for the recycling of plastic food and non-food products. Prior to mechanical recycling the materials are subjected to specific treatment processes, such as sorting and washing, in order to remove contaminants and substances that are unwanted, such as food residues. The degradation processes are not the same for all the polymers and the maintenance of their mechanical properties is a challenge in this technology that affects also the prices of recycled materials. The recycling efficiency is also dependent on the presence of compounds, such as fillers, antioxidants, blends, plasticizers that are used to enhance the properties and quality of the produced packaging films.

Solvent-based Recycling

Solvent-based recycling involves the use of solvents to selectively separate the targeted polymers from other materials or contaminants in multilayer packaging, mixed wastes and composites. Once the polymer is dissolved in the solvent, separation techniques, such as filtration or centrifugation, can be used to remove any insoluble contaminants, such as fillers, pigments, or other plastics. This technology can be easily commercialized and can lead to the production of plastic with quality similar to virgin materials. Though, the selection of the optimum solvents, the solvent ratio and the process

time should be optimized to reach a high efficiency. Additionally, the cost of the process may be high, due to the need for specialized equipment, solvent recovery systems, and safety measures (Sherwood, 2020; Ügdüler et al., 2020; Wagner et al., 2024; Walker et al., 2020).

Incineration or Landfilling

Incineration decreases the volume of waste and produces energy that can be used for heating or generating electricity. The process may result in the formation of toxic compounds (dioxins, furans, etc.) or the production of large amounts of hydrochloric acid (HCl). The neutralization of HCl with calcium carbonate or sodium hydroxide to convert it to salts or the utilization of filters to capture atmospheric emissions are usually used to limit the consequences of incineration. Also, incineration may be economically unfeasible if complete combustion of plastic waste is needed. Landfilling is a convenient and cost-effective method, however, in some cases it can cause serious environmental pollution, as well as not take into account the circularity approach.

5.3. Sorting processes

Digital watermarks for sorting

Recycling of polymer materials may need the use of sorting processes for the effective separation and the efficient recycling of the plastic waste. Digital watermarks are invisible, and contain many information, such as the manufacturer, the type of plastic material used, and instructions for recycling (Rumetshofer and Fischer, 2023; Treick et al., 2022). High-resolution cameras identify and decode watermarks included in the plastic packaging waste and enable the sorting of the waste into streams depending on their characteristics. This process requires very low energy and does not require water or chemicals (Taneepanichskul et al., 2022). On the other hand, digital watermarking can be expensive since it requires equipment and the relevant identification software, as well as standardization, but can be integrated into an existing recycling process line (Rumetshofer and Fischer, 2023). It may also need new investments at the converters for the printing of the digital marks on flexible packaging. In addition, in case of contaminations, folding, or damage on the waste packaging, the digital marks might not be recognised during sorting, since the décor print is done only on a partial surface of the pack.

Artificial intelligence (Ahmed & Asadullah, 2020)

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are efficient for sorting materials and filtering waste during waste recycling. The use of AI technology minimizes the risk of human mistakes due to process automation, requires less personnel and utilizes less energy. On the other hand, it is a high investment process with a low disposal rate. Furthermore, AI is not feasible for the recognition of flexible packaging, it is effective in the sorting of rigid packaging.

NIR sorting

Near-infrared (NIR) sorting technology allows the identification and classification of different plastic materials into categories (Ghaffari et al., 2022). NIR sorting for plastic packaging has shown significant potential in terms of reducing plastic waste and increasing recycling rates. NIR has many advantages, such as remote high-speed measurements, high penetration depth of the NIR radiation, sorting of mixed polymers, and high signal-to-noise ratio (Zheng et al., 2018). On the other hand, sorting of black plastics is a limitation of the technology. It is also an indirect method that needs calibration that may limit the efficiency of the sorting and increase processing time (Taneepanichskul et al., 2023). NIR cannot sort items that are not material relevant, for example it is not possible to separate food-packaging items from non-food packaging items by NIR, or it cannot be used to separate multi-material based packaging from mono-material based packaging, for such sorting, Tracer-Based Sorting as developed in CIRCULAR FoodPack project is appropriate.

6. SWOT ANALYSIS

Ecozept conducted a SWOT analysis for identifying market opportunities of Circular packaging:

Strengths

- Innovative circular packaging solution: The products offer a novel approach to packaging that is well aligned with current trends towards sustainability and Circularity.
- CIRCULAR FoodPack solutions offer a unique approach to incorporating post-consumer recyclate into packaging, more specifically in flexible food packaging, particularly with polyolefins, which has not been achieved before.
- Pose a more environmentally-friendly packaging solutions (LCA).
- Strong scientific and technological knowledge on the fields.
- Suitability for non-food products: The versatility of the circular packaging solution extends to non-food products.
- Suitability non-food products offer simplicity and potential market expansion.
- Awareness of food safety regulations: CIRCULAR FoodPack is seeking regulatory approval, such as from EFSA, to make it market-ready and increase its credibility.
- Closed-loop initiative: Emphasises physical recycling in line with industry preferences and contributes to a closed-loop packaging system.
- Establishes a closed-loop recycling system, maximising material life within the recycling process and reducing resource consumption and carbon emissions associated with incineration.
- Stakeholder involvement: Involves stakeholders from different stages of the value chain ensures practicality and effectiveness.
- Creation of new value chains: based on recycled polymers, targeting the food packaging market and meeting the needs of the packaging industry.
- Distinguishes itself by considering the entire life cycle of the product, from collection to recycling, while incorporating recycled content into food packaging.
- Innovative combination of technological approaches, including intermediate processes and products of interest to the market.

- Increased use of recycled content up to 62%: By incorporating recycled materials, the project promotes sustainability and reduces material accumulation, incineration, and waste.
- Advanced sorting technologies: Development of advanced sorting technologies in the form of tracer technologies helps to improve recycling accuracy.
- The focus is on working collection systems at scale and sufficient sorting, as these are key challenges for effective operation of multiple recycling loops.
- Secondary materials available for reuse with similar properties to virgin materials to ensure a closed-loop Circular economy.
- Ability to separate different plastic fractions from each other (food, non-food, or multi-material, mono-material).
- Advanced mechanical and solvent based recycling process cascades enabling in total sufficient reduction of contaminants present in end-of life packaging plastics.
- High market potential: significant market demand for Circular packaging, especially for food products, indicating a strong growth opportunity.
- There is a remarkable willingness among consumers to pay more: Approximately 50% of respondents are willing to pay approximately 12% more for sustainable packaging.
- Brand owner assessment: Brand owners see a high market potential especially for non-food applications.
- Consumer preferences and engagement: Consumers generally in favor of sustainable packaging, including the solution given by CIRCULAR FoodPack.
- Analysis of consumer preferences reveals a strong interest in biodegradable packaging, recycled materials, and sustainable packaging features such as stability and recyclability.
- Public knowledge and a positive attitude, which leads to greater acceptance.
- Recycled and recyclable plastics are in high demand.
- Suitable product selection: Coffee and chocolate are considered suitable products for initial efforts due to their high-quality material requirements and moderate risk levels.

Weaknesses

- Complexity of the food approval process: The lengthy food approval process for recycled materials is a significant challenge.
- Market opportunities highly dependent on approval by regulatory bodies such as EFSA
- Complex value chain: Complex value chain adds complexity to the implementation process
- Value-added depends on the ability to ensure a closed loop, which poses infrastructure and logistical challenges to collect enough material for multiple loops and to develop a collection system that works and causes the least risk of contamination.
- The lack of recycling systems for packaging materials, combined with the high EU standards, are significant hurdles to overcome.
- Close co-operation required between parties in the value chain
- Technical restrictions and challenges of technologies
- Uncertainties about the barrier concept

- Industry tends not to change from existing approaches as they have been working for years. Therefore, clear communication about the benefits compared to existing technologies is needed. Complexity of waste streams: The complexity of the waste streams and the challenges associated with sorting and recycling may jeopardize the achievement of predicted closure rates and ensuring quality control throughout the process.
- Implementing marker-based sorting for food packaging feasible for large brands, but there are significant barriers to adoption outside of large retailers or brands.
- Recycling challenges: Challenges related to the presence of non-intentionally added substances (NIAs) in recycled materials and concerns about the recyclability of multi-layer structures underline the technical complexity of recycling processes. Note: In CIRCULAR FoodPack, the newly developed packaging materials are recyclable.
- Contamination and inadequate sorting could affect the performance and acceptability of the packaging solution.
- Consumer reluctance: End-users are relatively reluctant to adapt new technologies
- Despite a willingness to pay more for sustainable packaging, a significant proportion of consumers are still reluctant to invest in these products, indicating a potential barrier to widespread adoption.
- Very individual consumer preferences regarding the acceptability of a change in the appearance of recycled packaging
- Cost considerations: Requirement for competitive pricing compared to virgin materials presents challenges in achieving cost effectiveness, potentially limiting market competitiveness
- Lack of clarity on pricing structure

Opportunities

- Regulatory changes: Anticipated regulatory changes, such as the Plastic and Plastic Packaging Regulations (PPWR), present opportunities for CIRCULAR FoodPack solutions to align with evolving industry standards and regulations, enhancing its market acceptance.
- Legislative advocacy: CIRCULAR FoodPack has the opportunity to advocate for legislative changes to address gaps and improve the regulatory framework, potentially facilitating the market introduction of innovative packaging solutions.
- Legislation is becoming more and more demanding in terms of recycling quotas, which could be met by a circular packaging solution.
- Synergistic collaboration between institutions: with complementary skills, ultimately achieving an integrated process along the entire product chain.
- Required technologies and know-how available from consortium partners.
- Involving stakeholders across the value chain provides opportunities for knowledge sharing, innovation, and practical solutions.
- Development of value chain components: Explore the physical recycling route to meet EU recycled content targets and improve circularity of food packaging.
- Collaboration with industry stakeholders and policy makers to address recycling infrastructure challenges could improve the viability of circular packaging solutions.
- Extremely high market potential supported by favorable policy framework and individual brand owner targets.

- Brand owners are interested in circular packaging solutions strengthened by the rapidly changing and beneficial legislation: PPWR.
- Among Brand owners there is a need for recycled materials in higher percentages, as companies must pay penalties and taxes otherwise. The legislator triggers changes!
- Leverage of increasing volumes and availability of flexible packaging.
- Consumer engagement: Engaging consumers in the Circular packaging process through refill and prefill approaches provides an opportunity to increase consumer trust, convenience, and acceptance of sustainable packaging solutions.
- Higher consumer attractiveness through providing a more sustainable packaging
- Positive consumer associations with recycling (e.g., purchase of recycled packaging triggers a good conscience).
- Align with consumer preferences and demonstrating a good LCA can lead to widespread adoption of circular packaging.
- Design is considered less important by consumers.
- Make gender-specific adjustments to the packaging.
- Relatively high willingness to pay of business customers.
- Consumers tend to prefer natural colours. Therefore, a clear color differentiation between the CIRCULAR FoodPack packaging and "conventional packaging" can be an opportunity to support the communication of the new packaging and demonstrate a commitment to sustainability.

Threats

- Regulatory compliance: Changes in legislation and regulatory requirements may pose challenges to project compliance and market introduction, particularly in relation to EFSA novel technology registration.
- Stringent regulatory requirements and bureaucratic processes can create barriers to innovation and market entry, particularly for novel technologies and recycled materials.
- Uncertainty about regulatory requirements and approval processes can create barriers to market entry and investment.
- Financial and economic viability: Limited uptake outside of major brands: Limited adoption of marker-based sorting outside of large retailers or brands can limit the scalability and impact of the solution.
- Competitive landscape: Competition from alternative packaging solutions and established market players may pose a threat to the market penetration and success of the product.
- Pressure from the virgin materials market, including lower prices and established supply chains, may threaten the competitiveness of recycled products.
- Competition from alternative recycling processes and materials.
- Resource constraints: Limited resources and infrastructure for closed-loop recycling systems can hinder the project's ability to ensure a closed loop and realize its full potential.
- Disruptions in the supply of raw materials or the development of collection infrastructure can hamper circularity efforts and limit product availability.
- Infrastructure challenges: Inadequate collection and sorting infrastructure, particularly in certain regions, can limit the availability of high-quality recyclable materials, impacting the feasibility and scalability of circular packaging initiatives.

- Brand owners: Little confidence in tracer technology and high expectations for artificial intelligence.
- Low willingness to pay more for circular packaging solutions and related technologies among brand owners.
- Retailers: Retailers are not willing to pay more for sustainable packaging solutions.
- Consumer acceptance: Consumer acceptance of recycled packaging materials and functional barriers can be a challenge, affecting market uptake and adoption.
- Concerns about the safety and efficacy of new packaging technologies can lead to consumer skepticism and resistance, hindering market penetration and adoption.
- High end consumer demands (e.g. transparency of packaging, high recycled content, etc.).
- Consumer reluctance to recycle and trust issues.
- Negative first impression of packaging made from only partially recycled material by end consumers.
- Greenwashing problem: the number of certified products makes it difficult for the uninitiated to identify truly environmentally-friendly packaging.
- Resistance to change: Resistance to the adopting new sorting technologies or recycling methods, whether due to cost concerns or reluctance to deviate from traditional practices, threatens the progress of recycling initiatives.
- Resistance to change in established waste management practices.
- Difficulty in positioning against primary polymers if the value chain does not value environmental aspects, leading to pure price competition and making market entry difficult.
- Aesthetic properties and sealing performance are factors that could influence market acceptance of circular packaging.

7. MARKETING STRATEGIES

The development of a sales and marketing strategy is of high importance for a company, a product or a technology that enters the market, since it helps to analyze the target market and target consumers, to maintain competitiveness, to attract new customers, as well as to increase public awareness and revenues. The sales and marketing plan constitutes the roadmap presenting the steps that need to be followed to achieve the marketing strategy. The steps of CIRCULAR FoodPack marketing plan are described in detail:

Overview of the value proposition – market strategy

CIRCULAR FoodPack offers PE-PCR, as well as flexible recyclable, traceable mono-material based flexible packaging containing PE recyclates, for various sectors, contributing to sustainability and circular economy and aligning with the strict regulations for minimizing waste and emissions. The developed PE-PCR is of high-quality and can be incorporated either in food or non-food packaging. The developed laminates are machinable and can be easily incorporated in the existing packing lines of the end-users. They contain functional barriers and/or tracers included in the printing inks for improving the films properties and making the collection and sorting more efficient. The new solutions offer a competitive advantage over companies that have not yet incorporated post-consumer recycled plastic into their materials or are using recycled PE of low quality, enhancing also their competitiveness and their brand identity.

Target market and customers

As described in the previous section of Market Analysis, recycled polyethylene is expected to reach 34.07 billion by the year 2031. The global flexible packaging industry is significantly growing with a CAGR of 4.8%. Specifically, food packaging industry was valued at USD 479.73 billion in 2023, with the plastic sector being the dominant one. Personal care packaging has also a significantly high CAGR of 10.7%. In addition, recycled plastic packaging sector is growing, due to the strict regulations, the increasing consumer awareness on sustainability and the increasing need to limit the climate change and the greenhouse gas emissions. Plastic packaging fortified with recycled content can be used in the food and beverage industry, as well as in personal care and cosmetics.

The target customers include the waste recycling companies, food and beverage industry, as well as personal care and cosmetics industry. The aforementioned industries will exploit the recycled PE as raw material for their developed products, aligning with the legislations towards circularity and increased use of recycled products as raw materials. Businesses interested in eco-friendly solutions for their products will take advantage of the developed CIRCULAR FoodPack products for incorporating recycled plastic into their products.

Depending on the needs of each sector, customized solutions can be offered, and specific marketing plans must be developed ensuring the satisfaction of the majority of the possible clients.

Competitors

The main competitors of CIRCULAR FoodPack developed technology are the various packaging recycling, and sorting methodologies. Although plastic packaging is known for its durability, lightweight nature, and adaptability, it contributes to pollution, takes time to degrade, and

introduces microplastics into the ecosystem. Paper-Based Packaging is more eco-friendly as it degrades faster and can be recycled multiple times and is cost-effective, it may contain chemicals that pose health and environmental risks and lacks robust barrier properties for long-term food storage. Bio-Plastic packaging is biodegradable and attractive to eco-conscious consumers, bioplastics often lack strength and stability and may require more energy to produce and higher costs for certain materials. Sorting processes for plastic recycling include various advanced methods to improve the separation of materials for efficient recycling.

Branding

A robust brand identity should be developed, designing the proper logos and marketing materials that will reflect the advancement of the value proposition, the competitive advantages over similar products or processes, as well as the circularity concept and alignment with the sustainability goals.

Marketing channels

Various marketing campaigns should be developed, and marketing channels must be used in order to increase consumer awareness on proper waste management, to disseminate and promote the value proposition, and increase the visibility of the proposed solution to the interested stakeholders. Collaboration with technology end users, providers of raw materials, as well as food and non-food packaging industry should be continuous with a view to expanding the distribution network for the developed processes and products. Digital sales channels, such as social media, websites, direct communication through emails, should be used to reach the target customers. A Search Engine Optimization (SEO) strategy must also be developed in order to increase the visibility of the digital tools. In addition, leaflets, banners, newsletters, infographics and videos development describing the advantages of developed products and processes will enhance the awareness of target audience to the value proposition. Networking with stakeholders through participation in conferences, industry events and exhibitions will also improve the visibility of the proposed solutions and will raise the interest towards waste management and sustainability. The marketing campaign should be continuous in order to strengthen the relationships with the potential clients and be in line with the customers' needs.

Sales channels

An effective sales strategy should be developed to promote the developed CIRCULAR FoodPack value propositions to potential customers. The target audience should be aware of the benefits of recycling and waste management, as well as the regulatory aspects of the use of recyclates in packaging products. Sales should be trained properly in order to effectively promote the competitive advantages of the developed solutions, the environmental aspects, as well as the ability to offer customized final products. Samples of the developed products could also be demonstrated to the target audience in order to be able to evaluate the final developed products.

Evaluation of the marketing activities

The efficiency of the developed sales and marketing plan should be evaluated based on specific indicators. These indicators could be the number of new customers, the revenue from the offering of the value proposition, the analysis of the specific market, etc. Based on the evaluation, the marketing strategy could be changed in order to better integrate the proposed products and services into specific markets.

8. FINANCIAL FORECAST AND FINANCING NEEDS OF THE MOST PROMISING TECHNOLOGIES

This section summarizes the financing needs for the deployment of the proposed technologies. Revenues, expenses, and profitability for the developed solutions have been described in detail in Del. 8.4. Here we provide the aggregate result in order to inform potential investors. Based on that, the estimated value of the PE-PCR is estimated within the range of the market price for virgin PE (0.80 - 1.85 €/kg), ranging from 1.25 to 1.75 €/kg. In addition, the laminates price is in line with the current laminate price, either for food or non-food packaging (close to 0.90 €/m²). The estimations have been calculated for an industrial unit utilizing 31,000 t of mixed plastic waste and producing finally 100 M m² laminates.

The analysis of the investment cost includes the evaluation of both the purchase cost of the equipment (capital expenditure, CAPEX) and the operating cost (operating expense, OPEX). The cost of the equipment for the PE-PCR production ranges from 12.6 to 25.2 M€ depending on the sorting and purification/recycling method used. The operating costs of the investment include the cost of raw materials, the consumption of energy and water required for the operation of the units, as well as the cost of employing staff. The total operating costs for producing the PE-PCRs range between 4.5 and 5.5 M€ per year. More specifically, the cost of the salaries is around 50,000 €/person.year (working in 3 shifts), while the rest accounts for utilities and transportation costs. The other costs, including maintenance and repairs, insurance, general expenses, taxes, etc. are in the range of 0.6 to 1.1 M€. The operating costs and general expenses are subjected to 2% inflation.

Regarding the packaging films containing inks, functional barriers and/or tracers, the cost of the equipment is around 3.6 M€, whereas the various general expenses are estimated at 110 M€. The cost of the utilities is around 2.4 M€/10,000 t for non-food packaging production, 2.6 M€/10,000 t for food packaging (Loop 2) and 2.4 M€/10,000 t for food packaging production (Loop 3), while the cost of raw materials (virgin and recycled PE) is close to 11.5 M€ for non-food packaging production and 14 M€ for food packaging. The cost of the salaries is around 50,000 €/person.year (working in 3 shifts). The operating costs and general expenses are subjected to 2% inflation.

Different scenarios were assessed for the production of laminates that will be used for either food or non-food packaging. The developed scenarios are:

- a. Non-food packaging using recycled PE coming from dissolution-based purification process
- b. Non-food packaging using recycled PE coming from advanced mechanical recycling with delamination/deinking (Business-to-Business Collection scenario)
- c. Food packaging using recycled PE coming from recycling with dissolution-based purification process (excluding sorting process) (Loop2 type, B2B, where the waste is collected, and it is known that it is coming from food packaging origin).
- d. Food packaging using recycled PE coming from advanced mechanical recycling with delamination/deinking (Loop 2 type, B2B, where the waste is collected, and it is known that it is coming from food packaging origin)
- e. Food packaging using recycled PE coming from advanced mechanical recycling with delamination/deinking (or CreaSolv® purification/recycling) (Loop 3 with TBS)

For the investment plan, we use a 15-year period as a time frame. Detailed results are given in Del. 8.4 of CIRCULAR FoodPack (see Section 4. Technoeconomic analysis). The business starts with a significant loss in the first year, due to initial capital (startup) costs. During the 15-year period, the turnover is steadily growing, which indicates sales growth. This can be realistic if it is supported by robust market demand and strategic business development. The production costs also increase gradually due to inflation. The cost increase is lower than the revenue increase, indicating a higher gross profit margin over time.

Other costs are high compared to the gross profit, leading to a negative operational result in the first year. However, from the second year, there is a positive operational result, suggesting a gradual improvement in profitability after initial startup costs or expenses. Taxes are calculated starting in the second year, reflecting positive pre-tax income. Net profit also increases yearly, demonstrating improved profitability as the business grows. For the smooth initiation of the investment, securing adequate financing is fundamental, in order to support the mitigation of potential financial risks and ensure the long-term sustainability and scalability of the business case. This financing can be provided through equity, debt, national or EU grants, or a strategic combination of these, depending on the project's scale, industry, and financial strategy.

From a strategic perspective, the full deployment of the proposed technologies may require the introduction of targeted incentives to encourage producers to invest in these technologies. Their active involvement, especially in waste collection, could reduce initial costs and support an effective implementation of such investments. Measures such as tax reductions, subsidies, low-interest loans would increase business activity on the specific fields. In addition, implementing policies that mandate participation in waste collection or require investments in recycling facilities can accelerate engagement and resource allocation toward sustainable practices. These incentives, in alignment with environmental sustainability, could make the investment more attractive and foster a circular economy, driving sustainable growth and enhancing environmental impact.

9. CONCLUSION

The CIRCULAR FoodPack business plan aims to address the need for sustainable packaging solutions focusing on the production of recyclable, high-quality packaging films that contain recycled polyethylene (PE) aimed to be used either in the food or in the non-food sector. Key findings and conclusions from this business plan are as follows:

- The business plan highlights strong growth potential for recycled plastic packaging, driven by increasing regulatory pressure and consumer demand for sustainable products. The food and beverage sector, along with personal care and cosmetics, are primary target markets that are well-aligned with circular economy principles.
- Initial operational results indicate expected losses in the startup phase due to significant initial costs. However, financial projections show positive operational results starting from the second year, suggesting long-term profitability as production scales up and the innovative processes stabilize.
- Advanced sorting and recycling technologies, including water-based and solvent-based purification, allow for the production of recycled PE that meets stringent quality and safety requirements. The recycled PE is utilized for the development of recyclable packaging films. These innovations position CIRCULAR FoodPack as a competitive and sustainable alternative to traditional packaging options.
- The plan also acknowledges potential challenges, including high initial costs, regulatory compliance for food-safe recycled materials, and the need for extensive consumer education to foster acceptance of recycled packaging. Addressing these challenges requires collaboration with stakeholders across the value chain, ongoing innovation, and alignment with evolving regulatory standards.

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ANNEX I

REPORT ON MARKET ANALYSIS

Associated Task: 8.1
Market analysis and identification of
stakeholders' preferences,
acceptances and expectations

Disclaimer

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PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of Task 8.1 within WP 8 is to conduct an analysis of the current market for recycled packaging and examine preferences and expectations of different stakeholders in the value chain with regard to Circular packaging for food, home and personal care products. To achieve this, 11 expert interviews were conducted based on qualitative research methods and 8 consumer focus groups in 4 countries (Spain, Germany, Belgium, and France) were conducted. A second round of data collection will be carried out end of 2023. In this Deliverable Report, intermediate results and a first version of a SWOT analysis are presented. The SWOT analysis will be adapted in the further course of this project.

By the first round of expert interviews and the consumer focus groups, valuable insights from experts of the packaging industry and consumers were collected. The implementation of the methods was successful and the intermediate results confirm the research strategy. Convenience and practicability of packages seem to be the most important features for consumers. Unpacked products or paper packaging are very attractive, as the consciousness regarding the environment increases. Further, the price plays an important role, as the willingness to pay more for a more sustainable packaging was limited. However, a lack of information on the recycling possibilities, consequences for the environment, or the relevance of replacing virgin material with recycled material could be determined.

The second round of interviews provided valuable insights into Circular FoodPack, highlighting both its potential and the challenges it faces. Experts generally praise the innovative approach and comprehensive scope of the project, in particular its focus on integrating recycle into packaging and promoting Circularity. However, obstacles such as the implementation of marker-based sorting and the need for a robust recycling infrastructure make it difficult to achieve ambitious targets. Key requirements for Circular packaging solutions provided by Circular FoodPack have been identified by experts, including legal compliance, functioning collection systems and effective sorting methods. Challenges in ensuring food safety, addressing consumer behaviour and maintaining competitive pricing were also identified. Concerns were also raised about the selection of appropriate barriers for different foods and the presence of unintentionally added substances in recycled materials. Overall, while Circular FoodPack shows promise in promoting sustainable packaging solutions, addressing these challenges will be crucial for its successful integration into the Circular economy.

Looking at the results of the brand owner survey, brand owners are increasingly evaluating sustainable packaging solutions such as CIRCULAR FoodPack, focusing on safety, compliance and sustainability. While interest is high, opinions differ on cost and material performance, with key challenges including reduced efficiency, higher mono-material costs and limited recycling infrastructure. Experts emphasize the need for a 50/50 balance between recycled and virgin materials to comply with the evolving Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). They see potential in technologies such as AI to minimize reliance on expensive tracer solutions. Despite notable improvements in recycling processes, concerns remain about residual ink and odour impacting on packaging quality. In addition, consumer reluctance to pay more for circular options and retailer resistance to price increases complicate the market landscape. Overall, while the

demand for circular packaging is robust, addressing the challenges of pricing, consumer behaviour and market readiness will be critical for successful adoption.

Overall, the market potential for the Circular packaging solutions introduced by Circular FoodPack, particularly in the food sector, is significant, driven by impending legislation and increased consumer awareness. Large multinational companies are key targets for adoption due to their influence and ability to absorb costs. Mainstream applications such as frozen and dry food are recommended for initial implementation, offering lower migration risks and easier regulatory compliance. Despite challenges such as food safety legislation and consumer perception, Circular FoodPack's comprehensive approach and targeted efforts across the value chain position it favorably in the competitive sustainable packaging landscape.

Looking at consumers, packaging material preferences show a clear trend towards biodegradable packaging and 100% recycled plastic, with women slightly favoring recycled plastic and biodegradable options. Consumers tend to prefer symmetrical, recycled looks with natural colours and more information. Stability and recyclability are the most important features, followed by ease of use and recycled content. On average, consumers are willing to pay about 12-13% more for sustainable packaging, with a weak correlation between willingness to pay and environmental awareness. Trust in new product developments correlates significantly with perceived product safety, with men being more skeptical than women. Increased awareness and knowledge of sustainable packaging correlates with higher purchase frequency, although other factors may be more important for people of different gender identities. There's also a weak positive correlation between positive feelings about sustainable packaging and purchase frequency. The relationship between waste separation and attitudes towards sustainable packaging is positive, but not strong. These findings highlight the complexity of consumer behaviour and the importance of considering gender differences when promoting sustainable packaging initiatives.

Based on a comprehensive analysis of both expert insights and consumer preferences, an action plan will be developed to effectively drive the Circular FoodPack project forward. Recognizing the importance of convenience, practicality and environmental awareness in consumer preferences, the project will prioritize the development of packaging solutions that address these key factors. Efforts will be intensified to increase consumer awareness and education on recycling options, environmental impacts and the benefits of switching to recycled materials. In addition, close collaboration with stakeholders across the value chain, including large multinational companies, recyclers and packaging manufacturers, will be promoted to facilitate the seamless integration and adoption of Circular packaging solutions. Furthermore, continued engagement with consumers through targeted communication strategies and promotional campaigns will be essential to drive acceptance and adoption of sustainable packaging options. By addressing these action points and capitalizing on emerging opportunities, the Circular FoodPack project aims to achieve its objectives of promoting circularity in packaging and fostering sustainability in the consumer goods industry. The market potential of the concepts pursued in the project, with the ultimate goal of circular packaging solutions, is generally considered very high.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
BPA	Bisphenol A
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
D	Deliverable (report)
DOA	Description of Action
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
PE	Polyethylene
PCR	Post-Consumer Recyclates
SBS	Sensor Based Sorting
SME	Small and medium sized enterprises
SWOT+A analysis	Analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats, and actions
TBS	Tracer-based Sorting
US	United States
WP	Work Package
WTP	Willingness to pay

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Description of Work Package 8

The tasks and results of this Deliverable Report are embedded in Work Package 8 “Market Analysis, Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication” that is led by NTUA. In the framework of this Work Package, the following objectives will be achieved:

- (1) Analyzing current market and stakeholders’ preferences and expectations of the whole value chain incl. waste management and recycling facilities, packaging producers, food companies, consumers
- (2) Setup and implement an exploitation, innovation and technology transfer strategy to protect and leverage project results
- (3) Identification of business opportunities and marketing strategies for market acceptance and exploitation
- (4) Develop a strategy or differentiated strategies to promote the industrial take-up of project developments
- (5) Create liaisons with relevant EU clusters, EU projects and external bodies for leveraging impact
- (6) Organization of information workshops for specific target groups, and promotion of the project at relevant events to increase (public) awareness on project results and the benefits to society

In order to achieve these goals, Task 8.1 led by Ecozept, provides a market analysis and research on stakeholders’ preferences, acceptances and expectations. This progress report describes the methodology that we applied, provides first results as well as an outlook (roadmap and agenda) for the next steps

1.2 Background of the deliverable and description of the associated task

The objectives of Task 8.1 are to conduct a market analysis and to identify experts’ and consumers’ preferences, acceptances and expectations. When we refer to “experts” on the one hand, this includes stakeholders and business deciders (B2B domain). When we, on the other hand, focus on “consumers”, we mean citizens as end customers of the respective products (B2C domain).

According to the DOA, Ecozept will identify potential market opportunities for the CIRCULAR FoodPack innovations by investigating the B2B and B2C demand building on the dialogue with stakeholders and consumers-citizens together with the partners of the consortium. We identified two innovations that we focus our research on: recyclable food packaging and home or personal care packaging with recycled content. We conducted interviews with experts and consumers and will continue with this process throughout the project. We will iteratively include stakeholders’ feedback in the development of the projects’ innovations.

Ecozept carries out the tasks and analyses the results, but input of all project partners is necessary at several stages of the work. The results of the market analysis will, for instance, be incorporated in exploitation plans and business modelling, thus data exchange with other tasks and work packages is necessary and takes place. SMEs and industry partners should also provide technical input on the project innovations in preparation for the interviews.

Major experts of the European packaging industry were interviewed using qualitative research methods to investigate the market potential. Based on the results from consumer and expert interviews, a SWOT analysis was conducted in order to identify actions needed for better market acceptance of the Circular packaging solutions introduced by Circular FoodPack. The final SWOT analysis will point out the process strengths and weaknesses, threats and opportunities.

We started to analyze consumers' preferences, acceptances and expectations with regard to innovative packaging by qualitative and quantitative research methods in 4 countries: Spain, Belgium, Germany, and France (as large potential markets). Special focus will be put on gender issues to understand differences in needs, motivations and perception regarding purchase decisions and after purchase behavior especially in the second round of consumer research.

Final results on stakeholder's assessment of the market and business potential will be included in the report (D8.7) of Task 8.2.

2. APPLIED METHODS

In the course of the CIRCULAR FoodPack project, Ecozept's task is to conduct several multi-stage surveys with experts and consumers at the beginning and after two thirds of the project,

More detailed information about the methods for data collection are described in the following chapters. We describe methods that were already applied, and give a short overview about the steps that will be carried out next.

2.1 Desk research

We carried out a bibliographic study in order to get an overview about the topic of Circular packaging, and to prepare the data collection for the expert interviews and the consumer study. As a first step, we determined key words on which our research was focused on. These key words were the following:

- "Circular packaging"
- "Sustainable packaging"
- "Multi-layer plastic packaging"
- "Consumer behavior towards Circular packaging"

Based on these key words we identified scientific articles on google scholar and Science Direct. Most appropriate articles were published in the journal "Sustainability". We focused on information that was useful for the expert interviews or consumer study like descriptions of the market for Circular packaging, challenges of existing multi-layer packaging, current designs for Circular packaging, etc. The results of the desk research can be found in chapter o "Theoretical background".

2.2 Identification of main innovations of CIRCULAR FoodPack as base for the data collection

In collaboration with the consortium partners, we identified the main innovations of the project to focus our market studies on, which were "packaging for food products" and "packaging for home and personal-care products". We chose the final applications instead of single technologies like Tracer-based Sorting, since the latter one is less tangible and concrete for consumers without technological knowledge. Regarding expert interviews, we additionally asked the experts for their assessment of single applied

technologies in order to gain a broader understanding. Since coming to an overall agreement of this focus with the consortium partners was challenging, there were slight delays with data collection.

2.3 Research and surveys on expert level

2.3.1. General methodology: the Delphi method

After having conducted the desk research, experts of the European packaging industry were interviewed by using qualitative research methods to investigate the market potential of the innovations of CIRCULAR FoodPack for the B2B sector. In order to do so, we made use of the “Delphi” method. This approach is a systematic, multi-stage and iterative process of several “rounds” (or “waves”) of interviews, mainly used to explore the “intuitive” (=non-documented, unwritten) expert knowledge namely in innovative and confidential domains which are too complex to investigate (Haber & Schärli, 2021; Bui, Tsai, Tseng, & Ali, 2020; Conchin & Carey, 2018).

A first round of interviews (“Delphi I”), characterized by mainly open questions and a semi-structured guideline explored the field of research. The results of this first round are expected to produce hypotheses for further refining and validation in the next round of expert interviewing,

The main principle of our Delphi-approach is a “2 steps forward, one step back movement”, the interview (=data collection) rounds alternate with feedback to the experts on individual opinions, experiences, information and knowledge and assessing group judgements. The objectives of Delphi are, thus,

- (1) to steer an indirect group communication process
- (2) to enable each expert to understand his/her own position with regards to the group’s opinion, and to revise or confirm his/her position in the next round of interviews
- (3) to obtain, after a certain number of rounds, a reliable consensus of an expert group.

There is a double core benefit of the Delphi technique, it (1) verifies hypotheses and at the same time (2) opens new communication within the expert group (Padel & Midmore, 2005; Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004).

The Delphi approach that we applied for the expert research in CIRCULAR FoodPack consists of two rounds in total. This is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of the framework for Delphi expert survey

Round	Time frame	Type of analysis	Objectives/content	Data collection method	Status
Delphi I	Sep-Nov 2022	Qualitative	Establishment of first insights about identification of market opportunities for the CIRCULAR FoodPack innovations	Phone interview	Data collection finished
Delphi II	Sep-Nov 2023	Qualitative	Validation, consolidation and supplementing of results	Phone interview	In planning

2.3.2. Identification of experts

We identified experts for the interviews in collaboration with the consortium partners. We aim for exploration of two innovations, and a number of ten experts per innovation should be interviewed, so 20 experts in total. Many experts were competent regarding packaging for both food- and non- food applications. An overview about the study sample is given in Table 2. We collected contact details by exploring consortium partners network of experts they know. We also applied the snowball method: we asked the interviewed persons to suggest further experts that might be eligible and competent to take part in our interview round and were willing to participate in the survey.

2.3.3. Set up of the product brief

Prior to the interviews, a product brief was prepared. This product brief gives a short overview of the project, describes the respective products of CIRCULAR FoodPack, as well as attributes and technologies, use and benefits. Requirements and key product information, which is necessary in order to develop and build the product, are outlined. SMEs and industry partners provided technical input on the project innovations in preparation for the interviews, especially the colleagues from Amcor, Nestle, Fraunhofer, Siegwerk, and Polysecure. The product brief was adapted after Delphi I and will further be adapted throughout the course of the project by iteratively integrating experts' needs and expectations, as well as adaptations made by the consortium partners. The current version of the product brief is attached in Annex 7.1 of this report.

2.3.4. Development of the questionnaire for expert interviews

Subsequently to the creation of the product brief, Ecozept drafted a questionnaire for the first round of interviews with respective topics for experts' assessment of the market potential of the innovations, and the Work Package leader NTUA adapted and approved the interview guideline. Those are the following ones: first impressions of the products of CIRCULAR FoodPack, requirements and expectations to a packaging from PE PCR, acceptance of the product in the industry/B2B sector, assessment of the market opportunities, challenges, target groups, willingness to pay, suitable applications, and competition. Further, results of the first round of interviews were analyzed and the questionnaire for the second round of expert interviews was adapted according to the results. The approved interview guideline contained the following aspects: first impressions of the products of CIRCULAR FoodPack with focus on benefits, added value and missing characteristics, requirements and expectations to a packaging from PE PCR with focus on safety aspects and comparison to new packaging, assessment of reprocessing and sorting process, assessment of the market opportunities, challenges and assessment on product choice. The final versions of the questionnaires are attached in Annex 7.2 of this Deliverable Report.

2.3.5. Conduction, study sample and analysis of the expert interviews

The interviews in the first round of Delphi with an overall number of 11 experts were conducted from September until November 2022, while the interviews of the second round with a total number of 10 experts were performed from September 2023 until February 2024. First contact with the respective experts was established via phone. They were briefly informed about our aim and asked, whether they would agree to take part in an interview. If agreed, further information about the project was given by a short e-mail. Participants had to give their consent about participating in the interviews by filling out a blank form on a self-administrable online form. We sent the product brief out to the participants in a timely manner before the interview appointment with the request to read the document.

The interviews were conducted by phone/ Microsoft Teams and the interview language was English. Interviewees' answers to our questions were directly transcribed in a Microsoft Word document and served as the base for our analysis. The survey sample comprised a large spectrum of different kinds of experts. The Table 1 different characteristics of the participants are depicted in Table 2.

Table 2: Study sample for Delphi II (Source: Own compilation of Ecozept)

Expertise	Delphi I: Number of interviews	Delphi II: Number of interviews
Food packaging	8	7
Food- and non-food packaging	3	3
Country		
Germany	2	4
Netherlands	2	3
Belgium	2	1
United Kingdom	/	1
Norway	/	1
USA	2	/
France	1	/
Switzerland	1	/
Australia	1	/
Type of company		
Packaging manufacturer	3	
Adhesives industry	1	2
Research institution	2	4
Consultancy	1	2
Online dispatch	1	
Union/federation of packaging companies	3	2
Position of the interviewee		
Director/managing director	6	3
Consultant	2	2
R&D manager	3	4
Total	11	10

The results of the qualitative interviews were analyzed by Ecozept using MAXQDA software. The basis is a thematic qualitative text analysis to reduce the large amount of qualitative data. The analysis is based on a defined category system which structures the data by categories derived from existing literature (deductive categories) and categories directly derived from the interviews (inductive categories). The results of this first round of interviews (Delphi I) delivers input for a first draft of the SWOT analysis in chapter SWOT analysis^{4,7} of the present deliverable report.

2.4 Consumer research

The assessment of the CIRCULAR FoodPack innovations were also examined by consumers, covering what we defined as B2C demand. In order to achieve a broad and detailed picture about the B2C assessment, consumers' preferences, acceptances and expectations with regard to new packaging solutions were examined in four European countries. An overview about the research methods and schedule is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of the framework for consumer research

Time frame	Type of analysis	Objectives/content	Data collection method
Sept+Oct 2022	Qualitative	Establishment of deep insights about consumers' preferences, acceptances and expectations	Focus group discussions
Sep-Dec 2023	Quantitative	Quantification of consumers perceptions by representative sampling	Online survey

2.4.1 Qualitative consumer research

At first, we examined consumers' insights qualitatively. We collected data from four European countries: Spain, Belgium, Germany, and France. These countries were selected due to their large potential markets. In the first round of data collection, two focus groups per country were looked at (8 focus groups in total). Ecozept set up guidelines for these focus groups discussions about consumers' preferences, acceptance, and expectations of packaging for food, home and personal care products which were translated in the respective languages. The translation in German and French language was conducted by Ecozept, and the translation in Spanish was carried out by IRIS. The focus group interviews in Belgium were carried out in French. The guideline is attached in Annex 7.3. When collecting self-reported data from consumers, the social desirability bias might have influenced participants' answers. This effect describes the tendency that research participants choose responses they assess as more socially desirable or acceptable instead of answering with their own true reflections, thoughts or feelings (Krumpal, 2013). This tendency results in over-reporting of responses seen as socially desirable, and under-reporting of those responses that are condemned to be socially undesirable/less desirable (Krumpal, 2013). The moderation technique and the structure of the guideline should compensate for this weakness.

We commissioned subcontractors in several countries for the following tasks:

- Recruiting participants
- Provisioning of the facilities incl. audio recording
- For Spain: moderation of the groups

We put out the task descriptions for tender and commissioned the most appropriate and economical companies. The companies helped us to recruit a relevant set of 10 consumers per focus group in each location. The final groups consisted of 8-10 attending participants¹. The requirements for participants to take part in the focus groups were the following:

1. (Co-)responsible for grocery shopping in your household
2. Age above 25
3. Gender as it falls
4. Normal consumers who buy normal (no special) food products.

The focus groups were conducted during September and October 2022. One experienced person moderated the respective groups, whilst another noted down the most important content of the focus groups. The transcripts were complemented by the audio recordings of the respective groups. The transcripts were the base for data analysis which was conducted by Ecozept with the tool MAXQDA. The results of the consumer study are also part of the SWOT analysis in chapter 4.7 SWOT analysis.

2.4.2 Quantitative consumer research

The second round of consumer research aims to verify, quantify and consolidate the results of the previously findings through a quantitative approach using an online survey. The online questionnaire was developed by Ecozept and was initially written in English. After the first draft of the questionnaire was agreed with the involved consortium partners, the questionnaire was translated into the respective languages of the four target countries (again Germany, France, Belgium and Spain). While ecozept provided the German and French translations, the Flemish and Spanish translations were done with the help of the consortium partners UGent and FCAC. The questionnaire was programmed into software specially designed for online surveys. A pre-test was then carried out in each country to check for linguistic and cultural differences. The feedback was incorporated into the online survey accordingly.

The conducted study was designed as a cross-sectional analysis to assess the acceptance, expectation, and preference of the innovative packaging material "Circular FoodPack-packaging." A total of 4001 individuals were surveyed from a pool with over 169m registered participants of an external survey company (Kantar Worldpanel). The sample was evenly spread across four European countries: Germany, France, Belgium, and Spain, with approximately 1000 respondents in each country. All participants were over the age of 18. The sample was chosen to be representative of the population of each country in terms of sociodemographic characteristics. The data collection took the form of an online survey conducted from 3rd until 10th of November.

For data collection, a structured questionnaire was used, comprising a total of 20 questions. It was structured as follows: At the beginning of the questionnaire, six questions were asked to collect sociodemographic data of the participants. These questions aimed at collecting basic information such as age, gender, educational level, income, and area of residence. There is some disagreement in research about the data level of Likert scales. In this evaluation, the data were interpreted as interval data and thus parametric statistics were used (Norman G., 2010). The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, ANOVA Analysis of variance, and the Pearson correlation coefficient to examine the relationships between the variables. IBM SPSS Statistics Version 29.0.1.0 (171) and Excel (2016) were used for the statistical analyses.

There is some disagreement in research about the data level of Likert scales. In this evaluation, the data were interpreted as interval data and thus parametric statistics were used (Norman G., 2010). The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, ANOVA Analysis of variance, and the Pearson correlation coefficient to examine the relationships between the variables. IBM SPSS Statistics Version 29.0.1.0 (171) and Excel (2016) were used for the statistical analyses. All participants were informed of the purpose and duration of the study before participating in the survey. Anonymity and confidentiality of the data were ensured through the use of an anonymous survey link and storing the data on a secure server. No personally identifiable information was collected to protect the privacy of the participants.

¹ Due to external factors, the focus groups in Belgium were smaller with a number of 4 – 5 participants per focus group.

2.5 SWOT analysis

A SWOT analysis is a strategic planning tool. It is used in order to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of a respective subject of matter. It includes a specification of the objective of the projects. Furthermore, internal and external factors have to be identified that are either favorable or unfavorable to achieve the determined objective (Plieninger, Bens, & Hüttl, 2006). The SWOT analysis includes a socio-economic assessment to identify process strengths and weaknesses and propose solutions to remove existing bottlenecks, ensuring acceptance by different market segments and the industrial ecosystem. The results are often shown in the format of a matrix.

The SWOT that we developed for the assessment of the market opportunities of packaging for food, home and personal care products within the CIRCULAR FoodPack project is delivered in an “enriched” form: “SWOT +A” – “SWOT plus action”. In addition to the description of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, we include in our analysis possible “Actions”, in order to accelerate the market acceptance and to enhance the market roll out of the innovations.

The SWOT+A analysis is delivered in this Deliverable Report based on the second round of expert interviews and consumer focus groups. We decided to compile one common SWOT+A analysis for both of the examined innovations (packaging for food, packaging for home and personal care products). Since many factors turned out to be similar for food- and non-food packaging, we combined it for reasons of clarity and highlighted the differences between the innovations transparently within the analysis.

3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND/ RESULTS OF DESK RESEARCH

In the following subchapters, we provide an overview about different aspects of Circular packaging. This information is based on results from literature research. The methodology was described earlier in chapter

3.1 Definitions of Circular and sustainable packaging

“Circular packaging” (Figure 1) is not clearly defined and can comprise several types of packaging. In general, Circular packaging can be considered as sustainable because by facilitating collection and sorting for recycling, composting, reuse, and waste-to-energy processing, sustainability in the packaging value chain is improved. Moreover, Circular packaging aims at processing of sorted packaging, more sustainable material sourcing, and reducing material and resource use, while preserving essential functions of packaging (Ingrao, Gigli, & Siracusa, 2017).

Figure 1: Simple illustration of Circular packaging (own compilation of Ecozept)

Main key characteristics of Circular packaging can be:

- Recovered and utilized effectively in biological and/or industrial closed loop cycles
- Beneficial, safe & healthy for individuals and communities throughout its life cycle
- Sourced, manufactured, transported, and recycled using renewable energy
- Optimizes the use of renewable or recycled raw materials
- Manufactured using clean production technologies and best practices
- Made from healthy materials throughout the life cycle
- Physical design optimizes materials and energy

3.1.1 Status quo and challenges for recycling of packaging

In order to accelerate plastics Circularity, increasing the overall quantity and quality of recycled plastics is necessary. There are different technologies that maximize the value of plastics after their use. There are various plastic recycling technologies (see Figure 2), including mechanical recycling, solvent-based recycling, organic recycling of compostable plastics, chemical recycling etc. At current state, mechanical recycling is the most used recycling process and provides the highest quantities of recycled plastics, up to 99% (Thébault, Dole, & Loriot, 2019).

In general, a smaller number of different polymeric components and layers in a packaging film promotes a higher recycling value (Forlin & Faria, 2002). Improving the barrier properties of packaging to control the quality and safety of food is one of the main objectives of the combination of materials. Barrier properties are needed, for instance, for oxygen (O₂), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen (N₂), water vapor (H₂O). Also light transmittance has to be controlled, and barriers can be needed against oil/grease, as well as for odor/flavor (Morris, 2017).

Figure 2: Explanatory diagram of the different recycling processes (Plastics Europe, 2022)

There are several challenges that impede the recycling process. Although multilayer packaging can be resource efficient, it is difficult to have high recycling rates with the currently implemented collection- and recycling infrastructure (Wellenreuther, 2016). Many material combinations present in multilayer materials cannot be processed together due to different melting points and thermal stability (Haig, Morrish, Mortin, & Wilkinson, 2012). Recycling rates of plastics waste are higher when the waste is collected separately instead of using mixed collecting methods (Plastics Europe, 2022). In case that the plastic waste fractions are collected via mixed waste streams, additional sorting steps within the recycling process are required. This is an obstacle of plastic valorization, and hampers the production of food-grade material (European Commission, 2022). The recycled materials obtained by the present recycling infrastructure are not allowed to be used for food products, yet food packaging is the most demanded and used packaging globally.

At the moment, flexible plastic packaging is barely recycled in the existing waste management infrastructure; as Europe largely relies on traditional mechanical recycling approaches in regrind processes, which usually means combined treatment of materials (Kaiser, Schmid, & Schlummer, 2018). Thermal incompatibility of the various combined materials is a major obstacle to reprocessing (Nickel, 1996). New technologies such as chemical recycling (with a percentage of 0.8%) and solvent-based recycling show promising results, but need further examination and scale-up (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017).

Regulatory and legislative aspects are another challenge. As specified in the Regulation (EU) No 10/2011, recycled plastics from mixed post-consumer waste are not permitted to be in direct contact with food.

However, they can be integrated into an inner layer of the packaging if they are separated by a functional barrier that avoids the transfer of unauthorized substances from the recycled layer to the food (European Commission, 2022). For non-food packaging, there are no restrictions on contact with the filling material (Plastics Europe, 2016).

The aim of recycling plastic has always been turning post-consumer waste into new resources. The latest statistics emphasized the European efforts in this regard: *“More than 10 million tons of post-consumer plastics waste were sent to recycling in 2020. Close to 90% (9.1 million tons) were treated in the EU27+3 to produce 5.5 million tons of post-consumer recycled plastics”* (Plastics Europe, 2022). Behind Building and construction, packaging applications make up the second largest market for post-consumer recycled plastics, followed by agriculture, agriculture and gardening (Plastics Europe, 2022). Since 2006, the total amount of postconsumer plastic waste sent to recycling facilities has more than doubled. Overall, recycling quantities increase due to more efficient sorting technologies that have enhanced waste collection systems, and the expansion of plastic waste recycling initiatives (Plastics Europe, 2022).

3.2 Consumer studies on Circular and sustainable packaging

The diversity of claims suggesting sustainability of different types of packaging, i.e. biodegradable, misleads the consumers. For instance, the term “biodegradable”, which is defined as the ability to be decomposed by the action of microorganisms, suggests that the packaging is readily biodegradable in the environment. Instead, most commercially available biodegradable polymers can only be decomposed in industrial systems under controlled conditions. (Ndahebwa Muhonja, Magoma, Imbuga, & Makonde, 2018).

One factor that influences consumers’ decision in favor or against the purchase of a respective product is the Willingness to Pay (WTP) (Boz, Korhonen, & Koelsch Sand, 2020). A study carried out in 2016 revealed that recycling motives (such as improved water quality) had a significant impact on consumers’ WTP (Klaiman, Ortega, & Garnache, 2016). Willingness to pay is also part of our own data collection, the results are described in chapter 0.

Sustainable packaging can influence the perceived ethicality of the brand and purchase intentions in a positive way (Magnier, 2015). Moral norms can foster persons to prefer environmentally-friendly packaging at purchase (Thøgersen, 1999). Moreover, moral reasoning and compliance with expectations that the consumer perceives affected the preference of reduced-waste packaging. Consumers are always looking for a positive spillover (Thøgersen, 1999).

Consumers’ preferences are also influenced by the design of the packaging. Thus, it is essential that the packages present good aesthetics to convince the consumers to buy the product (Weber Macena, Carvalho, Cruz-Lopes, & Guiné, 2021). In addition to this, verbal claims like, e.g., labels, are another factor for consumers’ decisions due to captivating information (Weber Macena, Carvalho, Cruz-Lopes, & Guiné, 2021). However, the presence of too many labels may confuse consumers (Lazzarini, Visschers, & Siegrist, 2017).

Plastic as a material is often assessed negatively by consumers, and the functional features of the material, such as protecting the product, is not always acknowledged (Popovic, Bossink, & van der Sijde, 2019). Therefore, assessing a Circular plastic packaging as sustainable might not be intuitive for consumers and requires measures of communication and information.

Changing consumers' purchase behavior is challenging. However, it is anticipated that society would gradually adopt sustainable habits, questioning its choices and taking the environment into account. Therefore, effective communication on sustainable packages, like "recyclable", "made of recycled material", "decreased packaging bulk", etc. might influence the consumers' response to a product favorably in case they are clearly defined and understood (Weber Macena, Carvalho, Cruz-Lopes, & Guiné, 2021).

4. RESULTS

In the following chapters, we present the results of the first and second round of data collection. We present the results of the expert interviews and of the 8 consumer focus groups. In addition, we describe the results of the survey of brand owners. All results are integrated in the SWOT+A analysis in chapter 4.7. After each paragraph, the most important findings are summarized in a few sentences. These summaries are highlighted in green.

4.1 Results of the qualitative expert interviews (Delphi I)

Since most of the interviewees were experts for both food and non-food packaging (see Table 2 above), we present the results for both packaging applications together. Within the paragraphs, we point out the differences between the two applications where applicable. In subchapter 4.1.5, additional differences between food packaging and packaging for home and personal care are highlighted separately. Verbatim quotes of single experts are marked with quotation marks. Whenever we use the term "Circular packaging", we refer to the packaging that is developed in the CIRCULAR FoodPack project. All results reflect experts' opinions, and therefore do not claim to be a holistic consideration of the subject matter.

4.1.1 First impressions

Many experts had positive first impressions about the project and the Circular packaging after having read the product brief. The consortium with the respective partners is well known. The packaging solution that the project aims for is seen as innovative and important. Moreover, it is well connected to the needs of the industry, and kind of a "holy grail". However, this simultaneously means that the goals are assessed to be very ambitious and hardly achievable. Not only is the final product evaluated as interesting, but the intermediate building blocks, technologies and products as well. One expert did not think that the technologies in the project were innovative. Doubts were expressed by all expert regarding diverse challenges, which will all be discussed more in detail in the following subchapters.

Most experts find the project and its aims interesting and evaluate it positively, though it contains many challenges and doubts with different regards were expressed.

4.1.2 Main benefits

According to the experts, one of the main benefits of the Circular packaging would be that it allows making more use of recycled material. More virgin PE is used for mono-material packaging anyway, therefore lots of material would be available for recycling after the first use, and could then even be used for high quality products like food packaging instead of, e.g., garbage bags. Another benefit is that this type of packaging would be very innovative, especially for food-products. A beneficial LCA would be another advantage compared to conventional packaging. Several experts also stated that the Circular packaging would be “a good story to tell” and advantageous regarding marketing and publicity. Furthermore, the packaging was assessed as being truly Circular since no other material like aluminum foil would be integrated as barrier, which enables recycling.

Main benefits of the packaging are the increased use of recycled material, the innovation potential, environmental benefits, as well as a good marketing story.

4.1.3 Experts’ assessment of the different technologies

In the following, we provide insights about experts’ critical assessment of the different technologies that we develop and optimize of in the project.

Tracer-based sorting

Regarding tracer-based sorting, doubts were expressed by many experts. The technology seems to be well researched, but many questions remain open, for instance the following collected ones:

- How would the second recycling work?
- Does the tracer get transferred through every recycling step?
- What about the food contamination risk caused by the tracer?
- What happens if the tracer comes into contact with the food?

One single opinion is that the technology is rather seen as outdated in the industry, and there would rather be an agreement on the use of digital watermarks or barcodes. Disadvantages of tracer-based sorting, which the experts named, are, e.g., that the technology is expensive and uneconomical, it adds concerns, it requires to adapt the sorting lines for a benefit that is seen as limited, it is hard to be established on the market, and that the tracers themselves must be food-grade and cannot lead to contamination of the respective packed products. One major limitation is that the system would only work if the tracers are applied on every packaging, at least in Europe. But without any binding commitment or legislation, this does not seem realistically implementable. This, however, is the same for digital watermarks or any other similar system. In addition, the support and cooperation of sorting centers would be needed on a large scale, so many different stakeholders would have to cooperate. One participant demurred regarding cross-contamination of materials for food-packaging when being collected otherwise than in a refund system. When all packaging is collected in a joint collection, contaminations with, e.g., leaking batteries or poisonous substances could occur. Despite the potential advantages of the technology, its applicability for food-grade material is questioned. One expert was highly critical about tracer-based sorting and stating that this technology would contradict the “overall global strategy of the packaging industry”. As reason for this he declared that agreement was being discussed within the industries to focus on bar codes as sorting technology. Overall, consensus existed among the experts that some kind of intelligent system for sorting is needed, and some experts declared themselves in favor of the system with tracer-based sorting especially regarding the sorting out of food-packaging.

Experts are rather skeptical about tracer-based sorting for food-packaging because there are too many open questions and alternative beneficial systems exist. However, most of the questions that came up can be answered or are addressed within this project, which is very new and not widely known yet.

Pre-treatments: deinking and deodorization

Since printing is an important tool for packaging in general, deinking processes are seen as necessary and useful for aesthetics/design and consumer acceptance of the packaging as well as for safety and decontamination. The deinking processes needs to be mainstream and economically and environmentally viable. It is important to demonstrate business cases and to highlight the ecological benefit and lower footprint of washing and deinking in comparison to other methods. Regarding multilayer packaging, deinking faces the challenge that ink could have been applied between the different layers and then the deinking technology might reach a limit. Also mentioned was that the type of ink that is used needs to fulfil certain criteria regarding toxicity, which is of course always the case for inks.

Deodorization also aims against contamination and is seen as important step in recycling circle. However, one expert stated that odor could be a “deal breaker” and that deodorization generally does not yet work perfectly in polyolefin at the moment, so there still seem to be technical restrictions.

For improving the quality of the final product, pre-treatment technologies are assessed as useful. Technical challenges need to be overcome, which is being investigated in this project.

Mechanical recycling and CreaSolv®

Regarding the CreaSolv® process, main concerns arose regarding the approval for food packaging and its establishment on the market. Mechanical recycling is generally seen as a challenge, mainly because it is competing with chemical recycling and its benefits (although market-size wise and technical readiness-wise, the two technologies are not yet competing), and due to doubts that mechanical recycling is compliant with food grade quality.

4.1.4 Requirements for the Circular packaging

The most frequently mentioned requirement for the Circular packaging is that it should have the same characteristics and properties as conventional, high quality packaging from virgin material. This is valid for both food and non-food packaging. As features that have to be similar, the experts named, for instance, mechanical properties, functional properties, same levels of moisture-, light- and other barriers. Safety requirements must be met as well, and it has to be recyclable all over several times again and be recurrently used as the type of packaging for the same product categories again in order to guarantee for “true Circularity”. Requirements regarding shelf-life must be the same as for conventional packaging, applying for both food- and non-food packaging. Regarding aesthetic requirements of the final packaging, experts have diverging opinions. Some state a compromise with regard to the color (not completely transparent, a bit yellowish) are acceptable in case the packaging is recyclable several times and circular, others disagree and demand new-looking material. The “voice of the customer” is an important factor here; consumers’ expectations have to be taken into account. Requirements regarding the price are discussed in a separate subchapter (see chapter 4.4.9). For production of the recycled packaging, it is crucial that the properties of the material allow being processable on existing machines, the machine compatibility is a major requirement for the common manufacturing practice. Food grade quality will be discussed in a separate chapter (see chapter 4.1.6). Another requirement that was mentioned by several experts is that the final product has to be beneficial in terms of LCA and energy use.

It has to be transparent, how “green” the whole process actually is.

Main requirement of the Circular packaging is that it has the same characteristics and functionalities as conventional packaging from virgin material.

4.1.5 Differences for food, home and personal care products

The requirements regarding the application of PE PCR material as packaging for the different product categories food and non-food are similar regarding performance like mechanical requirement, aesthetics, etc. They do not differ either regarding their operability on existing machines when being processed. Concerning functionality, one expert stated that there might be some products where it is not as critical to have the same top-performance as for food products, as it is not that much the matter of taking care of safety and health.

The major difference can be found in the legal requirements since home and personal care products do not have the same demands as food-grade quality. Food products need functional barriers unexceptionally when recycled content should be integrated, for home and personal care products this is only the case in some special cases. Personal care products like wet wipes and face masks, are more sensitive, because they are made for direct contact with the human body. Household products like detergents are much less critical. One expert reported that food-grade quality is required for packaging of cosmetic-/personal care products, as well.

Nevertheless, requirements of business customers besides regulations are the same, according to the assessment of one expert. The industry tries to avoid complexity: one packaging manufacturer supplies all industries. Food packaging is often used for non-food products, as well, because it is simple and safe and everything can be processed on the same machine. A manufacturer cannot use non-food packaging on existing food machines. “Food is the lead market, that's where the entry point is, it is easier that way in our linear world.”

Major difference between packaging for food- and non-food packaging are legislative issues and the need of functional barriers to incorporate recycled material. However, also within non-food products there can be different requirements for personal care products that are made for direct application on the skin compared to household products like detergents.

4.1.6 Main issues and challenges

In the following, the topics that are seen as the biggest obstacles in a technical perspective are discussed. The topics are addressed in decreasing order according to the frequency they were mentioned by the different experts.

Legislation

Food safety regulations are by far the issue most frequently mentioned. There are very high requirements for EFSA approval and no compromises with consumer safety are made. The regulations of the EU are much stricter than, in the US. Therefore, the majority of experts does not believe that EFSA will currently give the approval for packaging of PE PCR as food-grade. To get food- grade approval is already a challenge for packaging from virgin material. This is even assessed as aggravated by the new regulation effective from 10 October 2022, in which the regulations for functional barriers are tightened. This makes it, on the one hand, more difficult to get approval, but, on the other hand, could limit competition because every developer has to prove the safety of his/her packaging, and everyone needs to play by the same rules. Nevertheless, also the regulations themselves pose challenges, thus many things seem to be unclear

in the new regulations. Some documents are not yet available, recycled content calculations are unclear, no guidance is available, the transition period is not defined, and there are a lot of further open questions. If the PE PCR packaging will ever be approved for food-grade, this is expected to take a very long time. Experts see food compliance only as a long-term objective, but in a sector with high dynamic and much change, this might be a threat also with regard to competitive solutions.

All experts see the food safety regulations and authorization of the PE PCR Circular packaging by EFSA as the biggest challenge.

Migration, contamination and barrier concepts

The second most frequently named issue was the topic of barriers. Since PE has very low barrier properties, another type of barrier is necessary. Some experts assessed functional barriers as not sufficiently enough to prevent migration from PCR. The material has to be completely decontaminated (which is already complex due to the open structure of PE as a material) before bringing it in contact with food products, and the recycled PE has to be put behind functional barriers again. Oxygen-, vapor-, aroma-, and light barriers have to be implemented as fundamental requirements of food packaging, and partwise for packaging of personal care and home products. One expert addressed the topic that also low levels of BPA, phenols, and endocrine disruptors are a huge issue. They are all present in recycled polymers, which is a huge impediment especially if mechanical recycling is applied.

Experts doubted the feasibility of a completely recyclable mono-material PE packaging with PE from PCR that is food-grade mainly due to missing barrier properties.

Infrastructure, investments and scalability

All experts are united in the opinion that the processes that are included in the development of the Circular packaging have to be integrable in existing infrastructure without massive investments for an only limited benefit. This refers to all the single stages in the value chain which all have to be considered, and applies likewise for small and big companies. It needs to be accessible to, e.g., recyclers who reprocess the material, everyone in the whole chain needs to be able to incorporate the new technology into their processes, and ideally everything should be processable on the already existing machines. It should be kept in mind, that the packaging market is not a specialty chemical business. It is simply a production business, and solutions should be created that are not too complex to be implemented. Investments in new technologies of the different stakeholders in the value chain could only be made if all stakeholders/parties in the respective countries cooperate and bindingly agree on a solution. This is a system challenge that is difficult to solve in case it should be industrially adapted and on scale. Proving that the technologies work on other scales than laboratory and pilot scale, and proving the business case and that the implementation on industrial scale is feasible are challenging targets. A further obstacle is also that every country has different and very inhomogeneous systems and regulations. This is already the case within the European Union, and even more pronounced in, e.g., the US, where there is according to one interviewee not even a proper infrastructure for collection, sorting and storage.

The innovative technologies have to be scalable, implementable in the existing infrastructure and investments have to pay off.

Sorting, collection and availability of material

Sorting and collection are huge challenges. Avoiding contamination of sensitive (food-) packaging throughout the collection stream is a big issue that we already addressed earlier in this report. Sorting out food- from non-food packaging as well as distinguishing between different materials has to be feasible for the sorting plants. The challenges that go along with this have also already been mentioned, for instance, that for the use of tracer-based sorting and sufficiently enough stakeholders have to make use of them. Enough food packaging material has to be on the market, and the market share of the Circular packaging in the recycling stream must be sufficiently high. There are several markets and industries that need to be supplied with material, which creates a pressure on the availability.

Sorting and collection is a further challenge, as is the availability of material.

4.2 Results of the qualitative expert interviews (Delphi II)

4.2.1 Impressions of product

General impression

In line with the first round of interviews, many experts had a positive first impression of the product after reading the product brief. The aimed Circular packaging solution, whether for food or non-food items, is seen as innovative and aligning well with current trends. One expert also said that in order to meet the EU's recycled content targets, it is necessary to explore the mechanical recycling route, which increases the Circularity of food packaging.

As described in the first round, the targets are considered very ambitious and difficult to achieve. One expert was even more critical, noting that the majority of packaging has no recycling system and that even if collection systems were in place, it would be difficult to meet the high EU standards for packaging materials. In addition, the implementation of marker-based sorting for food packaging may be feasible for large brands, but there are significant barriers to wider adoption outside of large retailers or brands. Another voice elaborated on her thoughts about the functional barrier. The expert noted that the effectiveness of the functional barrier depends on its composition. Nanocoating is seen as a favourable option due to its reliability, while the use of other polymers presents challenges, particularly in terms of evaluation criteria and potential contamination with unknown polymers. Polyamide barriers are considered critical from a design point of view. Finally, one expert noted that while the focus has been on food due to complex compliance and recycling challenges, Circular packaging is also suitable for non-food products and offers simplicity.

Most experts find the project and its aims interesting and evaluate it positively, though it contains many challenges. Most experts had a positive impression of the solution Circular FoodPack suggests, for both food and non-food products, considering it innovative and comprehensive. However, achieving the ambitious targets is difficult due to different hurdles like the implementation of marker-based sorting, the functional barrier composition and need for recycling infrastructure.

Main benefits and added value

Main benefits:

In addition to the findings of the first round of expert interviews, the experts in the second round identified clear benefits of the packaging solution provided by Circular FoodPack. The approach is considered as a novel method for incorporating recycle into packaging, particularly with polyolefins, which has not been previously achieved. While similar approaches exist, they often lack legal approval, such as from EFSA, making them ineligible for market use. The project is described as one of the few closed-loop packaging initiatives emphasizing mechanical recycling, aligning with industry preferences. Involving stakeholders from various stages of the value chain ensures practicality and effectiveness.

Further, the experts were unanimous that the overall concept provides a major advantage. Several experts stated that the comprehensive consideration of the entire value chain, incorporating collection, sorting, decontamination, recycling methods and adding a functional barrier, is a key advantage. One voice added that the project is noteworthy for its focus on incorporating recycled content into food packaging while considering the entire lifecycle of the product. Another expert pointed out that the products fill a gap in the market, particularly in terms of PE recycling. It is designed with recycling in mind, aiming for recovering material of similar quality to virgin material.

In addition, the simplification of materials into single-product, multi-layer formats improve recyclability and encourages material reuse. Designing for recycling therefore streamlines the process and improves feasibility.

In terms of specific positive aspects, one voice commented that the project stands out as one of the few closed-loop packaging initiatives that emphasizes mechanical recycling. Further, the project is viewed as highly promising, especially considering forthcoming regulatory changes like the Plastic and Plastic Packaging Regulations (PPVR). While uncertainty remains regarding the feasibility of zero food contact applications by 2030, the product selected for study, requiring high barrier properties for quality preservation, is considered optimal for such investigations. Finally, one voice stressed the need to explore the mechanical recycling route, as chemical recycling isn't financially or environmentally viable.

In addition to the very positive overall impression, some experts also expressed a few critical thoughts regarding the benefits of Circular FoodPack. There are still concerns about the quality of recycled materials due to contamination and potential inadequate sorting. Therefore, there is one voice emphasizing to prioritize strategies to ensure a cleaner input stream, extending beyond design for recycling to address long-term quality concerns. Another expert noted that the impact of packaging should be balanced with the overall carbon footprint of the product it contains.

Added value:

The experts had very clear and largely unanimous views on the added value of Circular FoodPack. Beyond the material aspect, the project has a significant added value, mainly due to its contribution to addressing key challenges in recycling and reuse. Most experts agreed that improving Circularity in flexible packaging is one of the main added values. Several voices emphasize the need to establish closed-loop recycling systems, similar to those for rigid packaging like glass, in order to maximize the life of materials within the recycling process and reduce resource consumption and carbon emissions associated with incineration. It was noted that the main value lies in increasing the use of recycled content in products, aiming for sustainability by using more renewable sources. Despite the challenges in the industry

regarding high quality recycled materials, the demand for such materials remains crucial. In line with this, one expert added that the use of recycled materials provides significant value by reducing material accumulation and incineration, as well as conserving resources and minimizing waste.

When analyzing the sub-steps of the value chain, several experts highlighted the technical progress. In line with this, another expert emphasizes the need for traceable sorting to effectively recycle food packaging back into food packaging, highlighting its indispensability in achieving this goal. Finally, the deinking, delamination and deodorisation processes are viewed favorably as they increase the recycling potential, particularly for complex materials. Finally, two experts highlighted the functional barrier system. While functional barrier systems are not new, their development for polyolefins is a significant challenge due to their inherent properties.

However, there were also critical voices. One expert stated that simply returning food packaging to its original state may not be feasible. The inclusion of barriers for added protection raises some skepticism about food safety. In addition, one voice questioned whether these efforts would result in a fully functional product. Finally, one expert stressed that there is only added value if a closed loop can be guaranteed.

The main benefits of Circular FoodPack are the integration of recyclate into packaging while meeting regulatory standards, closed-loop packaging involving stakeholders across the value chain, full life-cycle considerations and the implementation of functional barriers.

Its added value lies in promoting Circularity in flexible packaging, increasing recycled content and technical advances in collection, sorting and recycling.

However, there are concerns about the feasibility of returning packaging to its original state, food safety, product functionality and the need for a guaranteed closed loop.

Experts' additions

While many experts did not identify any missing aspects in the product description, others commented on aspects that they felt were under-represented in the product description. Two experts focused on legislation. One expert highlighted a regulatory gap in current legislation and the need to positively influence the development of legislation. He emphasized the complexity and inadequacy of the existing legislation, particularly in relation to polyolefins, and the lack of input from EFSA. Another voice added that the framework had changed during the project. There is a new recycling directive. This means that the final results have to go to EFSA and be registered as a novel technology if it is to be introduced to the market. Previously, with the functional barrier approach, this would not have been necessary.

The experts also focused on the quality of waste streams. Several experts expressed concern about the complexity of waste streams and the challenges associated with sorting and recycling. They also highlighted the uncertainty of achieving the predicted levels of closure due to quality control issues. Therefore, the importance of focusing on waste quality and sorting was underlined, as quality in is quality out. In addition, one expert commented that there is a need for sufficient feedstock, a way to sort the feedstock, a way to produce good recyclate and a way to make fit-for-purpose packaging from the recyclate. Regarding the collection of reusable packaging, one expert presented two possible approaches. The expert highlighted refill and prefill. Refill involves consumers refilling containers themselves, while prefill involves empty packaging being returned to producers for refilling. The expert considered prefill to be better for food safety. Finally, the involvement and consideration of consumers is crucial for the implementation of Circular packaging solutions.

In conclusion, one expert stated that entropy must be observed. He pointed out that there is a risk of too much entropy, i.e. complexity, in processes such as deinking and delaminating, which could hinder the recovery of materials. The voice further noted that chemical recycling could make it easier to end up with a molecular product.

Experts highlighted under-represented aspects in the product description, in particular legislation and the complexity of waste streams. One expert highlighted the need to influence legislation due to gaps and changes in regulations. At this point, recommendations to legislators from projects such as Circular FoodPack are considered useful. Concerns were raised about the quality of waste streams and the sorting. Therefore, the importance of focusing on waste quality and sorting for successful recycling was emphasized. In addition, consumer involvement was seen as crucial to the implementation of Circular packaging solutions. Finally, the importance of entropy management was highlighted.

4.2.2 Requirements for the Circular packaging

General requirements

The experts interviewed also described the requirements for Circular packaging for a practical introduction. The most frequently mentioned requirement was legislation and regulatory compliance. Two experts noted that the final results for food packaging will have to be compliant and approved by according to European Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1616 of 15 September 2022 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods, and repealing Regulation. Therefore, the material on its own has to get EFSA approval or it has to be approved as a novel technology. The regulatory compliance is described as mandatory and as a prerequisite for all further steps. For non-food packaging, chemical quality is vital, with less emphasis on other requirements.

Beyond regulatory approval, the experts consider a fully functioning cycle to be an essential requirement. One expert describes the requirements in detail:

1. Functioning collection at scale, because if there is no collection at scale, then there won't be enough raw material.
2. Sufficient sorting in order to separate the materials into the grades wanted
3. Ability to make a recycle that can be used in addressed applications
4. Conception of fit for purpose and safely compliant packaging out of recycled material

The packaging needs to combine all the aspects mentioned above and at the same time have at least a decent LCA. Finally, a competitive price compared to the virgin market is needed. Economic discussions and individuals often acknowledge the value of utilizing recycled materials, yet they question why they should opt for a more expensive recycled version when a cheaper alternative is available.

When looking at the requirements for to make the packaging as practical as possible, one expert stated that the technology must be accessible to a wide audience to ensure widespread adoption. In addition, criteria for the material have to be established so that it aligns with the preferences of as many people as possible, facilitating its return to the loop.

The experts emphasized the necessity of regulatory compliance. Key requirements for Circular packaging are functioning collection systems, effective sorting methods, production of recyclable material, and creation of fit-for-purpose packaging. Further, the packaging must also demonstrate a decent life cycle assessment (LCA) and be competitively priced compared to virgin materials. Finally, accessibility and alignment with consumer preferences were emphasized to ensure widespread adoption and successful integration into the Circular economy.

Requirements for food packaging from recycled PE

The experts were also asked about their assessment of the requirements for food packaging made from recycled PE. Here the experts went more into detail compared to the general requirements.

Food safety and functional barrier:

All experts agreed that food safety is the most important requirement when using recycled PE in food packaging. Despite the closed loop, there is always a risk of contamination. Therefore, several experts stress the importance of ensuring that there is no unacceptable migration of substances from the packaging to the food, especially when working with polyolefins. They also emphasize the need for comprehensive documentation and verification processes to build consumer confidence and meet potential future scrutiny from NGOs. The aim is to ensure that recycled materials used in packaging are safe and trustworthy, possibly even exceeding the safety standards of virgin materials. In addition, the packaging must retain its functionality in terms of mechanical properties, water barrier and oxygen barrier to effectively protect the food product. Despite the use of recycled content, it's crucial to ensure that the water barrier remains functional, given chocolate's sensitivity to moisture.

When considering food safety, the experts emphasized the importance of the functional barrier in ensuring food safety. One expert stated that the functional barrier is critical to food safety. He went on to say that when working with polyolefins, the virgin layer is only for appearance or aesthetics. The virgin layer is not a barrier. Therefore, the functional barrier is mandatory. Another expert described the functional barrier block approach as clever. In this context, another expert highlights the strict regulatory requirements for functional barriers and recycled materials in food packaging. He explained that functional barriers have to go through a rigorous approval process to ensure that they do not pose a health risk. He concluded by expressing concern that the current regulations hinder the development of such products due to bureaucratic delays. Despite efforts to streamline the process, obtaining approvals remains a challenge. Finally, one voice mentions the importance of the recyclability of the material, stressing the need for a structure that facilitates recycling while maintaining functionality and safety.

One voice was more critical of PE and its fit for purpose. The expert stressed the importance of considering the shelf life of the packaging and suggested that materials such as PP or PET are more suitable due to their barrier properties and ability to withstand high temperatures. Overall, the voice believes it's possible to use recycled material in food packaging, but not with PE alone, advocating a combination of recycled and virgin materials for optimal performance and safety.

Finally, experts discussed the varying safety requirements regarding migration of substances into the chosen types of products. Firstly, experts stated that there are differences between food and non-food packaging. The experts do not consider the requirements for the selected non-food products to be critical. For facial products, any substance that migrates into them will inevitably be applied to the skin and may be absorbed. However, the benefit lies in the fact that the exposure area and duration are relatively

limited. Therefore, detergents are assessed to be entirely non-problematic. Since there is minimal skin contact, and if there is, it is promptly washed off. Wet wipes are also considered to be relatively uncritical. However, the possible exposure of small children has to be taken into account.

When looking at food packaging, the requirements regarding safety are much higher than for non- food. The experts assess ground coffee to be much less critical than chocolate powder, due to the exposure to only adults. In contrast chocolate powder can also be eaten by children and there is a big difference in the exposure per kg body weight of an infant and an adult. Therefore, chocolate powder is considered as the holy grail. Once it receives approval from the EFSA, any concerns about other products diminish.

Legal requirements

When considering food safety, the experts also addressed regulatory requirements. Several experts highlighted the importance of regulatory compliance, and in particular the need to comply with the regulations. The functional barrier has to be applied for novel technology authorization, ensuring that the functional barrier as such, i.e. the barrier system, has to decontaminate the product to a level where it does not pose a risk to human health. One expert emphasized the importance of being listed as an appropriate technology, which allows for wider use and market opportunities. In addition, one voice noted that the technology needs to be standardized. In order to expand operations and ensure widespread usability, it is essential for the initiative to involve not only existing partners but also engage a substantial portion of the industry.

Collection and Sorting:

The experts also identified an ideal collection and sorting process as one of the most important requirements. In terms of collection, the experts emphasized the need to create conditions for separate collection of PE, ideally from food packaging back into food packaging. This would minimize contamination from mixed packaging. However, such collection conditions require a well- functioning collection infrastructure.

Further, experts highlighted the importance of advanced sorting technologies to ensure high quality recyclates. One expert noted that a separate project is also investigating fluorescent markers in a project focused on PP recycling. There is therefore some concern that all components will work effectively, especially on a large scale. If only two large companies adopt the practice, while the rest of the industry refuses to participate, the objective will be undermined, as there will not be a sufficient amount of food-grade material collected.

The experts provided detailed insights into the requirements for food packaging made from recycled PE, emphasising food safety and the importance of a functional barrier to prevent contamination. They stressed the need for thorough documentation and verification processes to ensure consumer confidence and regulatory compliance. In addition, the challenges of regulatory approval and slow bureaucracy in the EU Commission were addressed, highlighting the need for adaptation to effectively accommodate recycled materials. Collection and sorting processes were also seen as critical, with concerns raised about scalability, as the collection and sorting infrastructure is poorly developed in many countries, and without collection on a large scale there will not be enough raw material. In addition, the effectiveness of technologies such as fluorescent markers on a large scale was questioned, as a great deal of effort is required to modify equipment.

Recycled packaging compared new packaging

Finally, the experts interviewed also described the requirements for recycled packaging compared to new (virgin) packaging. Several experts emphasized that the requirements for the use of recycled material are at least the same as for virgin material when it's intended for the same application. Packaging made from recycled material should meet the same, if not higher, standards as virgin or new packaging. If a closed-loop system is considered, where material is reused for the same purpose, the requirements remain the same. Conversely, if the recycled material is used for different applications, such as transport packaging in an open-loop system, the requirements can vary significantly.

The experts identified a number of requirements over and above those for virgin packaging. Firstly, several experts reiterated the paramount importance of safety when recycling material. One voice focused on the risk of contamination by non-food products during collection. If the liquid in the yellow bag runs over the packaging, in the worst-case scenario, such as exposure to glyphosate, it would be heavily contaminated. However, the consumer must be as safe as with new product packaging. This requirement has to be met because the EU Commission and EFSA will not compromise on human safety. Therefore, packaging structures must effectively block contaminants and ensure that food safety standards are met. As a result, the main difference between the use of recycled and virgin materials lies in the regulations governing their use, in particular the source of the material and the decontamination processes required for recycled materials. There are still no approved decontamination processes to achieve this goal. Recycled packaging has higher and more stringent requirements than virgin packaging, as it must comply with both food packaging and recycling regulations.

In practical terms, packaging made from virgin material is typically thinner but has comparable strength to thicker packaging made from recycled material. This is because virgin material has longer polymer chains, making it stronger. Recycled plastic, with shorter chains, requires thicker packaging to achieve the same strength. However, additives can improve stability and lamination provides functionality against oxygen and water vapour transmission.

Finally, the experts highlighted the importance of consumers and brand owners in identifying the requirements for recycled packaging. One expert suggested that consumers may prioritize longer shelf life over environmental benefits, underlining the importance of maintaining quality standards in recycled packaging. Another voice stated that the appearance of packaging is a key consideration for brand owners as sustainability becomes increasingly important. Therefore, differentiating recycled packaging through color and meeting mechanical property requirements through multi-layer films is another requirement for recycled packaging.

The experts outlined the requirements for recycled packaging in comparison to virgin packaging, emphasizing that recycled material must meet or exceed the same standards as virgin material for the same application. Safety is paramount, and concerns persist about contamination during collection and the need for effective blocking of contaminants to ensure food safety. Recycled packaging faces stricter regulations and must undergo approved decontamination processes. While virgin material may be thinner yet equally strong due to longer polymer chains, recycled material often requires thicker packaging. Consumer preferences for longer shelf life and brand owners' focus on packaging appearance also influence the requirements for recycled packaging.

4.2.3 Experts' assessment of reprocessing, sorting and recycling

Reprocessing of recycled PE after use

Regarding the reprocessing of recycled PE after use, experts stated that the same requirements apply as for the initial production, with cleaning, deinking, delamination, etc. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, experts consider that there is always a risk of contamination when using Circular food packaging in a closed loop. This is particularly true as PE absorbs many components from the environment due to its nature/structure. In general, the experts stated that the reprocessing process should be designed to allow multiple cycles. If it is limited at one point and then has to be replaced by another technology, then it is ineffective. Other experts suggest a hierarchy for recycling, prioritizing food packaging applications, followed by non-context sensitive packaging, lower grade plastics and then exploring different generations of materials. Finally, packaging should be reclassified as recyclable, leading to a focus on making packaging as recyclable as possible. In addition, advanced recyclability can avoid high packaging taxes.

In addition, experts focused on the different stages of recovery. With regard to collection, experts emphasized the need to create conditions for separate collection of PE, ideally from food packaging back into food packaging, in order to minimize contamination from mixed packaging. A collection infrastructure is therefore needed.

The recycling process was then examined by an expert. The expert sees a complexity in the recycling processes, especially in the reuse of barrier materials. In reprocessing, the degradation of polymers during recycling needs to be taken into account, as this can lead to the formation of by-products that may migrate and raise toxicological concerns. Finally, recycling technologies should be designed for multiple cycles to increase efficiency. Otherwise, there is no Circularity.

The experts also assessed the different recycling technologies in detail. With regard to mechanical recycling, the experts highlight the potential of the CreaSolv technology for recycling, noting its effectiveness when properly handled and segregated. However, it lacks food contact approval, which necessitates the use of functional barriers. Mechanical recycling in the polyolefins sector is also not approved. Nevertheless, achieving high recycling rates, even if not 90%, is desirable, and even 50% or 30% would be beneficial. One voice added that even lower levels of recycled content could still offer benefits, such as tax exemptions in countries like the UK, where packaging with 30% recycled content is tax free.

In contrast, a few experts addressed chemical recycling, stressing that chemical recycling could be an equal or superior process. One expert is unsure about the viability of multiple recycling cycles for PE and suggests that chemical recycling may then be required for some materials. Another voice goes further and suggests that there is less risk of contamination with chemical recycling compared to mechanical recycling. In addition, the expert advocates chemical recycling as it can offer advantages in terms of installation, efficiency in removing contaminants and flexibility in processing polymers back to their liquid form. Overall, the expert considers chemical recycling to be a more suitable option than mechanical recycling. Correspondingly, another expert has more confidence in chemical recycling for food-to-food packaging than in mechanical recycling. A more critical voice sees chemical recycling as a competitor, but points out the disadvantages such as high-energy costs and the need for green energy.

At the end of reprocessing, one expert stressed the importance of ensuring that recycled materials do not negatively affect the manufacturing process or the quality of the final product. The recycled material should not hinder production efficiency or compromise the overall compliance and desirability of the packaging. In addition, another voice added that at the end of the manufacturing process, there is a need to provide packaging that is mechanically and visually fit for purpose, while also being economically viable.

Recycled PE must meet the same stringent requirements as virgin material during reprocessing, including cleaning, deinking and delamination. This is due to the risk of contamination in closed-loop food packaging systems, particularly with PE's tendency to absorb environmental components. Reprocessing should allow for multiple cycles to ensure effectiveness, with a hierarchy prioritising food packaging applications and advanced recyclability. One benefit of holding the PE in a circle lies in avoiding high taxes, which would result from non-compliance with future regulatory requirements. Collection infrastructure for separate collection of PE is considered crucial to minimise contamination. The complexity of recycling processes, particularly for barrier materials, raises concerns about polymer degradation and migration of toxic by-products. Mechanical recycling technologies such as CreaSolv are seen as very promising, but chemical recycling is seen as a competitor due to its efficiency, reduced risk of contamination and flexibility in processing polymers. Ultimately, recycled materials should not compromise production efficiency or end product quality, and economically viable solutions are essential.

Assessment of sorting process

With the exception of a few more critical voices, the experts were unanimous in their assessment of the sorting process. Advanced sorting technologies such as tracer technologies and digital watermarks were considered essential to improve sorting accuracy in recycling processes. They emphasize the need for advanced sorting methods to distinguish between different types of packaging, including food and non-food, as well as different multilayer materials. Several experts consider collection and sorting to be crucial for a Circular approach as it ensures high quality recycled materials, likening it to the adage "garbage in, garbage out". The experts also made suggestions for optimizing the sorting and collection process. One expert suggests implementing deposit systems or incentives to improve collection rates, citing successful examples like those in Northern Ireland (where milk bottles were taken back and the person who returned them got 3 cents donated to the local football club). In accordance to that, another expert advocates for implementing a take-back system, particularly for PE, to enhance purity in recycling.

In particular, several experts stated that markers are a promising approach to improve collection and sorting processes. They suggest that markers on flexible packaging are a promising option due to the limitations of current infrared techniques and artificial intelligence methods. One voice also stated that markers on flexible packaging would be easy to implement as they are visible from both sides. Another expert compared the benefits and challenges of tracer-based technology in recycling. This voice stressed that the introduction of tracer-based technology into sorting systems can have both advantages and disadvantages. If it is already built in, then all you have to do is train the software. Otherwise, it has to be retrofitted to the sorting systems. This creates an additional sorting stream, the tracer stream. This could lead to rejection by sorters, who already have a lot more work to do than they do today. Some experts also raised concerns about tracer-based sorting. One noted that tracers could affect costs in multiple recycling loops. Another highlighted the difficulty of ensuring tracer distribution in fragmented packaging and the need to completely remove markers to avoid contamination in subsequent recycling cycles.

A third expert was skeptical about markers entering the recycling process and suggested either their destruction or removal as possible solutions. Another voice went even further, stressing that sorting with invisible QR codes is the only feasible sorting technology.

Finally, several experts mentioned ongoing projects such as the Holy Grail project and the Perfect Sorting project, which aim to develop innovative sorting techniques using digital watermarks, barcodes and artificial intelligence based on the shape of the packaging. The experts recommended an exchange with these projects in order to benefit from synergies.

Experts generally agreed on the importance of advanced sorting technologies, such as tracer technologies, to improve the accuracy of recycling processes. Efficient sorting is needed to distinguish between different types of packaging and multi-layer materials, which are essential for high quality recycled materials. To optimise sorting and collection processes, the introduction of deposit systems and take-back programmes could be a solution. Tracer-based markers were considered very promising for improving sorting. However, concerns were raised about their cost, distribution and potential contamination. Ongoing projects such as the Holy Grail and Perfect Sorting were noted for their innovative approaches, with experts recommending collaboration to exploit synergies.

4.2.4 Main issues and challenges

As in the first round of interviews, the topics considered to be the greatest obstacles from a technical point of view are discussed. The challenges named by the experts were completely consistent with those of the first round and complemented them. For this reason, only challenges that provide information beyond the first round are discussed below. These are listed in descending order of the frequency with which they were mentioned by the different experts.

Food safety regulations and compliance approval

Food safety regulations and compliance approval is by far the most frequently mentioned issue by the experts. As described in the previous paragraphs, all experts were unanimous in their opinion that food approval of the final products for food packaging is mandatory and a prerequisite for all further steps. According to the experts, the ESFA and the EU Commission will decide whether the products are safe or unsafe. If the authorities decide that the products are unsafe, there is a risk that some of the stakeholders will withdraw. In addition, one voice noted that another challenge arose during the project. There is a new recycling directive. This means that the final functional barrier has to be approved by EFSA in order for the new technology to be registered for the market. Previously, with the functional barrier approach, this would not have been necessary. Experts therefore see the new regulation as a challenge to adapt to.

Under the current regulation, the process for placing recycled food contact materials on the market was described as very complicated and lengthy. This is because there are already some products on the market that are not safe. This is the reason why functional barriers are now part of the new regulation as part of novel technologies and not suitable technologies. From this perspective, the experts agreed that the current legislation needs to be adapted to effectively accommodate recycled materials. One voice noted that one of the most challenging parts of food authorization is the very slow and heavy bureaucracy in the European Commission. From 2008 to date, there have been 230 concepts for recycled materials with a positive EFSA opinion, but none have been approved by the EU Commission. Inclusion in the list of suitable technologies would therefore be a major requirement and market opportunity.

Another expert criticizes the fact that legislation on packaging materials focuses too much on material specifications rather than the overall design of the packaging. He argues that EU regulations are too strict and inflexible, often requiring unnecessary testing. Finally, two voices stated that legislation treats food contact materials as if they were all virgin material, which doesn't fit with recycling processes. There's a disconnect between efforts to increase the use of recycled materials and the design of legislation. Therefore, greater involvement of consortia such as Circular FoodPack with practical industry involvement would be beneficial, but this is often lacking in practice.

Finally, the experts had mixed views on upcoming legislation such as the Plastics and Plastic Packaging Regulations. Several experts were optimistic due to the changes in legislation and the EU's aim to promote Circularity. One voice stated that these regulations will drive change in the future. However, there is still a lot of uncertainty. Other experts were more critical, as many things, such as food contact applications in 2030, seem unclear in the new regulations. In a sector characterized by high dynamics and frequent changes, experts see food compliance as a long-term goal, but also as a potential threat to competitive solutions.

Experts agree that food safety regulations and compliance approvals are the biggest challenge for PE Circular packaging. They stress that approval from authorities such as EFSA and the EU Commission is essential for stakeholder confidence and market opportunities. Challenges arise from new regulations, such as the requirement for EFSA approval of functional barriers under the Recycling Directive. Experts advocate adapting legislation to better accommodate recycled materials and criticise current regulations for focusing on material specifications rather than packaging design. Experts are divided on forthcoming legislation such as the Plastics and Plastic Packaging Regulations, with some optimistic about promoting Circularity and others concerned about its clarity and potential impact on competitive solutions in a dynamic industry.

Sorting, collection, decontamination and availability of material

In line with the first round of expert interviews, experts identified sorting and collection as a major challenge. As described in 4.2.2, one challenge is the need to implement advanced sorting methods to distinguish between different types of packaging and materials, including food and non-food items. The implementation of tracer-based technology in sorting systems could raise several issues and challenges. The most frequently cited challenge is the recycling of such tracers. There is uncertainty as to whether the tracers are recyclable or will be lost in the recycling stream. The experts also questioned whether the tracers would affect recyclability, as this technology is not included in any recyclability schemes or recycling guidelines. From this perspective, issues such as increased costs need to be considered. In addition, one voice stated that there could be difficulties in ensuring tracer distribution in fragmented packaging. Finally, experts raised concerns about the effectiveness of introducing tracers in the market. This requires a low entry threshold (financial and labor costs). If the technology can be easily implemented in existing machines, there will be a willingness to do so. If machines need to be upgraded, incentives are needed.

In terms of collection, the experts identified several challenges. Initially, the biggest challenge is setting up a well-functioning collection system and developing the collection infrastructure. However, the recovery of packaging is a major issue. According to the experts, it is impossible to recover 100% of packaging. At best, 50% of packaging is expected to be returned. Therefore, the introduction of deposit or take-back systems has been proposed to improve collection rates, especially for materials such as PE.

As described in 4.2.1, experts also see challenges in decontamination. Specifically, the requirements for the use of recycled materials differ from those for virgin materials, in particular the source of the material and the decontamination processes required for recycled materials. In summary, recycled packaging has higher and more stringent requirements than virgin packaging, as it must comply with both food packaging and recycling regulations. There are still no approved decontamination processes for recycled food packaging. One challenge is therefore to get decontamination approved. Experts advocate separate collection of PE, preferably from food packaging back into food packaging, to minimize contamination prior to decontamination processes.

Finally, consolidating the impression from the first round, experts identified sufficient quantities and consistent quality of material as a key challenge. If there is not enough material, there will not be enough return to run multiple loops. Quantity flows are therefore a key issue.

After food approval, sorting and collection are major challenges for Circular packaging. The implementation of advanced sorting methods, in particular tracer-based technology, poses several challenges, including uncertainty about recyclability and potential impacts on existing recycling schemes. There are also challenges in ensuring tracer distribution in fragmented packaging and the effectiveness of market introduction of tracers.

On the collection side, the main challenges are to establish a well-functioning system and develop the infrastructure, and to recover a significant proportion of the packaging.

Decontamination presents further hurdles, with different requirements for recycled materials compared to virgin materials, requiring approved decontamination processes.

Ensuring sufficient quantities and consistent material quality remains a key challenge for the effective operation of multiple recycling loops.

Consumers

Another key challenge identified by the second round of experts was the consumer. Firstly, there is a major challenge in educating consumers to improve sorting behaviour and the importance of effective collection and sorting processes, and in raising consumer awareness. Another issue is consumer coherence. Although there is a strong trend towards sustainability, there is often a lack of coherence in individual consumer behaviour. In general, consumers want recycled products. But the products do not have to be much more expensive. They also need to be functional and sensory. For example, if the recycled packaging smells bad, consumers will not buy the product. One voice noted that the use of recycled packaging in food packaging could be an issue because the packaging has been used before. Consumers are very selective when it comes to food and want the best product. Finally, the experts agreed that the main challenge with consumers is to get the product right.

Because there can be a very good product, but if consumers don't like it, they can destroy its reputation. Especially in today's social media society.

To overcome this challenge, experts suggest an awareness campaign on the benefits of recycling and Circular food packaging. To show the benefits of packaging compared to new material. One voice added that it could be beneficial to communicate that recycling and Circular packaging reduces plastic waste and therefore less plastic ends up in the environment. Another expert goes even further and emphasizes that educating and engaging all stakeholders, including consumers, legislators, brand owners and converters, is crucial to change mindsets and ensure proper recycling practices.

Consumer behaviour is a major challenge, according to the second round of experts. Educating consumers about sorting practices and the importance of effective collection and sorting processes is essential, as is raising awareness of sustainability. However, there's often inconsistency in consumer behaviour, despite a general desire for recycled products that also meet functional and sensory standards. Consumer sophistication, particularly when it comes to food packaging, is an additional hurdle. Experts suggest awareness campaigns to highlight the benefits of recycling and Circular packaging, emphasising the reduction of plastic waste and the importance of engaging all stakeholders to change mindsets and promote proper recycling practices.

Price

Although price was not mentioned first and was not perceived as a key challenge, the experts believe it is a critical issue. The price has to be competitive in order not to be killed by the virgin market. One voice noted that if the price is too high, there will be price resistance from consumers, brand owners and converters. In conclusion, the challenge is to offer competitive prices. The experts felt that the price could be 10-20% higher, but not more. A 50% more expensive product would not be accepted. However, at the right price, consumers, brand owners and processors will be willing.

Excessive pricing risks resistance from consumers, brand owners and processors. The consensus is that while a modest increase of 10-20% may be feasible, a 50% increase is likely to be rejected. The challenge is therefore to offer competitive prices that are acceptable to stakeholders.

Functionality and recyclability.

In contrast to the first round, the experts had fewer doubts about migration and the barrier concept. However, they identified a challenge in finding the right barrier for different types of food, temperatures and storage times. One barrier does not fit all. In addition, another expert noted that the structures developed would need to perform comparably to existing structures, but without problematic materials such as aluminium or wax layers.

Another voice raised the issue of recycling. The expert emphasized that one problem with the processing and recycling of polyolefins, especially polyethylene (PE), is the presence of non-intentionally added substances (NIA) that are created or absorbed during the recycling process. It is almost impossible to know what these substances are. Therefore, another challenge within the recycling process is to measure these NIAs and ensure that they do not pose a food safety risk. Another expert focused on the recyclability of the final product. The expert questioned whether the inorganic part (functional barrier part) is recyclable and whether this could be an issue in terms of recycling. Another voice added that there could be limited recyclability if the inorganic part is more than 10%.

Finally, the experts also identified sustainability as a challenge. One voice emphasized that the final product must be truly sustainable in terms of Circularity. The expert questioned whether such a complex structure with multiple layers is sustainable overall. However, the expert added that the process has to start somewhere. Another expert complemented this by suggesting focusing on the entropy of the whole process. According to the experts, there could be a risk of putting too much entropy into deinking, delamination, e.g. to recover the goods, as there are also many new solutions such as chemical recycling that make it easier to end up with a molecular product that can be used for recycling. The process could be made sustainable by taking into account the entropy required.

Experts highlighted challenges in selecting appropriate barriers for different foods, temperatures and storage times, as a one-size-fits-all approach is not feasible. In addition, the presence of non-intentionally added (NIA) substances in recycled PE could pose significant recycling challenges, the impact of which on food safety remains uncertain. Another concern was the recyclability of the final product, in particular the inorganic barrier part, with experts questioning whether its presence could hinder recycling, especially if it exceeded 10% of the product. Finally, experts discussed the overall sustainability of complex multi-layer structures and suggested focusing on the entropy of the whole process to ensure sustainability.

4.3 Results of brand owner survey

4.3.1 Requirements for using circular food packaging solutions such as the CIRCULAR FoodPack solution

The brand owners were asked to assess the requirements for using packaging material that strives for sustainability such as the CIRCULAR FoodPack solution. The experts described the key considerations when selecting their materials. The experts agreed on the importance of safety, compliance and sustainability. However, their perspectives on cost, material performance and recycling challenges differ. One expert prioritizes cost and sustainability alongside safety and compliance. He also emphasizes the need for compelling life cycle assessments and strong barrier properties. Ultimately, the expert highlighted that if they cannot make a credible claim about the benefits of a new material, there is little incentive to change. In contrast, another expert focuses on the specific requirements for pouches, such as printability, heat resistance, blowability and appearance. He also stressed that the new material must retain the same properties as the previous solution, even if machine adaptations are required.

In addition, experts identified improved machinability as a key requirement. In general, new material leads to lower efficiency and more waste. Ongoing fine-tuning is essential and retrofitting is often required, meaning that machines need to be adjusted even after they have been installed.

In addition, one expert focused on mono materials. The expert explained that working with mono material is more complex for machines because pure mono material does not have the same barrier properties. In addition, mono material is more expensive due to limited competition in the market. Another expert added that another key requirement is to find suitable recycling streams. The focus is mainly on Europe, as many countries lack the infrastructure for proper waste collection and recycling, although Germany has (according to the expert) a functioning system. He also notes that there isn't currently enough volume to establish a dedicated recycling stream for certain materials. In addition, post-consumer recycling remains a challenge, making it difficult to manage recycled materials effectively.

Despite the existing requirements and challenges, one expert explained that there is a great deal of

interest in overcoming these challenges and meeting the requirements. He further explained that they had introduced bags containing 33% PE-PCR using a mass balance approach about two to three years ago. Another expert added that initially, the focus for new packaging solutions was on products like coffee, cacao, and milk powder, which present challenges due to their moisture barrier requirements. The expert suggests that frozen and chilled food applications could also be considered for these innovative packaging solutions.

Brand owners evaluated the use of sustainable packaging such as the CIRCULAR FoodPack, highlighting the importance of safety, compliance and sustainability. Opinions varied on cost and material performance, with one expert emphasising life cycle assessment and barrier properties, while another expert focused on machinability and pouch-specific requirements. Challenges include reduced efficiency, higher costs for mono materials and limited recycling infrastructure. Despite this, there is strong interest in overcoming these issues and examples of innovative packaging solutions, such as 33% PE-PCR bags, are already in use.

4.3.2 Assessment on key performance indicators (KPIs) of CIRCULAR FoodPack

The brand owners were also confronted with the KPIs of CIRCULAR FoodPack and shared their opinions on the KPIs. The experts agreed and had a positive impression of the KPIs. The experts went into more detail and focused on the different KPIs.

Regarding material balance, the expert emphasized the importance of achieving a 50/50 split between recycled and virgin materials to meet regulatory requirements and sustainability goals. With evolving legislation, in particular the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), there is a critical need to integrate higher percentages of recycled materials to avoid penalties.

Another expert emphasizes the importance of exploring new technologies to facilitate this transition, noting a shift in perspective on tracer solutions. While there were initial reservations, advances in AI could reduce the reliance on tracers as A, although they may still be necessary for security purposes. The expert explains this position by the increased cost and complexity of managing additional chemicals through tracers within the supply chain.

Regarding recycling, and in particular deodorisation and deinking, the experts were positive about the improvement of cleaning and purification efficiency, as deodorisation and deinking are crucial for the further use of the material. However, the experts were concerned about the remaining 5% of ink and odour, as this can have a significant impact on the overall quality of the packaging and the product itself. This is particularly relevant for the recycling of coffee pouches. One expert also stated that residual ink and odour might not be a problem in B2B contexts, but pose significant challenges in B2C situations.

Experts had a positive impression of the KPIs for CIRCULAR FoodPack, with particular emphasis on key areas. One expert highlighted the importance of a 50/50 balance between recycled and virgin materials to meet regulatory and sustainability targets, particularly under the evolving Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). Another expert highlighted the need for new technologies, such as AI, to reduce reliance on tracer solutions, which add cost and complexity to the supply chain. While improvements in recycling processes such as deodorisation and deinking were praised, concerns remain about the impact of residual ink and odour on packaging quality, particularly in the B2C context.

4.3.3 Investment and willingness to pay

Looking at brand owners' insights into investment and willingness to pay for sustainable packaging solutions, several key themes emerge.

One expert emphasizes that there are several investment factors to consider. He points out that several factors have a significant impact on production costs, particularly the choice of materials and the scale of production. New materials are often produced on a smaller scale, which can lead to higher costs. In addition, the machinability of these materials is critical, as any need to modify production lines can incur significant costs. In terms of production timelines, the expert notes that equipment typically had a lifespan of around 50 years. However, the pace of change has accelerated in recent years, mainly due to evolving regulations that require production processes to be adapted. In addition, another expert raised concerns about the properties of new materials, in particular their tendency to be stiffer and thicker, which is viewed unfavorably by the industry.

In terms of willingness to pay, one expert highlights a lack of willingness on the part of customers to pay more for circular food packaging solutions and associated technologies. Despite the dynamic nature of this market, with taxes targeted at specific sectors, the general feeling remains that consumers are reluctant to incur additional costs. Research suggests that taxing virgin plastics is an effective regulatory approach, but the current market is complicated by fluctuating virgin plastic prices, which have become both higher and more volatile due to changes in raw material costs, including oil and energy. This volatility makes strategic planning difficult as the economic viability of eliminating virgin materials can vary significantly from year to year.

When considering the drivers of this change, one expert states that regulation and stakeholder influence are more important than retailers. The experts agree that retailers often refuse to switch from plastic to more sustainable solutions and pay higher prices for these products.

Brand owners note that production costs are heavily influenced by material choice and scale. New materials are often more expensive due to lower production volumes and potential machine modifications. Concerns about the stiffness and thickness of these materials also remain.

In terms of willingness to pay, there is a general reluctance among customers to spend more on circular food packaging, despite regulatory pressures and taxes on virgin plastics. Fluctuating prices for these materials make strategic planning difficult. Experts agree that regulatory and stakeholder influences are stronger drivers of change than retailers, who are often reluctant to switch to more sustainable options.

4.3.4 Assessment on market demand for circular packaging solutions such as the CIRCULAR FoodPack solution

When assessing the market demand for circular packaging solutions, in particular the CIRCULAR FoodPack initiative, experts agreed that there is a high market demand. Experts also highlight a significant shift towards bioplastics, largely driven by legislation such as the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). This regulatory environment is forcing brand owners to adapt to new standards, with post-consumer recycled polyethylene (PE-PCR) emerging as a viable option, particularly for dry food applications where hot filling is not required. This transition to mono-material and more sustainable, circular options is seen as essential for business survival. The expert also identified potential market opportunities in regions where plastic packaging is taxed, suggesting that regulatory measures could further drive demand.

Overall, the EU is recognized as a key market for innovative and sustainable solutions due to its stringent regulations, and companies are taking proactive steps to adapt to these changes.

In terms of potential applications, non-food applications such as detergents were identified as promising markets as they do not require food contact approval, making them more accessible for innovation. The experts expressed a keen interest in exploring intermediate product streams for these applications and mentioned that shrink film applications could also be particularly advantageous given their significant use in current operations.

When considering the factors that will drive market demand for circular packaging solutions such as the CIRCULAR FoodPack solution, experts unanimously cite high prices and low material availability as significant challenges to adoption. The focus is primarily on mono-polypropylene (PP) and mono-polyethylene (PE), both of which are similarly priced. While there are promising developments in this area, the experts remain cautiously optimistic about future improvements.

In addition, another expert acknowledged that many machines around the world will need to be adapted to accommodate these new materials. Reflecting on historical practices, the expert noted that previous solutions have been in place for 55 years, but the accelerating pace of innovation poses a challenge to rapid development. Another voice highlighted the reliance on polypropylene for decades and the urgent need to find alternative solutions within a short timeframe, suggesting that many companies are likely to be interested in these advances.

Brand owners also identified retailers as a key factor for PCR-PE. Retailers, on the other hand, are expected to pay a premium for mono-material products such as pouches, but often resist such price increases. This resistance forces companies to make up the cost difference by improving efficiency in other areas of their operations.

Another frequently cited factor influencing market demand is consumer behaviour. According to the experts, consumer behaviour adds another layer of complexity. Several experts describe an incoherence between consumers' stated preferences and their actual purchasing decisions. Even if the target group includes environmentally conscious teenagers, the purchasing decisions are mainly made by their parents, who tend to prioritize price over sustainability. As a result, these consumers are generally unwilling to pay more for environmentally-friendly products. In addition, consumer acceptance of reuse and refill options is declining, making it difficult to implement these systems due to their inherent complexity. While such initiatives may be successful in countries such as Germany and the Netherlands, they face significant challenges in markets such as France and Switzerland. The concept of bulk displays and refilling stations in supermarkets has not taken off, indicating limited consumer acceptance.

In summary, while there is an urgent need for circular packaging solutions, the interplay between pricing, consumer behaviour and market readiness present significant challenges that must be overcome for successful implementation.

Brand owners agree that there is strong market demand for circular packaging solutions driven by legislation such as the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). This regulatory landscape is encouraging brand owners to adopt new standards, with post-consumer recycled polyethylene (PE-PCR) emerging as a viable option. The shift to mono-material and sustainable options is seen as essential for business survival, with opportunities in regions that impose taxes on plastic packaging. However, challenges such as high prices and low material availability are hindering widespread adoption, despite promising developments in mono-polypropylene (PP) and mono-polyethylene (PE). Retailers play a significant role, often resisting price increases for mono-material products, making it difficult for brands to manage costs. Consumer behaviour also adds to the complexity, with an incoherence between expressed preferences for sustainable options and actual purchase decisions, with price often taking precedence. Overall, while the need for circular packaging is urgent, overcoming the challenges of pricing, consumer behaviour and market readiness is critical for successful adoption.

4.4 Assessment of the market for Circular packaging

In the following, we will give an assessment of the market for Circular packaging based on the information from the expert interviews. The market potential we will give an overview about market barriers, potential target groups and competition, factors for market acceptance, price structures and existing competition. On the end, open questions are collected and we point out which information the experts were missing.

4.4.1 General market potential

The experts were unanimous in their assessment of the market potential for reusable packaging. According to the experts, there is a huge market appetite and a huge gap in the market for recycled and flexible PE. Of course, this assumes that the challenges described can be overcome.

There is a "big story" to tell and the project is moving in the direction of what the industry needs. That's what all but one of the experts agreed. The experts emphasized that the industry urgently needs sustainable and recyclable packaging for several product categories, especially food. There is nothing on the market for food packaging and very little for non-food packaging. Therefore, the industry in Europe has a huge demand for this type of packaging. For the USA, there are conflicting estimates of the market. To get a clearer picture, this market would have to be assessed in more detail. For the European markets, some positive statements from the experts were "it's like a blockbuster, everyone will want it", "the packaging will sell like hot cakes" and "it will be a very hot market".

Market opportunities also depend on policy. There is a political appetite for the use of recycled material in PE. If this is reflected in legislation, there will be even more demand for this type of packaging because the industry will have to meet the requirements. One expert pointed out that the legislator is working on a new proposal for the Packaging Ordinance. This will come into force in 2024. According to the new regulation, all European packaging should be 100% recyclable. In addition, companies often have their own corporate targets and standards that go beyond the requirements. Additionally, the potential for non-food applications is seen as even greater, given fewer regulatory constraints. Brand owners set targets for recycled packaging in terms of compliance, functionality and aesthetics.

This means, for example, that they have additional requirements such as negative lists that exclude certain substances from being used in their products, even though their use would be legally permitted.

Brand owners currently seem to be more committed to incorporating certain amounts of recycled material into their packaging applications where possible. This means that brand owners have a lot of power and can be a driving force in improving recycling in packaging. Getting brand owners on board for Circular packaging can greatly help to increase market opportunities and market acceptance. Brand owners are considered to have the most power in the value chain compared to, for example, converters. After that, consumers can be a huge market opportunity. Experts emphasized that consumers want and can accept recycled products. If the price and marketing are right, consumers can be a powerful force. Therefore, they need to be informed and educated (e.g. through image campaigns) to recognize the added value of the products (less plastic production) and to help them in their purchase decision.

However, when assessing the market potential of reusable packaging, it is important to consider all the steps in the value chain and to look at them as distinct markets rather than as one complete system. The innovation lies primarily in the sorting and collection methods, while the effectiveness of the functional barrier layer could have a significant impact on market acceptance and value. Overall, successful implementation could lead to widespread acceptance and popularity.

The market potential for Circular packaging in general is considered to be very high, especially for food products. The experts agreed that there is a significant market demand for Circular packaging. Policy changes, such as upcoming legislation requiring recyclability, could further drive demand. Brand owners have a key role to play in promoting recycled packaging, with consumers also showing interest if pricing and marketing are aligned. However, to assess the market potential, each step in the value chain must be considered separately, with innovations in sorting, collection and functional barriers crucial for successful introduction and widespread acceptance.

4.4.2 Market opportunities and Safety & hygiene aspects

Safety & hygiene aspects further have a crucial influence on the market opportunities. Several experts identified the approval of technology by EFSA as the biggest market opportunity as it opens the door for everything else. All the regulations that are applying for both virgin and recycled material have to be covered. And with the approval there is a proof of concept, meaning that the technology is safe.

Furthermore, the barrier concept can provide a market opportunity. It serves as a good starting point in guaranteeing safety and shelf life of food products. Experts advocate for starting with concepts that may initially serve a limited market or specific applications as a means of progressing towards broader implementation. In addition, one voice added that many companies are exploring the development of mono-layer packaging with a minor addition of a barrier layer to maintain the packaging's status as 100% recycled. Overall, the barrier concept could facilitate faster advancement in packaging technology and make things easier and therefore faster. However, a few experts expressed their desire to eliminate the need for a functional barrier in packaging and emphasized the importance of actively researching and developing solutions to eventually eliminate the need for a barrier.

Experts highlight safety and hygiene as critical factors shaping market opportunities. EFSA approval is seen as an important gateway for technology adoption, ensuring compliance and validating safety. The barrier concept is also cited as improving food safety and shelf life, particularly in monolayer packaging with minimal barrier additives. While some advocate expanding the use of barriers to drive technological progress, others aim to eliminate the need for barriers through ongoing research and development efforts.

4.4.3 Market barriers

The following are the biggest market obstacles identified by the experts. It should be noted here that market opportunities, challenges and market barriers are very closely interlinked. The market barriers are listed according to their frequency of mention and expert weighting.

Food safety legislation

When looking at market barriers, experts unanimously identified food safety legislation as the biggest market barrier. Experts emphasize the importance of achieving full compliance, especially with regulations such as 1616/2022, before moving forward with novel technologies to ensure the safety of the material produced. At present, however, development and practical implementation are not progressing as quickly as they should because the requirements are so high. Despite efforts to streamline the process, the regulations still pose significant hurdles, in particular due to slow-moving bureaucracy within the European Commission. Since 2008, many concepts have received positive opinions from EFSA, but none have been approved by the EU Commission. There is therefore a need to monitor what it takes to get approval. Here, experts express the need to find a route from legislation in a functional, timely and affordable way.

Consumer

Besides food safety legislation, experts consider consumers as the biggest market barrier. One voice emphasized that the message has to be done right, meaning that specific image campaigns are needed. If not communicated well, the product will not be accepted. Furthermore, the consumer has to see the benefit for themselves. Like saving the planet or saving their grandchildren or doing something good. The motto is: what's in it for me. Otherwise, there is the classic say do gap and the consumers will not buy the product.

Quantitative input & Quality

As described in 4.2.3, the supply of raw materials is a market barrier. In order to think 'Circular', there must be continuous loops. It is therefore necessary to continue to integrate recyclates. If only 30% of the material is recycled, there will be very few loops and no circularity. In conclusion, a high percentage of the material on the market (around 90%) needs to be recovered and recycled, which means that around 10,000 tonnes per year is needed for a recycling loop to be profitable. Anything less is very expensive in terms of transport, logistics, etc.

The experts believe that product quality could be a market barrier. It needs to be of comparable quality to virgin products. For example, it must be as safe as virgin products, offer the same functionality in terms of flexibility and durability, and have a favorable sensory experience. Otherwise, there could be a quality resistance.

Collection

Experts also see the collection and collection infrastructure as a market barrier. Collection systems and facilities need to be developed. Therefore, the collection infrastructure needs funding. One voice stated that EU research funding is needed to help companies set up the infrastructure. In the first place, companies are at a market disadvantage in developing a collection infrastructure. The price disadvantage must be overcome.

Price

Finally, experts identified price as a key market barrier. The price of recycled materials has historically been higher than that of virgin materials, which is another barrier to widespread uptake. As described in 4.2.3, the price needs to be competitive to avoid being killed off by the virgin market. The experts felt that the price could be 10-20% higher, but no more. A 50% more expensive product would not be accepted. However, at the right price, consumers, brand owners and processors will be willing.

Food safety legislation stands out as the main market barrier, with experts stressing the need for full compliance, especially with regulations such as 1616 2022, before adopting new technologies to ensure material safety. Slow bureaucracy within the European Commission is hampering progress despite efforts to streamline regulations, with no approaches approved since 2008 despite positive EFSA opinions. Consumer perception is another significant barrier, requiring effective communication of product benefits to drive uptake. Ensuring comparable quality to virgin products is essential to avoid quality resistance. In addition, raw material supply, collection infrastructure development and competitive pricing are identified as key market challenges that need to be addressed for widespread adoption of recycled materials.

4.4.4 Target groups

Most experts agreed that the main target group for the final packaging should be large multinational concerns. This is due to different reasons:

1. They are the main beneficiaries.
2. They will be able to absorb some of the upcoming extra costs.
3. If signature brands are on board with the Circular packaging, it would have a huge influence and impact on the market.
4. Huge companies with "heavily branded items are more likely to be targeted by anti-plastic groups". The use of Circular packaging could therefore prevent them to be scrutinized by the public.

With regard to the Circular packaging, the process and product are not assessed as being suitable for niche applications by the majority of experts. The focus should rather be for mainstream applications in order to demonstrate a business case. In addition, larger packaging sizes might be an option for the food industry, not only small packages for end consumers. One suggestion was to focus on the B2B sector than B2C markets, since businesses are easier to train than end consumers. This corresponds well to the aim of the project.

One expert stated that the brand owners and converters are the beneficiaries and are therefore a less important target group. Focus should be put more on recyclers and sorters, since they have to make investments and are therefore very important stakeholders in the value chain. In addition, polymer producers are enablers because they are the ones who apply the technology for the implementation, and the coatings and adhesives producers who provide the functionality

The majority of experts advocate targeting large multinational companies for the introduction of Circular packaging due to several factors: their role as primary beneficiaries, their capacity to absorb additional costs and their potential to influence market trends if they support the concept. Experts suggest focusing on mainstream applications rather than niche markets to demonstrate the viability of Circular packaging. It is also recommended to focus on the B2B sector rather than B2C markets, as businesses are seen as more receptive to training and adoption. Finally, the importance of targeting stakeholders such as recyclers, sorters, polymer producers and coatings/adhesives producers in the value chain is highlighted for successful implementation.

4.4.5 Applications

The experts had clear opinions on the most suitable applications. For food, several experts recommended starting with frozen products. Given the use of PE structures, they suggest focusing on the frozen sector, such as the storage of vegetables and French fries. This market is advantageous because the low temperatures in the freezer reduce the risk of migration, making it a significant opportunity for PE-based packaging. In addition, the frozen food market is a huge market. One voice went further and suggested working with customers who already have their own logistics, such as Bofrost. In addition, the experts consider dry products to be simple entry-level products. These products have the lowest barrier requirements, such as pasta, and do not need many structures in the final packaging, such as sealing. Furthermore, one voice expects dry products to have different, probably simple, migration modelling. In addition, one expert recommended starting with high volume packaging applications that can be mono-material. Good examples would be packaging for crisps or chocolate, i.e. applications with low and medium barrier requirements. These are products that also have larger volumes in the market and are not niche applications.

In addition, several experts highlighted the importance of considering the target market, noting that baby food packaging requires higher standards than packaging for adult use. Therefore, another voice recommended to focus on products for adult use only, as this is easier to regulate. In addition, two experts felt that less emotive products could be advantageous as neutral packaging is possible. The experts gave examples such as flour, sugar substitutes, pasta, soup and cereals. One voice added that these products do not have an attractive packaging design and are more pragmatic choices. Finally, three experts would prefer to start with non-food applications and focus on the personal care and home sectors. However, most of the experts agreed on the product selection within the project, advocating starting with the most challenging product categories. More detailed information on product selection is given in the following section.

Experts were also able to identify inappropriate applications. One expert stated that fatty foods are a "no go" because there is much more migration potential. Therefore, the results of migration tests will either be on the line or not safe. Another voice added that acidic foods or products with high acid content should also be avoided.

Experts recommend starting with frozen food products, particularly in the deep freeze sector like storing vegetables and fries, due to the low risk of migration in PE-based packaging at low temperatures. Dry products, such as pasta, are also suggested as simple entry-level options with minimal barrier requirements. Products like chips or chocolate, with low to medium barrier needs and large market volumes, are seen as suitable initial targets. Considerations for target markets include focusing on adult-use products to simplify regulatory compliance and opting for less emotionally attached items like flour. Additionally, fatty or acidic food products are deemed unsuitable due to increased migration potential.

4.4.6 Suitable markets

The experts also identified suitable markets for the launch of the products and agreed that there is a demand for Circular packaging everywhere. Therefore, several experts stated that the whole EU could be a potential market. However, conditions vary greatly from region to region. The most frequently mentioned regional markets were Germany, France, the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, Norway, Sweden and Finland. According to the experts, these countries stand out because of their collection infrastructure and source of materials. Another voice mentioned that Spain and Italy are focusing on recycling but still have big problems with collection and sorting. Finally, one expert said that the Netherlands is a good market to start with as it is small and innovations are easy to implement. England was also seen as suitable as e-commuters are further ahead.

The experts agreed that there is a widespread need for Circular packaging and identified the whole of the EU as a potential market. However, they recognised regional differences in infrastructure and material sources. Germany, France, the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, Norway, Sweden and Finland were highlighted as promising markets due to their collection systems and material sources.

4.4.7 Assessment of product choice

When it comes to the choice of products within the project, the experts were in complete agreement. The choice of coffee and chocolate is seen as ambitious but positive. Two experts stated that the chosen product types are very interesting as they are the type of products that require a certain quality of material, i.e. high barrier properties, in order to preserve the aroma, odour and quality of the product. According to the experts, it is risky enough, but not too risky. Another voice added that it was an optimal product choice for this type of study.

Furthermore, some experts focused on the targeted products in detail. Regarding non-food products, one expert stated that they were uncritical. Regarding facial masks, one voice noted that anything that migrates into a mask is also 100% smeared on the face and can be absorbed. However, the advantage is that the area and time of exposure is relatively small. Detergents were also seen as uncritical, as there is very little skin contact and if there is, it is easily rinsed off. The wet wipes are also considered relatively uncritical. However, the possible exposure of small children (babies' bottoms) has to be taken into account. In conclusion, non-food products are not considered critical by the experts. One voice mentioned that it might even work if the functional barrier block was omitted.

Regarding food, one voice stated that ground coffee is much better and easier than chocolate powder because it is an adult product. Chocolate powder can also be eaten by children. As a result, there is a big difference between the exposure per kg body weight of a teenager and an adult. Coffee cream is also intended for adults.

But here the surface-to-volume ratio is the worst. Finally, the experts described chocolate powder as the "holy grail". If the EFSA gives it a clean bill of health, then all the other products are no longer a problem.

However, some experts were more critical of the choice of product. One noted that chocolate is not an appropriate choice as it is an impact product. He further explained that it is very elaborate with different foils and great designs. Another expert added that chocolate can also be a difficult product to work with due to migration. Finally, one voice pointed out that coffee is extremely sensitive in terms of sensory properties. Because of its surface, coffee has the potential to absorb foreign odours.

Most experts agreed on the choice of coffee and chocolate as project products, considering them challenging but suitable due to their high quality material requirements and moderate risk levels. Non-food products such as facial masks, detergents and wet wipes were not considered critical due to limited exposure, although caution is advised for products used on sensitive areas such as babies' bottoms. Chocolate powder was seen as key, with EFSA approval potentially resolving issues for all products. Despite reservations about the impact product status of chocolate and the sensitivity of coffee to foreign odours, most experts supported the product choices.

4.4.8 Influence on market acceptance

Several factors could influence the acceptance of the Circular packaging on the market. The most frequently mentioned one is aesthetics. On the one hand, same aesthetical properties like transparency are required, on the other hand, by appropriate measures of communication, trade-offs could be accepted in favor of recycled material. It seems unclear in how far business consumers would really make compromises with this regard. Consumers' assessment of aesthetical properties is also described in chapter 4.5.2 of this report. Price is another factor. We provide a more detailed examination of this factor in subchapter 4.4.9. Sealing performance is a technical challenge, and could limit the market acceptance if not solved appropriately. Furthermore, infrastructural factors, like integrability in existing processes, affected or reduced shelf-life of food products, the applications and target groups, or safety concerns could influence market acceptance as well. Competition as an influence factor will be discussed in chapter 4.4.10. One expert mentioned long-term sustainability as an issue. Goals are adapted regularly, and it remains open how to measure them.

Influencing factors for market acceptance are inter alia aesthetical characteristics, price, and technical performance of the Circular packaging.

4.4.9 Price

In the business sector, participants expect price premiums for the PE PCR material as realistic and accepted by the industry. One expert stated that in the beginning, whatever price premium would be paid by the industry because the product CIRCULAR FoodPack aims to develop is wanted and needed by the whole industry. She assessed mechanically recycled food-grade packaging as "the top-notch product that everybody wants to have. If we are talking about the Holy Grail that you are promising to deliver, it is as simple as that: Whoever is first will make a lot of money until other companies develop similar products. You could put whichever price you want – until it becomes mainstream available and the availability is limited. People are desperate to get their hands on a product like that."

Other experts are more skeptical regarding the acceptance of higher prices for this kind of packaging. Another common opinion of some experts is that there might only be an acceptance of price premiums if there are policy regulations that require the use of recycled packaging in the respective sectors. If the price difference is too large and combined with the fact that there is no legal requirement, this might slow down the uptake of recycled material. Prices are “sky rocketing” at the moment and the circumstances are difficult. She fears that economic aspects unfortunately may slow down the whole Circular economy ambitions. Prices are very unstable at the moment, but several experts think that at least the business sector might accept price increases up to 20% compared to conventional packaging. One expert noted that the competition coming from virgin material will dictate the price, and other packaging materials like paper or carton will be challenging the market. There will also be differences regarding price aspects and acceptances between different countries.

Estimations about acceptance of price increases of end customers are rather pessimistic. It depends on the product categories/application and target groups, but end customers are unlikely to accept price increases, even small ones are already seen as deal breaker. This is also depending on the recycles content. One expert explained that consumers might consider packaging with recycles contents below 75% as greenwashing only. We give more insights on this in the chapter about the results of the consumer focus groups in chapter 6.

Experts consider it possible that business customers are willing to pay higher prices for the Circular packaging. However, the major driving force is expected to be needed from politics.

4.4.10 Competition

Since the market for packaging solutions is a very important one and a transition towards Circularity and sustainability is needed, there is competition. There are many stakeholders, many projects, many different approaches that are ongoing to contribute to a more sustainable and Circular packaging industry. This is reflected by the experts’ assessment. Two experts emphasized that competition is what the sector actually also needs, because it is a free market. On the one hand, there seems to be enough space for everyone to occupy their corner on the market, on the other hand, experts fear that there is a risk of a too much fractionated market, and too many resources might be used for different technologies. Therefore, it might be an opportunity to align some of these research projects in order to gain more scale quickly. Due to the number of ongoing research and development concepts, timing is an important influence factor. One expert summarizes this with the following statement: “The question is which one will break through. You do not know who will win”.

When we asked the interviewees for concrete competitive approaches compared to CIRCULAR FoodPack, experts declared two following unique characteristics of the project: “CIRCULAR FoodPack goes beyond the aims of the other projects”; “In the area of PE PCR, there are some projects, but they mostly deal with only one part of your project”; “CIRCULAR FoodPack is the only other project that also focuses on the quality of the recycles”; “Other similar projects are not as extensive as CIRCULAR FoodPack, so it is not really comparable.”

Concrete technologies and companies that the experts mentioned, were, for instance, one technology provider² who is dealing with decolorization. They are already in the scaling up phase and they are working with large brand owners like PG and Unilever. Several PE companies, e.g., Borealis, sabic industries, and DOW Chemical, are all working on solutions for recycled PE.

So “the giants of the PE industry” are all working on PE recycling. HolyGrail 2.0 with the technology of digital watermarks is a strong competitor regarding sorting technologies, this was mentioned by several experts.

As to competing technologies with mechanical recycling, the experts mentioned mainly chemical recycling. This has, according to the experts, advantages like to produce clearer material, gain more safety in terms of product quality, and the regulations are less strict than for mechanical recycling technologies. However, it is more expensive, and it has less environmental benefits due to higher CO₂ emissions and the use of chemicals. Time is also a factor in the competition between chemical and mechanical recycling. At what time the approval for food-grade material is provided to a technology might be a decisive factor, and how much time it takes to scale up a respective technology, as well. Regarding the approach with mechanical recycling, that the CIRCULAR FoodPack project follows, the majority of experts is not very optimistic that the EFSA will give its approval as food-grade material anytime soon.

Other materials pose competition, as well. Especially from an end-of-life standpoint there is always the prospect of competitive threat from other packaging formats e.g., steel cans, glass, paper, aluminum. Those all have the potential to benefit from the bad perception of plastics of the public. Glass takes lot of energy to be produced, distributed and recycled, it has really good conservation and food-safety properties, but it can break fairly easy, and it is quite heavy and difficult to handle. But if the end-of-life is a bigger concern then it will always win over plastic, the same holds true for steel or aluminum cans according to the assessment of one expert. Some companies are already shifting their packaging material. Consumers’ preferences regarding packaging materials are described in chapter 4.5.1. However, not all products allow to be packaged in any type of material. If certain food products cannot come along with a paper packaging, for instance, because they have distinct needs for functional barrier properties, then recycled plastic packaging could be a good alternative. It seems useful to communicate this background to the consumers in order to get higher acceptance.

There is much competition in research and development of Circular and sustainable packaging. CIRCULAR FoodPack has outstanding characteristics, like the combination of many technologies. Timeframe regarding approval from authorities and for scaling up is crucial in competing with other technologies. Other materials pose also high competition, especially because end consumers have aversion of plastic as packaging material.

² The name of the company is something like Ionica (?), but was not clearly understood in the interview

4.5 Results of qualitative consumer focus groups

In the following subchapter, we present the results from the eight consumer focus groups in the four different countries. Results of all focus groups are displayed in an aggregated manner. In case that there are significant differences between the countries, this is indicated accordingly.

4.5.1 Consumers' preferences

Consumers' preferences regarding food packaging

Consumers were asked which kind of packaging they prefer in general and for certain food products. Most participants stated that they prefer packaging made from paper/cardboard. The limitation here is that it breaks easily, and that it is not applicable for all products. Glass was another highly favored packaging. Reasons for this were that it is seen as easily recyclable, food products are assumed to taste better when packed in glass, and that it is a qualitative packaging. One participant said, "Glass is the high value-added packaging par excellence" (focus group in Lyon at 6 October 2022). Limitations of glass, however, were mentioned as well. It is heavy and especially for people who live in cities and do not do their groceries by car, buying products packed in glass is too inconvenient. Furthermore, glass takes more place for storage and is therefore not practical. Also, it is fragile and breaks easily. Many participants expressed that they like to buy especially fruits and vegetable without packaging at all. Next to saving packaging waste, it is seen as advantageous to see the single food items and to be able to pick out selected ones. However, some participants disagreed and assessed it as unhygienic to buy food items unpacked because it could be contaminated when, e.g., lying on the checkout belt. Furthermore, food products are often more expensive when they are offered in glass or without packaging at all, which consumers disliked. Most participants expressed their aversion of plastic as packaging material due to different reasons (e.g., environmental reasons, health concerns, etc.). Some participants, however, saw benefits in plastic packaging because it is resistant, practical and light in weight.

Apart from naming preferred materials, some participants also stated that they would like to avoid packaging that is made from different materials with different layers, and that they preferred recycled packaging in general. We asked all participants about their preferences for recycled or new packaging. Most participants said they preferred recycled packaging due to environmental reasons. Some participants, however, did not have preferences with this regard. They did not care whether the packaging is recycled or not, or what kind of packaging it is at all, this is (at least for known and preferred products) not part of the purchase decision. However, a recycled packaging would not prevent most persons from buying a particular product. In any case, for most of the participants the product itself is much more important than the packaging. Not much attention and awareness is paid to the packaging. This means, that people buy habitually and would not stop buying distinct products in case the packaging would change. What people do pay attention for is how much content of the respective product is in the packaging. In case the packaging would change, many people are suspicious if the packaging contains fewer content of the product for the same price, which is not appreciated.

In summary, most people spoke out against plastic and preferred alternative materials like paper or glass, although this goes along with certain disadvantages that are mentioned above. In general, the consumers do not pay much attention to packaging and the food product itself is much more important than its packaging.

Consumers' preferences regarding design of food packaging

We also asked consumers about their preferences regarding the design of packaging. Participants gave very different answers and have personal preferences regarding aesthetics of packaging for different products. For representative statements, a more quantitative survey would be needed. However, we can already present some qualitative preferences with a broad range from colorful to natural colors, from unpretentious to lively and eye-catching. Comfortable haptic is also a mentioned characteristic, especially since for some persons recycled packaging obviously has the reputation of feeling too rough and being ugly. Many people stated that it is important for them that the packaging looks attractive. However, as mentioned earlier in the paragraph, the packaging per se is not part of the purchase decision for already known products. Our findings regarding design could therefore be especially interesting for newly introduced products. Design preferences are also dependent on the type of product that is inside the respective packaging. Another factor is packaging size. It is undesirable for participants to have packaging that is too big for the respective amount of product. It would be approved if the packaging size is adapted to the respective content. Also, people appreciate if there are no residues in the packaging.

Regarding packaging design, people have very individual preferences.

Consumers' preferences regarding non-food packaging

We posed the participants of the focus groups also questions about their preferences regarding packaging of home and personal care products. Again, many people stated that they do not pay attention about the packaging of the home and personal care products they buy. The product itself is, again, more important. These products are often only available with plastic packaging. Therefore, many of the participants buy them without having an alternative, but only few persons would even care about another type of packaging. Some participants try to avoid plastic packaging, but this is hard to achieve due to the relative absence of alternatives. Detergent seems to be available in a cardboard box, and this packaging is preferred by some participants due to ecological reasons. Few people prefer plastic packaging due to comfortability reasons for all home and personal care products. Two participants mentioned that they would, for instance, prefer face cream in a glass packaging because it gives a better feeling of quality. Unpacked products are no option, except for solid shampoo, which is not used to due comfortability and quality expectations.

Several participants mentioned that they use refill packages when it comes to home and personal care products like, e.g., soap and shampoo. Some persons stated that by this, they try to reduce packaging, others said that the refill packs are in plastic anyway, so it unfortunately would not make that much difference. The mentioned problems with the refill system is that the refill packaging is often only available for a limited time. In addition, it is only possible to gain certain particular products, and it is, according to single persons, not suitable for high quality products.

Several participants seem to have aversion against plastic packaging for home and personal care products, but due to missing alternatives as well as due to the relative unimportance of the type of packaging, people buy these products in the available packaging, which mostly is some kind of plastic. Refill systems are no permanent solution currently.

4.5.2 Consumers' expectations

Consumers' expectations regarding food packaging

Although many participants of the focus groups stated their aversion against plastic, for many of them it is very important that they are able to see the respective product through the packaging. This is because they want to check the quality of the product, or see how the content of the packaging actually looks like. This holds true for different product categories, for instance, cereals, dairy products, etc. Another important feature is that the packaging is resistant. They expect the packaging to protect the food products, and it should not leak, not break easily, be durable, and give extra solidity. Food safety and hygienic protection of the food items by the packaging are very important for consumers. Additionally, easiness and practicability of the packaging are relevant characteristics. Furthermore, the packaging should be easy and neat to open and close, and preferably resealable. Convenience is a key factor for consumers, purchasing decisions are made very quickly, grocery shopping needs to be integrated in everyday life easily and flexibly. Therefore, refill is not always an option because people would have to plan bringing their own containers in advance and would not be so flexible anymore. Reducing packaging in the "consumer society" seems unlikely anyway for many. An often mentioned advantage of pre-packaged food is that it contains a best before date.

It is most important for consumers to see the food product through the packaging. It should also be easy to handle and be practical, convenience is a key factor.

Consumers' expectations regarding non-food packaging

For cosmetics, the expectations regarding practicability and simple handling are the same as for food packaging. For some people, an optically attractive packaging design is more important in the sector of cosmetic and personal care than for food products.

Consumers' assessment of an ideal packaging (for food products)

When we asked the participants about ideal packaging in their personal opinion, they answered with the characteristics that are listed in the following (multiple answers per person possible):

- Biodegradable
- Practical
- Reusable
- Refillable
- Easy to open and close and resealable
- No packaging at all
- Glass
- Paper
- Depending on the purpose
- "I think the ideal packaging for each product is the one that fulfils its function and poses as few problems as possible, both practical and moral."
- Plastic for convenience, glass for hygiene
- Practicability is more important than environmentally-friendly
- No microplastics
- No pollution

The participants did not name plastic as an ideal packaging, their expectations and descriptions of an ideal packaging were very different.

Consumers' assessment of the most sustainable packaging (for food products)

In a next step, we asked participants to give their personal expectations of the most sustainable packaging. Again, their answers are listed in the following:

- Glass (most frequent answer)
- Bioplastics/biodegradable (second most frequent answer)
- Tetrapak (single answer)
- Paper (single answer)
- No packaging at all (single answer)

Participants of the focus groups evaluate glass and bioplastics/biodegradable packaging as the most sustainable forms of packaging in general.

4.5.3 Consumers' acceptance

Consumers' acceptance regarding food packaging

Willingness to pay

We asked the participants about their willingness to pay for a more environmentally-friendly food packaging. Most participants are not willing to pay more for this. An often-mentioned argument was that prices are rising for everything at the moment due to rising inflation rates, they feel disadvantaged therefore anyway, and that they would not be willing to spend more for packaging. In addition, some participants took the view that not end consumers should be the ones to pay the higher prices for this kind of packaging, but the food companies. Some persons claim that more environmentally-friendly packaging should even be less expensive than conventional one.

Some participants could imagine to maybe pay a higher price for the packaging, but strongly depending on how much more. The increase must be in proportion and clearly traceable, because suspicions raise that companies only pursue greenwashing and aim for higher profits. Some participants might be willing to pay a few cents more, but only reluctantly.

When asked about their willingness to pay a price premium for environmentally-friendly packaging, many participants independently answered that they would be willing to pay more for species- appropriate animal husbandry instead. This indicates that other factors next to the quality/characteristics of the food product itself are more important for the consumers than packaging, accompanying a higher willingness to pay for those other factors.

A significant raise of costs for more environmentally-friendly packaging would not be accepted according to the majority of the participants. Under certain circumstances, some participants would be willing to pay only a small price premium.

Positive associations with recycled packaging

Positive associations with recycled packaging cover, in general, a broad range. Some participants simply stated that they think recycled packaging is a good thing, even/especially when it is recycled several times. This is mainly due to environmental reasons. However, participants expected the recycled packaging to have the same quality and aesthetics as a new packaging, although some would accept to make compromises. One often raised aspect is that consumers have a better conscience when they buy products in recycled packaging. It gives them the feeling of making a compensation for the environment and feel better about themselves. However, also in this context, the restriction is made that the price for the recycled packaging should not be higher than for a new one. Most of the participants did not have concerns regarding the safety, quality and contamination issues of recycled packaging. The trust of participants is high in engineers, authorities, legal requirements, and controls with this regard.

Negative associations with recycled packaging

There were negative associations coming up, as well. For instance, some persons would not be willing to accept lower aesthetical requirements of the recycled materials, and therefore their trust in the packaging would be compromised. Some fear that the recycled packaging would be less resistant, and that it loses value compared to new packaging. These statements originate mainly from the French and Spanish focus groups. Several participants did not trust in recycling at all, they categorized the efforts as greenwashing, and that it does not really serve a purpose. Recycled packaging is furthermore associated with higher costs, which is not favorable. Moreover, several participants of the French focus groups raised concerns about health risks and contamination through the recycled packaging. Consumers in the French focus groups furthermore expressed their feeling that they are fooled, because they pay the packaging, do the effort for recycling, but by taxes on waste they pay the recycling, and then they pay for the packaging again. This leads to further negative attitudes towards recycling and the expenses that come along with it.

Doubts and trust issues are raised against recycling in general in all focus groups. Participants were skeptical, how and if materials really get recycled, and if this really is a sustainable solution. The credibility of companies was questioned as well, they were accused of making profit from claiming to recycle packaging, and that recycling claims only serve the purpose of greenwashing. For some people, this leads to the overall rejection of recycled packaging.

It became also clear during the conduction of the focus groups, that consumers lack information and knowledge about recycling in general. This refers to both the process and benefits of recycling, as well as the characteristics of recycled packaging compared to new one. Furthermore, consumers cannot identify which packaging is recycled at the point of sales. Desires were expressed for clear and transparent declarations of recycled packaging. But even then, not all consumers were sure to prefer the recycled version, and sometimes even the declaration "recycled packaging" is perceived as a mere marketing measure and is therefore not appreciated by the consumers. In everyday life, grocery and household shopping must go fast, and people do not often take the time to read all declarations on a product/packaging.

Consumers have both positive and negative associations with recycled packaging. Purchasing products with recycled packaging triggers good conscience. Many customers have reluctance and trust issues regarding recycling.

4.5.4 Consumers' assessment of packaging from a mixture of recycled and new material as in CIRCULAR FoodPack

We asked participants about their assessment of packaging that is made from both recycled and virgin material. In all focus groups, the first reactions were lack of understanding, skepticism and negative impressions ("Why only 50% recycled content?"). People did not see a meaning in this, and were rather frustrated about this obviously non-consistent and complicated solution. Concrete statements were, that "it is not thought through from beginning to end", "the story is missing", "I do not have the feeling of having saved something", "it' a sham", "it's a lot of rubbish to mix recycled with new plastic", "it is not green", "unnecessary and complicated", etc. After having explained the reason why part of a recycled PE packaging is virgin material, some people were appeased. Therefore, the communication about why also virgin material is included in the recycled packaging has to be extremely careful and clear on why this makes sense, why only a part is recycled material, why it is mixed with virgin material, etc. Due to the sensitivity of this topic, there should be either proper, sensitive and transparent communication or no communication at all about the recycled content in order to gain the acceptance of the customers.

Some participants were more unbiased regarding their first impression. Statements have been made like "if industrially there is no other choice, it is fine with me", "it's better than a product surrounded by new packaging", "as interim solution it would be ok", "50% is better than 0 %", "if you can't see the difference, why not", etc. However, no participant assessed a packaging with 50% recycled and 50% new content as a permanent solution. Higher shares of recycling content are seen as desirable.

The first reaction of most people was negative with regard to a packaging made from both recycled and new packaging. They did not understand why virgin material was added at first sight and therefore condemned the packaging. Communication must either be very sensitive and transparent, or there should be no communication about the recycled content at all to get customers' acceptance.

4.5.5 Additionally gathered information from the consumer focus groups

Personal problems with plastic

In an additional section, we asked participants about their individual personal concerns regarding plastics. The received answers are listed in the following:

- Too much quantity of packaging waste and littering (most frequent answer)
- Individual health issues (second most frequent answer, mainly participants of French focus groups)
- Fossil based and energy intense production
- Environmental issues, like taking a long time to degrade, micro plastics, marine pollution, etc.

Waste separation

The topic of waste separation was a lively discussed topic. Many participants stated to regularly separate their waste, but there are several limiting factors. The three biggest obstacles are:

1. Doubts that the products really will be recycled instead of everything being put in the landfill in the end
2. Confusion about allocation of packaging/materials to the respective bins
3. Space issues for different bins

Further factors are time issues, no awareness, comfortability reasons, and lack of infrastructure. There are very different systems regarding waste separation in the different countries. Especially participants of the French focus groups expressed their displeasure about too few and too full containers/bins especially in the cities.

People are overwhelmed by the waste separation system. Main obstacles for waste separation in households are trust issues, confusion and space issues.

4.5.6 Methodological limitations

There were some limitations coming along with the method of conducting focus groups. First, we used a qualitative approach for data collection with a non-representative sample. Data results are explorative and we do not make claims to representativeness in this first round of data collection. Second, all focus groups were conducted in big cities. Inhabitants of smaller cities or villages, or who do not live in metropolitan areas might have answered differently due to, for instance, different infrastructural circumstances or different modes of shopping behaviors. Furthermore, consumers in big cities might run their errands more often without using a car. This might influence purchase behavior with respect to the weight of packaging, e.g., glass.

4.6 Results of quantitative consumer web survey

A significant bottleneck for the success of such business models is the transition from feasibility in the pilot phase to achieving market maturity and implementability (Dijkstra et al., 2020). Consumers play a central role in this development process, as they are the ones who ultimately have to buy the packaging. A comprehensive understanding of the packaging-specific preferences, acceptance and expectations of consumers in the different countries is therefore essential in order to make the necessary adjustments.

4.6.1 General Information

The data collected from a total of 4001 respondents resulted in a gender distribution of 49.99 % female, 0.37 % diverse and 49.64 % male participants. Of these, 54.65 % lived in cities, 18.62 % in suburbs and 26.74 % in rural areas.

The bar chart below illustrates the distribution of age groups within the sample. The age groups 20- 29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-59 and 60-69 were represented in similar proportions, with a slight preponderance of 50- to 59-year-olds, who made up 20 % of the sample. The youngest age group, under 20, was represented with 3 % and the over 70s with 7 %.

Figure 3 Distribution of respondents by age group (Source: Own compilation of Ecozept)

When looking at the target group for sustainable packaging, there is disagreement in the literature, especially in socio-economic factors such as age and gender. The literature review by Ketelsen et al. sheds light on the gender-specific influence on preferences for environmentally-friendly packaging, with women being attributed a pronounced interest in the degradability of packaging and the reduction of packaging waste. In contrast, men showed a higher sensitivity towards the environmentally relevant aspects of packaging (Ketelsen et al., 2020). Other research findings emphasize that women are generally more environmentally aware and their consumption decisions are more influenced by environmental considerations (Čater and Serafimova, 2019; Lazaric et al., 2020; Susanty et al., 2021).

With regard to age, research has found a positive relationship between age and environmental awareness and recycling behavior. On the other hand, studies show that younger consumers are more aware (Brennan et al., 2021; Čater and Serafimova, 2019; Jaderná and Volfová, 2022). Furthermore, previous work has indeed shown that more educated people are more aware of environmental issues and therefore more inclined to behave in an environmentally-friendly way (Susanty et al., 2021).

The analysis evaluated all hypotheses in the context of five socio-demographic factors (age, gender, income, country, neighborhood) to create a detailed profile. In line with the existing literature, no uniform consumer profile could be identified in this study either. As the following results illustrate, no clear profile can be identified with regard to gender. However, it should be noted that people with diverse gender identities tend to give more extreme answers. However, this could be due to the small sample size of N=15. No significant differences can be observed between the urban and rural population or between countries. Some stronger correlations can be seen with increasing age and income, although these observations should not be generalized.

4.6.2 Consumers' preferences

Preferences regarding packaging material

Figure 4: Distribution of preferences regarding packaging materials (Source: Own compilation of Ecozept)

As can be seen in the diagram above, consumers were asked about various packaging materials and their preference. They were able to choose between 1 (disfavored very much) and 5 (preferred very much). The number 3 represents a neutral opinion, which is indicated by the red line.

An ANOVA analysis of variance was used to test whether there were differences in the preference for packaging materials. The asymptotic significance (<0.001) showed that there were significant differences between the ratings of the materials. In order to know where these differences lie, a post-hoc test called Bonferroni adjustment was performed. This showed that there were significant differences in preference between all packaging materials. Only between bio-based packaging and paper, bio-based packaging and recycled plastic, and paper and recycled plastic are there no differences in preference. These are preferred to the same extent.

The most popular packaging material is biodegradable packaging material, followed in equal measure by 100 % recycled plastic, bio-based packaging and cardboard. The Circular FoodPack- packaging is in third place. The least popular packaging material is plastic.

When the above analysis is broken down by gender, the picture is broadly similar. However, it should be noted that there is a difference between diverse people and women and between diverse people and men when it comes to bio-based packaging. Men and women prefer bio-based packaging more than diverse people.

In the case of biodegradable packaging and recycled plastic, there is only a difference between men and women. Women prefer recycled plastic and biodegradable packaging slightly more than men.

Recycled plastic, the second most popular packaging material, plays a key role in the Circular FoodPack concept. Our latest survey has provided additional insights that reveal a nuanced understanding of consumer attitudes. On the one hand, the average score of 3.9 indicating agreement with the statement "I would prefer recycled food packaging if I had a choice" confirms the trend of consumer preference for packaging materials. On the other hand, an average score of

2.46 in response to the statement "I am convinced that recycled food packaging is unhygienic" suggests that despite a general openness to recycled plastic packaging, some reservations about hygiene remain. This suggests the need for targeted education on the safety and hygiene standards of recycling processes to increase acceptance and confidence in recycled food packaging.

Preferences regarding packaging design

Figure 5: Distribution of preferences regarding design elements.

Source: Own compilation of Ecozept (via. SPSS).

The figure shows consumers' preferences for packaging designs. They were able to move the slider to the degree that best reflected their opinion.

An ANOVA analysis of variance was used to test whether there were differences in preference for packaging design. The asymptotic significance of <0.001 indicated that there were significant differences between the materials. Post-hoc Bonferroni adjustment was used to identify where these differences lie. Based on this analysis, there are significant differences in preference between all packaging designs, except design and symmetry. As the results for the design features are almost centered around the neutral point, it can be concluded that the designs are individually different. The survey also looked at the importance of design in general purchase decisions. On a scale of 1 (very unimportant) to 5 (very important), this question received an average score of 2.4. This suggests that packaging design is not typically considered to be the most important factor in purchasing decisions.

In summary, it can be said that consumers do not clearly prefer a specific design for sustainable packaging. They tend to prefer symmetric, recycled look, restrained design, natural colors and more information when it comes to sustainable packaging.

When the analysis is broken down by gender, the only significant differences between men and women are in colour, symmetry and appearance.

Women lean slightly more towards a new look, symmetry and natural colors. Nevertheless, the general direction remains the same.

Preferences regarding packaging feature

Figure 6: Distribution of preferences regarding packaging features

Source: Own compilation of Ecozept (via. SPSS).

The graph shows the mean values of preference for the packaging attributes. The different attributes are plotted on the x-axis and the mean values are plotted on the y-axis. Respondents were asked to rate the importance of each feature on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important).

As with the previous two evaluations, the first step was to check whether there were any differences in preference between the features. This was done using an ANOVA analysis of variance.

The ANOVA analysis of variance carried out showed that there were statistically significant differences (<0.001) between the features examined. A post-hoc Bonferroni correction was applied to further differentiate these differences. This analysis showed that there were significant differences for all the packaging characteristics considered, with the exception of the pairings between handling and use of recycled materials, and between stability and recyclability.

The stability and recyclability of packaging materials emerge as primary characteristics of central importance to consumers. Following these in the hierarchy of importance are the ease of handling and the proportion of recycled material, which are considered secondary factors. The weight of the packaging assumes a subordinate role. Meanwhile, the transparency and design of the packaging are rated as comparatively neutral to less essential, which relativizes their significance in the context of consumer preferences.

Upon a detailed examination of evaluations segmented by gender, differences across all categories between men and women become evident.

Women tend to rate all characteristics consistently as more important than men. There are no significant discrepancies in the evaluations between women and individuals of diverse gender identities, or between men and individuals of diverse gender identities.

4.6.3 Consumers' expectations

Willingness to overpay for sustainable packaging

Figure 7: Distribution of willingness to overpay regarding sustainable packaging.

Source: Own compilation of Ecozept (via. SPSS)

In order to assess the market potential of Circular food packaging, it is essential to understand customer expectations in terms of pricing. Therefore, the study also explored the willingness to pay for innovative product packaging technologies, including the extent to which participants would be willing to pay more for such innovations.

The illustration shows individuals with a higher willingness to pay for sustainable product packaging. It is noticeable that the willingness to pay a premium for sustainable packaging is quite similar across all packaging materials. This observation was further confirmed by an ANOVA analysis of variance, which found no significant difference between the different packaging materials.

On average, respondents would be willing to pay about 12-13 % more for all the packaging mentioned above.

However, it should be noted that a significant proportion of respondents (40-48%) are not willing to pay more for sustainable packaging. For example, 48% of respondents are not willing to pay more for carton packaging. More details on this can be found in the table opposite.

Table 4 Percentage of people who are not willing to pay more for sustainable packaging (source: Ecozept)

Packaging material	Percentage (%)
Cardboard	48,0
Biodegradeable	40,3
Recycled	43,5
Recyclable	44,5
Hybrid models like Circular FoodPack-packaging	45,6
Biobased	43,9

Source: Own compilation of Ecozept.

Additionally, no statistically significant difference in the perception of all packaging types among men, women, and individuals of diverse gender identities can be observed.

Correlation between willingness to pay and personal impact/leverage.

To understand how expectations can alter willingness to pay for sustainable packaging, it is important to consider the individual influence on the choice of sustainable packaging options. In this context, the relationship between willingness to pay and perceived personal environmental impact of using sustainable packaging materials was examined. Using the Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.167, a positive but weak correlation was found. However, the statistical significance of this correlation, indicated by a p-value of less than 0.01, cannot be ignored.

The hypothesis shows a significant, but weak correlation ($p <= 0.001$). This result indicates that people who see the purchase of sustainable packaging as an environmentally-friendly measure, tend to be willing to pay more for it. However, this relationship is weak.

The analysis of the Pearson correlation, segmented by gender, reveals that both men ($r=0.15$) and women ($r=0.17$) exhibit only a minimal correlation. In contrast, for individuals identifying as diverse, with a correlation coefficient of $r=0.07$, no significant relationship is discernible.

These findings suggest that among men and women, there is a modest but perceptible link between a heightened awareness of personal environmental impacts from using sustainable packaging and their willingness to pay. This contrasts with individuals who identify as diverse, amongst whom this correlation is not observable.

Product safety and new product developments

There is a general consensus that stakeholders have the same expectations of product safety for both conventional and sustainable packaging, not least because of legislation. The real question is whether consumers have confidence in the product safety of new product developments.

This specific issue has been thoroughly investigated in the present study. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to test this.

The result, with an r -value of 0.430, indicates that there is a significant correlation between consumer trust in new product developments and their perceived product safety.

Looking at this question in terms of gender, the data suggests that trust in the safety of new products varies according to gender identity. Individuals with a diverse gender identity show the highest level of trust (with a correlation coefficient of 0.622), indicating a strong positive relationship between their gender identity and trust in the safety of new products. Women follow with a moderate level of trust (correlation coefficient of 0.469), while men show the least trust in the safety of new product developments (correlation coefficient of 0.387).

These data imply that men tend to be more sceptical about the safety of new products compared to women, and especially compared to individuals of diverse gender identity.

4.6.4 Consumers' acceptance

As mentioned at the beginning of this section, many new products fail during their market introduction, often due to a lack of consumer acceptance (Dijkstra et al., 2020). The Technology Acceptance Model provides a framework for preventing such failures by understanding and influencing consumer acceptance. This model is an integral part of acceptance research, which encompasses a variety of aspects and dimensions. According to Everett M. Rogers, a pioneer in acceptance research, the acceptance or rejection of innovations is determined by a social process and a series of actions. (Rogers, E. M., 2003). In business research, acceptance is often divided into attitudes and behaviours.

These two models of acceptance go hand in hand. Behavioural acceptance aims to explain behaviour and emphasize the importance of appropriate behaviour. This area of research places particular emphasis on the internal processes of an individual. Attitudinal acceptance includes affective and conative, cognitive perceptual orientations, which were investigated in this study (Müller-Böling, D. et al., 1986).

Influence of knowledge on acceptance

In the scientific research, the null hypothesis (H_0) was that there is no significant correlation between consumers' level of knowledge about sustainable packaging and their frequency of purchasing such packaging. A Pearson correlation analysis was used to test this hypothesis.

The results of the analysis indicate a significant ($p < 0,001$) correlation ($r = 0.440$), suggesting that an increased awareness and knowledge of sustainable packaging are indeed associated with a higher frequency of purchasing these products.

When analysing the relationship between the level of knowledge about sustainable packaging and the frequency of purchasing such products, differentiated by gender, different correlation coefficients emerged. For men, a positive correlation of 0.465 was observed, indicating a moderate relationship. Women also showed a positive correlation, albeit slightly weaker, with a value of 0.417. Conversely, people with diverse gender identities showed a correlation of 0.099, indicating no relationship.

These findings indicate a weak positive correlation across all genders, with females exhibiting slightly higher correlation, suggesting a somewhat stronger association between waste separation conscientiousness and positive disposition towards sustainable packaging compared to males and individuals of diverse gender identity.

Influence of feelings on acceptance

To investigate consumer acceptance, the null hypothesis (H_0) was proposed that there is no significant relationship between the propensity to purchase sustainable packaging and the rate at which these packages are purchased. The subsequent Pearson correlation analysis yielded a coefficient of 0.280.

A correlation coefficient of 0.280 a p-value of <0.001 indicates a weak, but significant positive correlation. This means that while there is a slight association between the positive disposition towards sustainable packaging and the actual frequency of purchasing these products, this relationship is not strongly pronounced. The disposition towards sustainable packaging seems to be somewhat connected to the purchasing frequency, but the influence is relatively minor.

When analyzing the relationship between attitudes towards sustainable packaging and purchase frequency by gender, different correlations were observed: male participants showed a moderate positive correlation ($r=0.308$), followed by female participants with a weak positive correlation ($r=0.254$), while individuals with different gender identities showed a negative correlation ($r=-0.336$).

These results suggest that while there is a general tendency among men and women to purchase sustainable packaging more frequently when they have a positive attitude towards it, this trend might be negatively correlated in individuals with diverse gender identities. The findings emphasize the importance of considering variations in consumer behaviour by gender and point to the complexity of the relationship between attitude and purchasing behaviour.

Connection between waste separation and attitude towards sustainable packaging

The null hypothesis for this study is that there is a relationship between waste separation conscientiousness and attitudes towards sustainable packaging. Based on the Pearson correlation analysis conducted, a correlation coefficient of 0.269 was found.

A correlation coefficient of 0.269 indicates a weak but positive correlation. This result suggests that people who are more conscientious about waste separation tend to have a more positive attitude towards sustainable packaging.

The positive correlation reveals that there is a certain relationship between environmentally conscious behaviour in the form of waste separation and attitudes towards sustainable packaging, even though this relationship is not strongly pronounced.

In a gender-disaggregated analysis of the relationship between conscientiousness in waste separation and attitudes towards sustainable packaging, the following correlation coefficients were observed: males showed a correlation of $r=0.240$, females $r=0.297$ and people with a diverse gender identity $r=0.206$.

4.7 SWOT analysis

To enhance the strengths of the project, mitigate weaknesses, seize opportunities and neutralize threats, we present the first version of a SWOT analysis in

Table 5 as interim result. So far, aspects from the product description, results from the first round of expert interviews, and results from the consumer focus groups were the base for the analysis. The SWOT plus A will be periodically revised and finalized throughout the course of the project.

Table 5: SWOT analysis for market opportunities of Circular packaging for food, home and personal care products of Circular FoodPack

	<i>Helpful to achieving the objective</i>	<i>Harmful to achieving the objective</i>
<i>Internal origin (attributes of the system)</i>	<p style="text-align: center;">Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative circular packaging solution: The products offer a novel approach to packaging that is well aligned with current trends towards sustainability and Circularity. • Circular FoodPack solutions offer a unique approach to incorporating recycle into packaging, particularly with polyolefins, which has not been achieved before. • Pose a more environmentally-friendly packaging solution (LCA). • Strong scientific and technological knowledge on the fields. • Suitability for non-food products: The versatility of the circular packaging solution extends to non-food products. • Suitability non-food products offers simplicity and potential market expansion. • Awareness of food safety regulations: Circular FoodPack is seeking regulatory approval, such as from EFSA, to make it market-ready and increase its credibility. • Closed-loop initiative: Emphasises mechanical recycling in line with industry preferences and contributes to a closed-loop packaging system. • Establishes a closed-loop recycling system, maximising material life within the recycling process and reducing resource consumption and carbon emissions associated with incineration. • Stakeholder involvement: Involves stakeholders from different stages of the value chain ensures practicality and effectiveness. • Creation of new value chains: based on recycled polymers, targeting the food packaging market and meeting the needs of the packaging industry. • Distinguishes itself by considering the entire life cycle of the product, from collection to recycling, while incorporating recycled content into food packaging. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of the food approval process: The lengthy food approval process for recycled materials is a significant challenge. • Market opportunities highly dependent on approval by regulatory bodies such as EFSA • Complex value chain: Complex value chain adds complexity to the implementation process • Value-added depends on the ability to ensure a closed loop, which poses infrastructure and logistical challenges to collect enough material for multiple loops and to develop a collection system that works and causes the least risk of contamination. • The lack of recycling systems for packaging materials, combined with the high EU standards, are significant hurdles to overcome. • Close co-operation required between parties in the value chain • Technical restrictions and challenges of technologies • Uncertainties about the barrier concept • Some similar technological approaches already abandoned by the industry • Complexity of waste streams: The complexity of the waste streams and the challenges associated with sorting and recycling may jeopardise the achievement of predicted closure rates and ensuring quality control throughout the process. • Implementing marker-based sorting for food packaging feasible for large brands, but there are significant barriers to adoption outside of large retailers or brands. • Recycling challenges: Challenges related to the presence of non-intentionally added substances (NIAs) in recycled materials and concerns about the recyclability of multi-layer structures underline the technical complexity

- Innovative combination of technological approaches, including intermediate processes and products of interest to the market.
 - Increased use of recycled content: By incorporating recycled materials, the project promotes sustainability and reduces material accumulation, incineration, and waste.
 - Advanced sorting technologies: Development of advanced sorting technologies in the form of tracer technologies helps to improve recycling accuracy.
 - The focus is on working collection systems at scale and sufficient sorting, as these are key challenges for effective operation of multiple recycling loops.
 - Secondary materials available for reuse with similar properties to virgin materials to ensure a closed-loop Circular economy.
 - Ability to separate different plastic fractions from each other (food, non-food).
 - Mechanical and solvent based recycling process cascades enabling in total sufficient reduction of contaminants present in end-of- life packaging plastics.
 - **High market potential:** significant market demand for Circular packaging, especially for food products, indicating a strong growth opportunity.
 - There is a remarkable willingness among consumers to pay more: Approximately 50% of respondents are willing to pay approximately 12% more for sustainable packaging.
 - **Brand owner assessment:** Brand owners see a high market potential especially for non-food applications.
 - **Consumer preferences and engagement:** Consumers generally in favor of sustainable packaging, including the solution given by Circular FoodPack.
 - Analysis of consumer preferences reveals a strong interest in biodegradable packaging, recycled materials, and sustainable packaging features such as stability and recyclability.
 - Public knowledge and a positive attitude, which leads to greater acceptance.
 - Recycled and recyclable plastics are in high demand.
 - **Suitable product selection:** Coffee and chocolate are considered suitable products for initial efforts due to their high quality material requirements and moderate risk levels.
- of recycling processes.
 - Contamination and inadequate sorting could affect the performance and acceptability of the packaging solution.
 - **Consumer reluctance:** End-users are relatively reluctant to adapt new technologies
 - Despite a willingness to pay more for sustainable packaging, a significant proportion of consumers are still reluctant to invest in these products, indicating a potential barrier to widespread adoption.
 - Very individual consumer preferences regarding the acceptability of a change in the appearance of recycled packaging
 - **Cost considerations:** Requirement for competitive pricing compared to virgin materials presents challenges in achieving cost effectiveness, potentially limiting market competitiveness
 - Lack of clarity on pricing structure

<i>External origin (attributes of the environment)</i>	<h3>Opportunities</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory changes: Anticipated regulatory changes, such as the Plastic and Plastic Packaging Regulations (PPWR), present opportunities for Circular FoodPack solutions to align with evolving industry standards and regulations, enhancing its market acceptance. • Legislative advocacy: Circular FoodPack has the opportunity to advocate for legislative changes to address gaps and improve the regulatory framework, potentially facilitating the market introduction of innovative packaging solutions. • Legislation is becoming more and more demanding in terms of recycling quotas, which could be met by a circular packaging solution. • Synergistic collaboration between institutions: with complementary skills, ultimately achieving an integrated process along the entire product chain. • Required technologies and know-how available from consortium partners. • Involving stakeholders across the value chain provides opportunities for knowledge sharing, innovation, and practical solutions. • Development of value chain components: Explore the mechanical recycling route to meet EU recycled content targets and improve circularity of food packaging. • Collaboration with industry stakeholders and policy makers to address recycling infrastructure challenges could improve the viability of circular packaging solutions. • Extremely high market potential supported by favorable policy framework and individual brand owner targets. • Brand owners are interested in circular packaging solutions strengthened by the rapidly changing and beneficial legislation: PPWR. • Among Brand owners there is a need for recycled materials in higher percentages, as companies must pay penalties and taxes otherwise. The legislator triggers changes! • Leverage of increasing volumes and availability of flexible packaging. • Consumer engagement: Engaging consumers in the Circular packaging process through refill and prefill approaches provides an opportunity to increase consumer trust, convenience, and acceptance of sustainable packaging solutions. • Higher consumer attractiveness through providing a more sustainable packaging 	<h3>Threats</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory compliance: Changes in legislation and regulatory requirements may pose challenges to project compliance and market introduction, particularly in relation to EFSA novel technology registration. • Stringent regulatory requirements and bureaucratic processes can create barriers to innovation and market entry, particularly for novel technologies and recycled materials. • Uncertainty about regulatory requirements and approval processes can create barriers to market entry and investment. • Financial and economic viability: Limited uptake outside of major brands: Limited adoption of marker-based sorting outside of large retailers or brands can limit the scalability and impact of the solution. • Competitive landscape: Competition from alternative packaging solutions and established market players may pose a threat to the market penetration and success of the product. • Pressure from the virgin materials market, including lower prices and established supply chains, may threaten the competitiveness of recycled products. • Competition from alternative recycling processes and materials. • Resource constraints: Limited resources and infrastructure for closed-loop recycling systems can hinder the project's ability to ensure a closed loop and realize its full potential. • Disruptions in the supply of raw materials or the development of collection infrastructure can hamper circularity efforts and limit product availability. • Infrastructure challenges: Inadequate collection and sorting infrastructure, particularly in certain regions, can limit the availability of high quality recyclable materials, affecting the feasibility and scalability of circular packaging initiatives. • Brand owners: Little confidence in tracer technology and high expectations for artificial intelligence. • Low willingness to pay more for circular packaging solutions and related technologies among brand owners. • Retailers: Retailers are not willing to pay more for sustainable packaging solutions. • Consumer acceptance: Consumer acceptance of recycled packaging materials and functional

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive consumer associations with recycling (e.g., purchase of recycled packaging triggers a good conscience). • Align with consumer preferences and demonstrating a good LCA can lead to widespread adoption of circular packaging. • Design is considered less important by consumers. • Make gender-specific adjustments to the packaging. • Relatively high willingness to pay of business customers. • Differentiating recycled packaging through colour and meeting mechanical property requirements through multi-layer films can create opportunities for brand owners to demonstrate their commitment to sustainability. 	<p>barriers can be a challenge, affecting market uptake and adoption.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerns about the safety and efficacy of new packaging technologies can lead to consumer skepticism and resistance, hindering market penetration and adoption. • High end consumer demands (e.g. transparency of packaging, high recycled content, etc.). • Consumer reluctance to recycle and trust issues. • Negative first impression of packaging made from only partially recycled material by end consumers. • Greenwashing problem: the number of certified products makes it difficult for the uninitiated to identify truly environmentally-friendly packaging. • Resistance to change: Resistance to the adopting new sorting technologies or recycling methods, whether due to cost concerns or reluctance to deviate from traditional practices, threatens the progress of recycling initiatives. • Resistance to change in established waste management practices. • Difficulty in positioning against primary polymers if the value chain does not value environmental aspects, leading to pure price competition and making market entry difficult. • Aesthetic properties and sealing performance are factors that could influence market acceptance of circular packaging.
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Actions needed for better market acceptance

- **Food safety regulations and compliance approval:**
 - Advocate for regulatory reform: Lobby for adjustments to current regulations to better accommodate recycled materials, emphasizing the importance of overall packaging design rather than focusing solely on material specifications.
 - Engage in dialogue with policy makers to advocate for supportive policies that promote sustainable packaging solutions.
 - Strengthen collaboration between industry and government: Work closely with regulatory bodies such as EFSA and the EU Commission to streamline approval processes and ensure regulations are aligned with Circular packaging initiatives.
 - **The legislator triggers changes!**
- **Improve recycling infrastructure:**
 - Invest in improving recycling infrastructure, including collection, sorting, and decontamination processes, to ensure a cleaner input stream and address concerns about the quality of recycled materials
 - Rapid scalability and investment required to adapt infrastructure
- **Collection and sorting infrastructure:**
 - Work with stakeholders to establish efficient, large-scale collection systems to ensure the availability of sufficient raw materials for recycling processes.
 - Invest in advanced sorting technologies and infrastructure to improve the quality of recyclates and enable the separation of materials into desired grades for recycling.

- Optimise sorting and collection processes through the implementation of deposit schemes, take-back schemes and innovative sorting technologies.
- **Enhance collection infrastructure:**
 - Promote deposit or return schemes: Implementing deposit or take-back schemes to incentivise consumers to return packaging, especially for materials such as PE, can be very helpful in improving collection rates & increasing purity in recycling, similar to successful examples seen in other regions.
- **Invest in advanced sorting technologies:**
 - Promote marker-based sorting for food packaging: While marker-based sorting may be feasible for large brands, there is a need to explore strategies to overcome barriers to wider adoption, particularly among smaller retailers or brands. This could include working with industry stakeholders and policy makers to develop supportive frameworks and incentives for industry to upgrade to advanced sorting technology.
 - Collaborate with ongoing projects like the Holy Grail and Perfect Sorting to leverage innovative sorting techniques and share best practices.
- **Entropy management:**
 - Develop strategies to manage entropy and complexity in recycling processes to ensure efficient recovery of materials and minimize waste.
 - Collaborate with industry partners and research institutions to explore entropy management techniques, particularly in deinking and delaminating processes.
- **Optimize functional barrier composition:**
 - Investigate the composition of functional barriers, focusing on nanocoating as a reliable option. Address challenges associated with other polymers, such as evaluation criteria and potential contamination with unknown polymers.
 - Prioritize food safety by implementing documentation and verification processes to prevent contamination in recycled food packaging, particularly when using polyolefins.
 - Notify the functional barrier to EFSA as a novel technology
- **Brand owners:**
 - Engage Brand owners in areas where taxes are imposed on plastic packaging, as legislation is the driving force for brands to invest in circular packaging solutions.
 - Machinability is key. Installed machines have high dwell time and power. If there is a need to change the line, it's very expensive and there is less willingness to adapt.
 - Sorting technology: Convince brand owners of the advantages of tracer technology.
- **Consumer engagement:**
 - Develop targeted marketing and information campaigns to increase consumer awareness and acceptance of sustainable packaging and recycling. As a result, consumers will be encouraged to prioritize products with sustainable packaging and to participate in recycling programs.
 - These campaigns should be tailored to specific demographics, taking into account gender differences in preferences and attitudes, e.g. women tend to be more interested in a fresh look, symmetry and natural colours.
 - Develop a comprehensive communication strategy to inform stakeholders about the added value of the solution provided by Circular FoodPack, including its contribution to sustainability, resource conservation, and waste reduction.
 - Also highlight the technical advances and innovations in collection, sorting, and recycling processes to demonstrate the project's impact and potential.
 - Highlighting the environmental benefits of recycling and Circular packaging, emphasizing the reduction of plastic waste and the positive impact on the environment.
 - Implement consumer-centric initiatives such as refill and prefill approaches, which enhance convenience and promote food safety while supporting the Circular economy.
 - Establish channels for ongoing consumer engagement and feedback to monitor attitudes and preferences towards sustainable packaging over time. Using surveys, focus groups,

and social media platforms to gather insights from consumers and adapt strategies accordingly. This continuous feedback loop could help ensure that packaging solutions remain relevant and appealing to consumers.

- Enable customers to make more environmentally-friendly and circular purchase decisions.
- **Optimise product design:**
 - Use consumer preferences for packaging materials (compare with chapter 4.5), design elements and features to optimise the design of sustainable packaging. For example, prioritise the use of biodegradable materials and natural colours, and incorporate design elements such as symmetry and recycled looks. Ensure that packaging is perceived to be strong and recyclable, as these are key factors in reducing environmental impact.
- **Price competitiveness:**
 - Identify opportunities to streamline production processes and reduce costs to offer competitive prices for Circular packaging products.
 - Explore strategies to maintain competitive prices, such as modest price increases of 10-20% where feasible, while ensuring that any price adjustments remain acceptable to consumers, brand owners, and processors.
- **Market penetration strategy:**
 - Target markets with strong collection infrastructure and material sources, such as Germany, France, the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, Norway, Sweden, and Finland.
 - Consider smaller markets, such as the Netherlands for initial implementation due to easier adoption of innovation and focus on Circular initiatives.
- **Market expansion strategies:**
 - Start with specific applications: Begin with concepts targeting specific applications or limited markets to demonstrate feasibility and build momentum for broader implementation, gradually expanding into new product categories.
 - Collaborate with brand owners: Partner with brand owners to integrate Circular packaging solutions into their product lines, using their influence and commitment to sustainability to drive market acceptance and adoption.
- **Focus on target applications:**
 - Explore entry-level options such as dry products (e.g., pasta) and high volume applications with low to medium barrier requirements (e.g., crisps, chocolate).
 - Prioritize frozen food products, especially those stored in deep freeze conditions like vegetables and fries, for initial packaging efforts due to low migration risk.
- **Expand focus to non-food products:**
 - Recognize the potential of Circular packaging solutions for non-food products and explore opportunities to expand the scope beyond food packaging. This could involve developing tailored strategies and initiatives to promote Circularity in non-food product packaging while leveraging the simplicity offered by Circular packaging solutions
- **Invest in research and development:**
 - Allocate resources to research and development efforts aimed at continuous improvement of solutions developed in Circular FoodPack, including material optimization, process innovation, and technology advancements. Stay at the forefront of innovation in sustainable packaging solutions.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

By the first round of expert interviews and the consumer focus groups, we got valuable insights. The implementation of the methods was successful and the intermediate results confirm the research strategy.

The general feedback of the experts can be summarized in three points:

- Challenges in technology novelty, set up and upscaling were mentioned,
- Challenges regarding the legal regulations when it comes to food-grade recycling are well known,
- The market potential of a successful project and product is rated as very high.

This feedback shows that the challenges we are taking on in this project are well known and that the interest in finding solutions in the industry is high.

The second round of interviews with experts in the field provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of the solution aimed for in Circular FoodPack. The experts were generally positive about the solutions introduced by Circular FoodPack, considering it to be innovative and comprehensive, particularly in promoting Circularity in packaging and integrating recycle while meeting regulatory standards. However, they also raised concerns about various hurdles, including the implementation of marker-based sorting, the composition of functional barriers and the need for a robust recycling infrastructure. Key requirements for Circular packaging were highlighted, such as regulatory compliance, effective sorting methods and the creation of fit-for-purpose packaging. Challenges related to food safety regulations, consumer behavior and competitive pricing were identified, highlighting the complexity of implementing Circular packaging solutions. Concerns were also raised about the selection of appropriate barriers for different foods, the presence of unintentionally added substances in recycled materials, and the overall sustainability of complex multi-layer structures.

The assessment of market opportunities for Circular packaging underlines its high potential, particularly in the food sector, driven by increasing demand and impending legislation favouring recyclability. Despite challenges such as food safety regulations and consumer perception, targeting large multinational companies is recommended due to their influence and ability to absorb costs. Mainstream applications such as frozen food are suggested for initial implementation, with a focus on markets such as Germany, France and the UK due to their advanced collection systems. Coffee and chocolate are identified as suitable products, albeit challenging, with potential for EFSA approval. While business customers may accept higher prices, political support is crucial. The competitive landscape highlights the need for timely approval and scaling up against alternative technologies. Overall, Circular packaging offers promising opportunities but requires strategic targeting, regulatory compliance and competitive pricing for successful market integration.

Brand owners are increasingly evaluating sustainable packaging options such as CIRCULAR FoodPack, emphasising the importance of safety, compliance and sustainability. While there is strong interest in these solutions, opinions vary on cost and material performance. Key challenges include reduced efficiency, higher costs associated with mono-materials and limited recycling infrastructure. Experts stress the importance of achieving a 50/50 balance between recycled and virgin materials to meet

regulatory requirements, particularly under the evolving Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). They also highlight the potential of new technologies, such as AI, to reduce reliance on costly tracer solutions. While improvements in recycling processes, such as deodorisation and deinking, are noted, there are still concerns about residual ink and odour affecting packaging quality, particularly in consumer-facing contexts. Despite regulatory pressures and taxes on virgin plastics, consumer reluctance to pay more for circular packaging solutions complicates the market landscape. Retailers tend to resist price increases for sustainable options, making it difficult for brands to manage costs effectively. Overall, the demand for circular packaging is strong. However, overcoming the challenges of pricing, consumer behaviour and market readiness is critical for successful implementation.

From a consumers' perspective, a lack of information and knowledge could be detected showing trust issues and confusion about recycled packaging. Furthermore, a general aversion against plastic packaging and a limited willingness to pay more for recycled packaging, could be observed. It can be derived, that the information and communication strategies regarding the packaging composition must be carefully established, and a decision of whether or how recycled content is reported at all should be made.

Convenience and practicability are among of the most important features for consumers about packaging. A preference of unpacked products or alternative materials like paper is clearly pronounced by consumers, which might be competitive to the Circular plastic packaging being developed in this project.

Overall, it could be observed that the consumers are concerned by environmental issues and challenges, which shows the relevance of the development of more environmentally-friendly packaging. In this respect, they are open for communication, but a thorough communication strategy is needed to inform them about the usefulness and dispel their doubts about the Circular packaging solution provided by Circular FoodPack, especially Circular food packaging like the targeted ground coffee, chocolate powder e.g.

The quantitative consumer web survey provided important insights into consumer preferences and acceptance of sustainable packaging. Biodegradable packaging material emerged as the most popular choice, followed closely by recycled plastic, bio-based packaging and cardboard. Preferences tended towards a symmetrical, recycled look with natural colours and more information, with women showing slightly stronger preferences towards the previous mentioned attributes. Stability and recyclability were key attributes valued by consumers. On average, respondents were willing to pay around 12-13% more for sustainable packaging, with a modest correlation between willingness to pay and environmental awareness. There was also a significant correlation between consumer confidence in new product development and perceived product safety. In addition, increased awareness of sustainable packaging was associated with higher purchase frequency. Overall, there was a weak positive correlation between waste separation conscientiousness and positive attitudes towards sustainable packaging, suggesting a slightly stronger association for women. These findings highlight the importance of considering gender differences and environmental attitudes in sustainable packaging initiatives.

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7. ANNEX

7.1 Product brief status August 2023

CIRCULAR FoodPack

Specification of circular packaging

**Ecozept
Status August 2023**

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003806.

09/08/2023

EU-project: CIRCULAR FoodPack Circular Packaging for Direct Food Contact Applications

- Coordinator: Fraunhofer IVV
- Beneficiaries: 14 partners
- Type of Action: RIA
- EU contribution: 5.37M €
- Duration: 42 months

- Analysis of European Waste Streams
- **Tracer-Based Sorting** for food/non-food packaging
- Improved pre-treatments by **washing, deinking, deodorization, purification**
- Adjusted **recycling technologies** (mechanical recycling and CreaSolv[®])
- Assessment of **food compliance** by migration modelling
- **Innovative functional barriers**
- Design for recyclability with PCR
- **Proof of concept** in three demo-loops
- Target: food packaging & HPC

 <https://www.circular-foodpack.eu> 2

Structure of the product brief

Slide 4	Targeted products in the project
Slide 5	Developed and applied technologies
Slide 6	State of the art: Multi-layer packaging
Slide 7	Aims of the project
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Slide 15	TRLs
Slide 16	Roadblocks and risks – Awareness of the Consortium
Slide 17	Circular FoodPack links and contact person

Targeted products

Food products:

- Chocolate powder
- Coffee
- Single serve creamer stick pack

Non-food products:

- Wet wipes
- Detergent
- Face mask

Developed and applied technologies

Goal: Novel recyclable PE mono-material packaging concepts with post-consumer recyclates (PCR). The structure will guarantee the safe use in its next lifecycle. The innovations include:

1. Technology for tracers and novel sensors for improved sorting (ready to use on industrial sorting lines with minor adaptations) and specification of the waste stream [Polysecure, KIT and IRIS]
2. De-inking, delamination and purification processes for the novel packaging materials, the processes are compatible with the conventional waste treatment processes [Siegwerk, Ghent University, IVV and SUEZ]
3. Thermally assisted deodorization treatment for PCR [Kreyenborg]
4. Recycling process optimization based on mechanical and solvent based recycling (CreaSolv®) [Maastricht University and IVV]
5. Challenge test to predict contaminant behavior in packaging containing PCR [IVV and Nestle]
6. Development of functional barriers by migration modeling (to enable safe implementation of PCR) [Amcor, Nestle and IVV]

State of the art: Multi-layer packaging

- Conventional multi-layer flexible packaging is efficient: combines properties of materials to thin, lightweight packaging solutions for food and non-food products
- **Issues:** conventional multi-layer flexible packaging is rarely recycled to high quality material with existing waste management infrastructure
- **Challenges:** create recyclable packaging with PCR_s that is as efficient in terms of barrier properties, thickness, product safety, etc. as virgin packaging
- **Need:** Redesign of multi-layer flexible packaging for recyclability and circularity

Aims of the project

Develop PE based mono-material flexible food packaging containing high-quality PCR.

- Innovative designs of recyclable and food-safe mono-material laminates.
- PCR coming from tracer marked food packaging as high-value PE source.
- Integration of PCRs in high-value film applications with functional barriers.
- The functional barrier will enable safe implementation of PCRs and improve gas and water vapor barrier performance.
- The laminate will fulfil all the functional requirements, e.g. oxygen, water vapor transmission, sealability, machinability and mechanical properties.

Design of Novel PE Based Mono-Materials for Circularity

- Novel packaging concepts for recyclability
- Polyethylene content > 90% for mono-material design
- Thin inorganic layer for (functional) barrier
- Deinkable inks in combination with delamination primer
- Tracers for efficient sorting

Note: Not final film structure, only examples of material combinations!

- **Functional barrier** is a combination of a very thin (~60 nm) inorganic and an organic layer. It provides protection towards oxygen and water vapor. Therefore no change in comparison to the conventional packaging materials regarding this. The difference is in the sequence of the layers used within the final laminate.
- Design for **Recycling and Circularity** is being followed and evaluated
- **Food conformity!**

Demo use-cases

Achieve a circular material loop for each of the packaging concepts, where the material is identified and regranulated into a resin suitable for reuse in the same/similar packaging application, with a focus on keeping food packaging materials separate from non-food mater.

The pack is targeted to be recyclable meaning mono-material PE (90%PE according to the Ceflex design for recycling guidelines) in combination with a barrier material that helps to preserve the targeted shelf life of the packed product and enables to use PCR.

Demonstration Loop 1: High level cascade recycling: food and non food packaging to Home & Personal Care

Demo use-cases

Demonstration Loop 2: Circular Food packaging: Based on B2B collection (closed loop)

Demonstration Loop 3: Circular Food packaging into circular food packaging

Demo use-cases

Loop1:

- **Input waste:** Conventional (post-consumer) flexible packaging waste
- **Output material:** PE PCR
- **Final packaging material:** Recyclable PE (90%) based laminate including PCR (at least 50% in the laminate)
- **Final product type:** Home & Personal Care products

Demonstration Loop 1: High level cascade recycling: food and non food packaging to Home & Personal Care

Demo use-cases

Loop2:

- **Input waste:** Business-to-business collected PE-based (post-consumer) coffee packages
- **Output material:** PE PCR
- **Final packaging material:** Recyclable PE (90%) based laminate including PCR (at least 50% in the laminate). The design of the material is tailored for PCR incorporation. PCR comes from the collected food packaging waste.
- **Final product type:** Coffee packages

Demonstration Loop 2: Circular Food packaging: Based on B2B collection (closed loop)

Demo use-cases

Loop3:

- **Input waste:** Conventional (post-consumer) flexible packaging waste mixed with traceable PE-based post-consumer food packaging items
- **Output material:** PE PCR
- **Final packaging material:** Recyclable PE (90%) based laminate including PCR (at least 50% in the laminate). PCR comes only from traced food packaging. The design of the packaging material is tailored for PCR incorporation.
- **Final product type:** coffee packages, packed chocolate powder, creamer, etc.

Loop3 has 2 cycles: Cycle 1 and Cycle 2.

In Cycle 1, input waste is conventional post-consumer flexible packaging waste mixed with traceable PE-based post-consumer food packaging items (no PCR included in the packaging items)

In Cycle 2, input waste is conventional post-consumer flexible packaging waste mixed with traceable PE-based post-consumer food packaging items including PCR.

Demonstration Loop 3: Circular Food packaging into circular food packaging

Benefits of the circular packaging

1. Recyclable food packaging using existing infrastructure of collection, sorting etc.
2. Capability to introduce recycled material of high quality in food and non-food packaging in a safe way while minimizing the LCA impact
3. Effectively upscaling the recyclate quality/value to become competitive with virgin grades
4. Effectively reducing the direct dependence on fossil fuel based materials
5. Enabling the transition of plastic food packaging solutions from a linear economic model to a closed loop Circular Economy

TRLs

Technology	TRL (initial → target)
(i) Sorting	
Tracer-Based-Sorting (TBS) for food packaging waste	4 (start) → 5 (current) → 6 (target)
Sensor-based Specification (SBS)	4 (start) → 5 (target)
(ii) Pre-treatment & Recycling	
Thermally induced decontamination of sorted waste plastics	3-4 (start) → 5 (current) → 6 (target)
Solvent-based recycling for multi-layered food packaging materials	4 (start) → 5 – 6 (target)
New ink designs for de-inking with washing techniques	4 (start) → 5 (target)
(iii) "Design for circular food packaging": Mono- material based multi-layer packaging concept for food packaging, sortable, recyclable	
Mono-material multi-layers for food packaging with PE PCR:	3-4 (start) → 6 (target)
Migration modelling and assessment of suitable highly effective functional barriers	4(start) → 5 (current) → 6 (target)

Roadblocks and risks - Awareness of consortium

Risk and Roadblocks	Status	Mitigation
New other sustainable flexible packaging developments make the CIRCULAR FoodPack developments less attractive	Several flexible packaging developments exist with paper-based, or bio-plastic based materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results can be used to fulfil the product requirements that are difficult to achieve with those materials (for example wet foods or foods requiring high barrier properties). CFP will enable the incorporation of PCRs that all the new materials can benefit from.
"Advanced" chemical recycling	Tendency exists for the recycling of food packaging items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Treat carefully and assess (e.g. LCA/LCC comparisons, ...) Infrastructure for chemical recycling not available yet to provide the recycling of all food packaging waste.

Thank you!

If you have any further questions regarding the interview procedure, the project or the products developed in Circular FoodPack, we are at your entire disposal!

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7.2 Interview guidelines for expert interviews

Delphi I: CIRCULAR FoodPack: Guideline for expert interviews for assessment of market opportunities

Last update 19.09.2022

Important preliminary remark

The interviewees will have to sign the consent form if they agree to participate in the study. Please make sure that he or she has received the lime survey link and agreed to the terms before the interview. If it is not the case, remind the expert to open the e-mail and click on the link to fill in their personal information and agree to the displayed terms.

In case the interviewee cannot respond to the question asked, you should first ask him or her if another person within her or his company could answer this question and who it would be. If no one can answer the question, just document it in the records that they do not know the answer.

Name:	Organisation:	Country:
Date:	Job:	Application:
Consent form signed:		
Interviewer:		
<i>Only for interview administration. Results will be treated anonymously.</i>		

Formatting guide

Purple: Question to be adapted to the expertise of the interviewee

Italic: Bridge text, to be read aloud

(Finding optimized and sustainable (food) packaging solutions is one of your daily challenges. The CIRCULAR FoodPack project enables the transition of plastic food and personal care packaging solutions from a linear economic model to a closed loop Circular Economy by targeting some of the most critical enablers in the value chain through technological innovations. We are now identifying the market potential for the innovations of CIRCULAR FoodPack to meet the needs and expectations of the packaging industry.)

We thank you very much that you are taking time for this interview. It is important for us to get insights from professionals of the sector. You can obtain a free copy of the resume of this study.

I will document this interview in written form by typing your answers directly into a document and your answers will of course be treated confidentially and your answers still stay anonymously.

In the CIRCULAR FoodPack project, Ecozept is responsible for the market studies. If you have in-depth questions about the technologies, we are happy to clarify these in consultation with the project partners after the interview.

Is the procedure clear to you? Do you have any questions? Then I will directly start with the first question.

Introduction

1. To begin with, please briefly describe your company/institution and your position regarding (food) packaging.

In preparation for the interview, we sent you a product description for the food packaging/ packaging that is developed in the CIRCULAR FoodPack's project.

Do you still have it? If not, I'll send it to you right away.

[Interview instruction regarding product brief: make notes if the interviewee comments on the product descriptions, but do not get into depth; if the interviewee did not read the brief or doesn't remember, go there element by element]

2. Please describe your first impressions of the product that you gained from the product brief.

Do you think that this kind of product is a way to overcome the current limitations of multilayer flexible packaging?

Which are the main benefits of the product? Where do you see an added value of the product?

Are there important characteristics missing about the product? Are significant/important functions missing?

In how far do you think that it has advanced characteristics compared to similar products?

Focus

3. Which requirements and expectations do you have to a recycled packaging for food/personal care products?

How do you assess (food-)packaging from recycled PE that is coated with virgin material?

How do you assess tracer-based sorting in order to produce (food-)packaging from recycled PE?

How do you assess deinking and deodorization processes for (food-)packaging from recycled PE?

Which expectations must be met (e.g., barrier functions, food safety, etc.)? In comparison to conventional/non-recycled packaging?

What does the industry want/need?

Which are the basic requirements with regard to recycled packaging? Differences for food and non-food packaging?

4. **How do you assess the acceptance of the product in the industry/B2B sector?** Which factors could limit the acceptance of this multi-layer packaging with the combination of recycled and virgin material? Circular packaging? What actions would be needed/factors influenced in order to increase market acceptance?
5. **How do you assess the market opportunities for this Circular packaging?** (In terms of quality? In terms of price? In terms of migration and barriers? In terms of competition? etc.)
6. **Please describe challenges that have to be overcome/ conditions that must be fulfilled in order to introduce this kind of multi-layer packaging with the combination of recycled and virgin material for food/ non-food products to the European markets?**
(Technological constraints? Regulatory constraints? Price constraints? Competitive products? Constraints regarding applications? Infrastructural constraints? etc.)

Nice-to-have-questions (if there is enough time left)

7. **Who could be the target group of this packaging? (B2B customers)**
Could you name priorities of target groups?

Could you rank the target groups in terms of importance in the packaging sector?
8. **In how far do you assess that a price premium will be accepted by business customers?**
Which expectations do you have from a premium priced product in terms of quality?
9. **For which kind of products might this described packaging be suitable?**
Could you give some examples/priorities of applications? Why are these applications especially suitable?
10. **Do you know companies or organizations who are working on a similar product to the CIRCULAR FoodPack packaging?**
If yes: Can you describe this similar product please? (Name, raw material, applications, description of the producer, etc.) Do you assess these products as direct competition to the CIRCULAR FoodPack product? Are other materials more interesting in the packaging industry right now instead of recycled PE?
11. **Coming back to our packaging. Are there aspects of the market for recycled packaging that are relevant for you, but that we did not consider in our interview? Could you specify them please?**

Closing (organizational) questions

12. Do you know further experts (producers, distributors, and users or other specialist) who would be interested to participate in the survey?

13. Are you interested in receiving a summary of the results of this study? This document will of course not disclose any confidential information.

This discussion is now over. We thank you for your participation.

Delphi II: CIRCULAR FoodPack: Guideline for expert interviews for assessment of market opportunities

Last update 12.10.2023 (JL)

AF: Important preliminary remark

The interviewees will have to sign the consent form if they agree to participate in the study. Please make sure that he or she has received the lime survey link and agreed to the terms before the interview. If it is not the case, remind the expert to open the e-mail and click on the link to fill in their personal information and agree to the displayed terms.

In case the interviewee cannot respond to the question asked, you should first ask him or her if another person within her or his company could answer this question and who it would be. If no one can answer the question, just document it in the records that they do not know the answer.

Name:	Organisation:	Country:
Date:	Job:	Application:
Consent form signed:		
Interviewer:		
<i>Only for interview administration. Results will be treated anonymously.</i>		

Formatting guide

Purple: Question to be adapted to the expertise of the interviewee

Italic: Bridge text, to be read aloud

(Finding optimized and sustainable (food) packaging solutions is one of your daily challenges. The Circular FoodPack project enables the transition of plastic food and personal care packaging solutions from a linear economic model to a closed loop Circular Economy by targeting some of the most critical enablers in the value chain through technological innovations. We are now identifying the market potential for the innovations of Circular FoodPack to meet the needs and expectations of the packaging industry.)

We thank you very much that you are taking time for this interview. It is important for us to get insights from professionals of the sector. You can obtain a free copy of the resume of this study.

I will document this interview in written form by typing your answers directly into a document and your answers will of course be treated confidentially.

In the Circular FoodPack project, Ecozept is responsible for the market studies. If you have more detailed questions about the technologies, we are happy to clarify these in consultation with the project partners after the interview. Is the procedure clear to you? Do you have any questions? Then I will directly start with the first question.

1. Introduction

1. To begin with, please briefly describe your company/institution and your position regarding (food) packaging.

In preparation for the interview, we sent you a product description for the food packaging/ packaging that is developed in the Circular FoodPack's project.

Do you still have it? If not, I'll send it to you right away.

[Interview instruction regarding product brief: make notes if the interviewee comments on the product descriptions, but do not get into depth; if the interviewee did not read the brief or doesn't remember, go there element by element]

2. Please describe your first impressions of the product that you gained from the product brief. Do you think that this kind of product is a way to overcome the current limitations of multilayer flexible packaging?

Which are the main benefits of the product? Where do you see an added value of the product?

Are there important characteristics missing about the product? Are significant/important functions missing?

In how far do you think that it has advanced characteristics compared to similar products?

2. Focus

3. Please describe the requirements for Circular packaging for food/ non-food products?

How do you assess the requirements for (food-)packaging from recycled PE that is coated with virgin material?

Which expectations regarding safety and hygienic aspects must be met (e.g., barrier functions, food safety, etc.)? Differences between food packaging than for non-food packaging?

Which are the basic requirements with regard to recycled packaging?
Differences for recycled packaging and new packaging?

Compared to new packaging?

4. How do you assess the reprocessing of recycled PE for food packaging? (after use)

5. Which sorting process do you consider useful for the production of recycled PE for food packaging?

6. How do you assess the market opportunities for Circular packaging (introduced in product brief) for **food/ non-food products**?

(In terms of food safety regulations? In terms of technical challenges? In terms of food vs. non-food products? In terms of functional barrier and migration? etc.)

What is the most promising approach?

What is the biggest market barrier? (Compliance with food safety regulations or : Technical challenges)

Which are the best applications/ Which applications are inappropriate for use? (dry products/ wet product, liquids, odour-producing, etc.)

Which are the best products?

In which markets can Circular packaging be applied? (Potential regional markets, **food/ non- food**, market to start with, etc.)

7. Please describe challenges that have to be overcome/ conditions that must be fulfilled in order to introduce this kind of multi-layer packaging with the combination of recycled and virgin material **for food/ non-food products** to the European markets?

(For example: Technological constraints? Regulatory constraints? Price constraints? Competitive products? Constraints regarding applications? Infrastructural constraints? What is the biggest challenge to overcome? etc.)

3. Nice to have

8. For which kind of products might this described packaging be suitable?

To what extent do you think the packaging is suitable for chocolate and coffee?

9. Do you know companies or organizations who are working on a similar product to the Circular FoodPack packaging?

If yes: Can you describe this similar product please? (Name, raw material, applications, description of the producer, etc.)

Do you assess these products as direct competition to the Circular FoodPack product? Are other materials more interesting in the packaging industry right now instead of recycled PE?

10. Coming back to our packaging. Are there aspects of the market for recycled packaging that are relevant for you, but that we did not consider in our interview? Could you specify them please?

7.3 Guideline for consumer focus groups (English version)

Focus group: CIRCULAR FoodPack

Timeframe:

16.00 h	Welcome of participants
16.15 h	Official opening Introduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Background and objectives of the focus group - Presenting instructions - Focus group interaction and discussion
17.45 h	End of structured / facilitated discussion - closure - final comments
18.00 h	Conclusion, thanks

Context and problem of the study: To assess consumers' expectation, acceptance and preferences regarding packaging for food and non-food products Material

- Paper A 4
- Pens/ markers

Instructions:

I'm going to ask you some questions: do not overthink and just say what you think.

- It is your personal opinion that interests us (say "I" and not "people")
- Speak up, not all at once
- **Do not interrupt each other!**
- All opinions are interesting; no one is right or wrong (we don't censor ourselves, we don't censor others)
- MOBILE PHONES SWITCHED OFF
- If you have any questions, we will be happy to answer them (if possible) at the end of the exercise.
- **Warm-up round: the moderator introduces her-/himself, thereafter every participant introduced her-/himself: everyone writes their name on a card and tells what he or she works and what he/she likes to do in his/her spare time**

Goal: Identifying consumers' acceptances, preferences and expectations with regard to packaging of food and non-food products

5 min	Introduction/warm-up/know each other/breaking the ice: see instructions above
PART 1: Packaging I – preferences and expectations (35 min)	
20 min	<p>Objective: to identify consumers' preferences regarding food packaging</p> <p>When you are doing grocery shopping, what is the food packaging that is attractive for you, and which package do you avoid? Why?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does this apply for dry products, e.g., rice and coffee powder? • How does this apply for fruits and vegetables?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does this apply for dairy products? • How does this apply for drinks? <p>Do you prefer your food product packaged in a new plastic packaging or recycled one? And why?</p> <p>When you think about personal care products (like detergent, etc.) and cosmetics, how are these packaging issues different for you? How does this apply for cosmetics?</p>
20 min	<p>Objective: to identify consumers' expectations regarding food packaging</p> <p>Imagine you are doing grocery shopping. What do you pay attention to when you buy packaged food? What is important to you with regard to food packaging?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality parameters • Contamination • Freshness preservation • Packaging design • Material • Advantages • Disadvantages • Differences between product categories (dry / wet / chilled / frozen; dairy / fruits and vegetables / meat / convenience food / etc.) <p>Imagine a food product that you buy regularly. Now imagine that this product is packaged in recycled plastic packaging. Would you buy it anyway or would you not buy it anymore? Would you prefer the product with recycled packaging or with packaging that is new? Which packaging would be the ideal from your point of view? Also with regard to environmental issues?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability • Low environmental footprint • Recyclable • Deposit system • Other <p>Would you spend more money for a more environmentally-friendly food packaging? Why? How much?</p> <p>What is important to you regarding the conceptional design of the food packaging?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resealable • With outer packaging • Partial portions • Opening/opening device • Etc. <p>When you think about personal care products, like detergents or wet wipes, in how far do you have different expectations to the packaging? And for cosmetics?</p>
PART 2: Packaging I – acceptance and further issues (35 min)	

20 min	<p>Objective: to identify consumers' acceptance regarding food packaging What do you think of food that is packed in materials that was already used? Recycled several times? That is a mixture of recycled or fresh materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Positive associations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmentally-friendly ▪ Fighting plastic waste ▪ Circularity ▪ No waste of resources ○ Negative associations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Threat to safety and health
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ "Dirty" ▪ Cheap ○ Neutral associations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ I don't care ▪ As long as it fulfils its functions... ▪ That already exists <p>What is the most sustainable packaging in your opinion? And why? What do you think about personal care products like detergents or wet wipes that are packed in materials that are recycled? How about cosmetics?</p>
20 min	<p>Objective: Identify consumers' motivation/needs/after purchase decision Do you separate your packaging waste? Why? Do you always know which packaging goes to which bin? If no, why not? What confuses you? What would help you to separate your packaging waste easier? What would be your personal problem regarding plastic packaging?</p>
5 min	Thank the participants, give them information about the use of the data collected

7.4 Guideline for consumer web survey (English version)

Questionnaire for consumer web-survey: consumers' preferences, expectations and acceptance

Dear participants,

As part of the EU project "Circular FoodPack", Ecozept is conducting a survey on a new recyclable packaging material for food, especially for coffee and cocoa. Through this project, a way is sought to address the problems caused by packaging. The aim is to find out consumers' preferences, expectations and acceptance of the new product.

In order to integrate packaging into the long-term material cycle, the "Circular FoodPack" project has developed a new packaging that meets the strict requirements of food legislation and can be used safely for food. This packaging material consists of two layers, a hybrid approach so to speak. The outer layer is made of recycled plastic and accounts for 90%. The inner layer accounts 10 %, serves as a protect barrier and is made of new, very thin plastic, which is 100 % recyclable.

Recyclable means that the material, especially plastic in our case, can be completely reused after use. We characterize 'sustainable packaging' as beneficial throughout its entire lifecycle which is safe and healthy for individuals and communities. They are produced, transported, and recycled using renewable energy, while maximizing the use of renewable or recycled source materials, which can be effectively reused and recycled in biological or industrial loops. The goal of sustainable packaging is to promote a more environmentally-friendly and resource-efficient utilization while ensuring the health and safety of people (Nguyen et al., 2020).

The survey will take a maximum of 10 minutes to complete. Please note that all data will be used for scientific purposes only. Furthermore, it will of course be kept anonymous and confidential.

Thank you very much for your participation in this survey and for interest in sustainable packaging solutions.

Socio-demographic questions

1. Please indicate your gender

- A Male
- B Female
- C Other

2. Year of birth.....

3. Living situation/ area

- A City
 B Suburbs
 C Rural region

4. Education Show answer option according the repective country

- A Primary Education
 B Secondary education
 C Journeyman
 D Master craftsman
 E Bachelors or equivalent level
 F Masters or higher education

5. Number of persons in the household?

Number of persons in the household?

Please specify?

Adults older than 18 years Children below 18 years.....

I do not want to answer

6. Total household income per year (before tax)?

- A Less than 30.000 EURO
 B 30.000 – 59.999 EURO
 C 60.000 - 89.999 EURO
 D 90.000 – 119.999 EURO
 E 120.000 EURO or more
 F I would not like to tell

7. How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement: “Sustainable packaging materials can solve the environmental issues of plastic such as microplastic, threats to marine habitats or air pollution. 1 (“I strongly disagree”) to 5 (“I strongly agree”)

1	2	3	4	5	Don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>					

8. Do you see yourself as individuals with a duty to be proactive about sustainable packaging or the framework conditions (e.g., legislation, food retail) ? Please move the slider to the degree that reflects how you see yourself.

9. Please indicate how important the following features are for you regarding packaging of food. Please move the slider to the degree that reflects your opinion from “not important at all” to “very important”.

1.	Transparency of packaging (I want to see the food product through the packaging)	Not important at all Very important
2.	Convenience (e.g., easy to open and close, that it does not take too much space, etc.)	Not important at all Very important
3.	Lightness (I want the product to be as light as possible)	Not important at all Very important
4.	Design (e.g., natural colours, recycled look, handy)	Not important at all Very important
5.	Stability (I want the packaging to protect the product)	Not important at all Very important
6.	That it can be recycled (packaging can potentially go through a recycling process)	Not important at all Very important
7.	That it is made from recycled material (packaging is made out of recycled material)	Not important at all Very important
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not care about the packaging		

If there is another important feature regarding your packaging preferences, please indicate so:

10. Which material for packaging for coffee and cocoa do you prefer? Please move the slider to the degree that reflects your opinion from “disfavored very much” to “preferred very much”.

1.	Glass	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
2.	Paper/ carton	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
3.	Aluminium	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
4.	Plastic	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
5.	100% Recycled plastic	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
6.	Hybrid Model (90 % recycled plastic, 10 % new plastic)	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
7.	Unpacked	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
8.	Biobased packaging (= at least partwise made from renewable resources, e.g. plant biomass)	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
7.	Biodegradable packaging (= material degrades completely by microorganisms to water, CO ₂ and biomass)	Disfavored very much		Preferred very much
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not care				

If there is another type of packaging that you prefer, please indicate so: _____

11. Do you buy coffee or cocoa? If yes, how often do you look for sustainable packaging when shopping these items? 1 (“never”) to 5 (“always”)

1	2	3	4	5	Don't know	I don't buy coffee of cocoa
<input type="checkbox"/>						

12. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements on a scale from 1 ("I strongly disagree") to 5 ("I strongly agree").

		1	2	3	4	5	Don't know
1.	For me, the food product is essentially more important than the packaging.	?	?	?	?	?	?
2.	The type of packaging for food products is absolutely decisive for my purchase decision.	?	?	?	?	?	?
3.	The design of the packaging for food products is absolutely decisive for my purchase decision.	?	?	?	?	?	?
4.	I do not care about packaging when I do grocery shopping.	?	?	?	?	?	?
5.	I would buy the same food products as usual regardless of their packaging.	?	?	?	?	?	?
6.	If the packaging of a food product that I usually buy changes, I would strongly reconsider my purchase decision.	?	?	?	?	?	?
7.	Packaging is very important because it protects the product.	?	?	?	?	?	?
8.	It is unnecessary to pack every food product.	?	?	?	?	?	?
9.	I would totally approve if innovative, sustainable packaging is used for the food products I usually buy.	?	?	?	?	?	?
10.	I love testing new product developments in the field of sustainable food packaging	?	?	?	?	?	?
11.	I trust new packaging in terms of safety	?	?	?	?	?	?
12.	New technologies, such as new packaging material, are associated with higher costs.	?	?	?	?	?	?

13. Which design characteristics do you like best for sustainable/Circular food packaging? Please move the slider to the according to degree that best reflects your opinion.

Natural colours	<input type="range"/>	Flashy colours
Restrained design	<input type="range"/>	Eye-catching design
Minimalistic information/text on packaging	<input type="range"/>	As much information/text as possible on the packaging
«Recycled» look	<input type="range"/>	New look
Symmetric	<input type="range"/>	Asymmetric

14. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements on a scale from 1 ("I strongly disagree") to 5 ("I strongly agree").

		1	2	3	4	5	Don't know
1.	I have a very positive attitude towards sustainable packaging.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
2.	Recycling of packaging is very important for Circular economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
3.	I unconditionally trust claims of packaging providers when they say their packaging is recycled.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
4.	I am convinced that recycling of plastic packaging is impossible.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
5.	I would prefer recycled packaging for food products if I had the choice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
6.	I am convinced that recycled packaging for food is unhygienic.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
7.	I would be willing to pay more for recycled packaging.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
8.	The recycling of packaging is essentially important for protection of the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
9.	I would rather choose biodegradable packaging instead of recycled packaging.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

15. How much more would you pay for the following packaging for coffee and cocoa?

		< 5 %	5	10	20	< 25%	I am not willing to pay a surcharge
		<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Cardboard	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Biodegradable	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Recycled	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Recyclable	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Hybrid Models like Circular Food Pack (10 % new Plastic, 90 % recycled)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Biobased	<input type="checkbox"/>					

16. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements on a scale from 1 ("I strongly disagree") to 5 ("I strongly agree").

		1	2	3	4	5	Don't know
1.	I want to know if the packaging of a food product I buy is recycled or not.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
2.	I would approve if a food packaging is made from 100 % recycled content.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
3.	I would approve if a food packaging is made from 90 % recycled content and 10 % new material.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
4.	I want to know to which degree the packaging of a food product that I buy is made from recycled content.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
5.	If a food packaging is only partwise made of recycled content, it's not trustworthy.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
6.	Communication about recycled packaging is very important for me.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
7.	I prefer to have information about the recycling content of the packaging directly on the packaging.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
8.	I always pay attention to labels about sustainable product packaging when I buy groceries. E.g. Recycling Symbol, EU Ecolabel, Fairtrade, EU-Bio Logo	<input type="checkbox"/>					

17. Which of the following information help you choose products in terms of packaging? 1 ("not helpful at all") to 5 ("very helpful")

		1	2	3	4	5	Don't know
		<input type="checkbox"/>					
EU Ecolabel (Ökoblume)							
Recycling-Symbol							
Fairtrade							
EU-Bio Logo							
Rainforest Alliance							

UTZ certified etc.)								
Green force								
Further explanations on the packaging								

18. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements on a scale from 1 ("I strongly disagree") to 5 ("I strongly agree").

		1	2	3	4	5	Don't know
1.	I know very well how I should dispose of my food packaging waste.	?	?	?	?	?	?
2.	I do absolutely correctly dispose of my food packaging waste.	?	?	?	?	?	?
3.	There is sufficient infrastructure for correct disposal of my food packaging waste (e.g., presence of respective containers for packaging waste) near my house.	?	?	?	?	?	?
4.	I do not correctly dispose of my food packaging waste because there is a lack of respective infrastructure.	?	?	?	?	?	?
5.	It is way too much effort for me to correctly sort and dispose my packaging waste.	?	?	?	?	?	?
6.	It is absolutely worth the effort to separate my household packaging waste and dispose of it accordingly.	?	?	?	?	?	?
7.	I am perfectly aware of the consequences that packaging waste has on the environment.	?	?	?	?	?	?
8.	I feel very concerned about the impacts of packaging waste on the environment.	?	?	?	?	?	?

19. How do you assess your knowledge of sustainable packaging 1 ("no knowledge") to 5 ("perfect knowledge").

1	2	3	4	5	Don't know
?	?	?	?	?	?

20. What benefits do you see in recycled plastic? Choose the three most important.**Multiple choice**

- Promotion of the Circular economy
- Reducing dependence on petroleum
- Reduction of environmental pollution

- Energy saving
- Landfill waste reduction
- Reduce CO₂ emissions
- Varietal purity
- Other
- None of this

